
Zircon Geothermometry and Zr-mineral saturation in natural magmas using rhyolite-MELTS

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Introduction

Zircon geothermometry is an important tool for estimating pre-eruptive temperatures in magmatic systems (Putirka and Tepley, 2008 [12]). Existing zircon geothermometers (Watson and Harrison, 1983 [17]; Boehnke et al., 2013 [1]; Gervasoni et al., 2016 [4]) are formulated using empirical models calibrated from experimental data on saturation conditions of zircon in magmatic silicate melts. In this paper we formulate an extension of the thermodynamic model for silicate liquids contained in rhyolite-MELTS (Ghiorso and Gualda, 2015 [6]; Gualda et al., 2012 [8]; Ghiorso and Sack, 1995 [7]) to account for the saturation state of zircon and related Zr-minerals as functions of temperature (T) and pressure (P) for compositions of naturally occurring magmatic liquids. We adopt thermodynamic properties of the zirconium-bearing minerals zircon and baddeleyite from Robie et al. (1995 [13]) and calibrate an internally consistent liquid model using the experimental data of Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) and Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]). The resulting model is applied as a zircon geothermobarometer and is utilized to estimate saturation conditions of zircon in phase assemblages forming in silicic magmatic systems.

Model Formulation

Ghiorso and Sack (1995 [7]) posited a functional form for the Gibbs Free Energy of magmatic composition silicate liquids that was largely based on the model of Ghiorso et al. (1983 [5]). Their model assumes that the thermodynamic properties of naturally occurring silicate liquids can be approximated using simple multi-component regular solution theory on the predicate that thermodynamic components are appropriately chosen to represent “mineral-like” stoichiometric compounds. They calibrated this model using experimental phase equilibrium data. The silicate liquid model of Ghiorso and Sack (1995 [7]; hereafter, MELTS) was not altered in the development of the rhyolite-MELTS model (Gualda et al., 2012 [8]) that extends MELTS to highly silicic magmatic compositions. The addition of oxidized carbon to the liquid model by Ghiorso and Gualda (2015 [6]) did require modification to the underlying thermodynamic formalism for the liquid phase. A thermodynamic component (CO₂) and a dependent species (CaCO₃) were added to account for the presence of both molecular CO₂ and carbonate in silicate melts. The addition of a carbonate species necessitated recasting of the regular solution model into a non-ideal associated solution (Ghiorso and Gualda, 2015 [6]).

The addition of Zr to the liquid model of Ghiorso and Gualda (2015 [6]) requires the selection of a Zr-bearing thermodynamic component. We adopt ZrSiO₄, because we assumed that Zr and Si form a strong association in the melt, and because the thermodynamic properties of the solid phase of equivalent stoichiometry (zircon) are well known (Robie et al., 1995 [13]). Experimental studies (Watson, 1979 [16]) and petrological observations (Nicholls and Carmichael, 1969 [11]) demonstrate that there is a strong relationship between the alkali-content of a melt and its capacity to hold Zr in solution under conditions of zircon saturation. In a series of elegant experiments on melts of widely varying alkali-contents, Watson (1979 [16]) established that alkali-zirconate species of stoichiometry four alkalis to one Zr likely form. The formation of these species effectively lowers the mole fraction of ZrSiO₄ in the melt, thereby lowering that component's chemical potential, which has the effect of understauring the melt in zircon. Watson (1979 [16]) suggested that species Na₄ZrSi₂O₈ and K₄ZrSi₂O₈ account for the sequestration of zirconium in alkali-rich magmas. It is interesting to note that the stoichiometry of these species is not reflected in the stoichiometry of alkali-metal, zirconium-bearing minerals that form in magmatic systems (e.g. wadeite, Zr₂K₄Si₆O₁₈, Carmichael, 1967 [2]), nor to the suppposition of Linthout (1984 [9]) that melt species of zirconium should likely reflect alkali-zirconate mineral stoichiometry.

We extend the associated solution model of Ghiorso and Gualda (2015 [6]) to include the species Na₄ZrSi₂O₈ and K₄ZrSi₂O₈. Thermodynamic components of the extended model, additional melt species and component-species transformations are summarized in Table 1.1. Reactions,

represent conditions of homogeneous equilibrium, permitting concentrations of melt species to be calculated by zeroing the Gibbs Free Energy change of all three reactions at specified T, P and bulk composition. The last two reactions demonstrate that reduction in the chemical potential (activity) of silica in the melt encourages the transfer of Zr to both alkali-zirconate species.

Using the notation summarized in Table 1.1, the Gibbs Free Energy of solution may be written:

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \mu_i^o + RT \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \log \left(\frac{y_i}{y_T} \right) + y_w RT \log \left(\frac{y_w}{y_T} \right) + (y_T - y_w) RT \log \left(\frac{y_T - y_w}{y_T} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T} \quad (1)$$

where n_i denotes moles of the i^{th} component and y_i moles of the i^{th} species. n_T is defined as $\sum_{i=1}^{17} n_i$ and y_T as $\sum_{i=1}^{20} y_i = n_T - y_{19} + y_{20}$. μ_i^o denotes the chemical potential of the i^{th} species in the standard state, here taken to be the pure substance at any T and P. R is the universal gas constant, and $W_{i,j}$ refers to temperature and pressure independent regular-solution energetic parameters. The number of moles of H₂O (either n_w or y_w) is treated specially in Eq(1) to account for its dissolution in the melt as two hydroxyl species (derivation in Ghiorso et al., 1983 [5]).

Differentiation of Eq (1) with respect to n_{ZrSiO_4} results in our model expression for the chemical potential of the ZrSiO₄ endmember component:

$$\mu_{\text{ZrSiO}_4} = \mu_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^o + RT \log \left(\frac{y_{\text{ZrSiO}_4} (y_T - y_w)}{y_T^2} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,\text{ZrSiO}_4} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2} \quad (2)$$

Evaluation of Eq (2) requires (1) a functional form and parameterization of $\mu_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^o (T, P)$, (2) estimated values for

$W_{i,j}$, and (3) solution of the three conditions of homogeneous equilibrium,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial y_{CaCO_3}} \right)_{n_i} &= 0 \\ \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial y_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}} \right)_{n_i} &= 0 \\ \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial y_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}} \right)_{n_i} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

to determine equilibrium concentrations of species mole numbers (y_{CaCO_3} , $y_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $y_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$) for a given bulk composition (n_i).

Eq (2) may be utilized to compute the saturation chemical affinity for zircon,

$$A^{zircon} = \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{liquid} - \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{o,zircon} \quad (4)$$

or equivalent zirconium-bearing solid phase, with solid-liquid heterogeneous equilibrium (saturation) achieved when A^{zircon} is zero.

Data Sources for Parameter Calibration

We consider four principal sources of experimental data on zircon saturation for calibration of the model: (1) the original exploratory study of Watson (1979 [16]), (2) the followup study that constructed the first comprehensive calibration database by Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]), (3) the study by Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]) that extended the experimental dataset to 2.5 GPa, and (4) the more recent study of Gervasoni et al. (2016 [4]) that focused on alkaline and aluminous melts. Of these four studies, the two of Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) and Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]) will be used for model parameter calibration. Watson (1979[16]) focused on understanding alaki-zirconate speciation in melts and to do so utilized synthetic-, compositionally-restricted systems. While his results are valuable in that they illuminate the effect of alaki content on zircon saturation, his liquid compositions lie outside of the applicable compositional domain of the MELTS model and consequently cannot be used to provide quantitative constraints. The experimental study of Gervasoni et al. (2016 [4]) extends the compositional range of natural liquids beyond that investigated previously, however, the liquids underwent near 100% iron-loss to the capsules during each experimental run, raising the likelihood that the experiments never achieved equilibrium. Tellingly, the zircon saturation geothermometer calibrated by Gervasoni et al. (2016 [4]) yields results on meta-aluminous high silica rhyolites dramatically at odds with previous models based on the Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) and Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]) datasets. This observation suggests that the three datasets are mutually inconsistent, and we choose to utilize as calibrants the two studies whose results are less problematic.

Calibration

Assumptions

Our model expression for the chemical potential of the $ZrSiO_4$ component (Eq (2)) will be parameterized under the following assumptions:

(1) To be compatible with Ghiorso and Gualda (2015 [6]; and consequently MELTS and rhyolite-MELTS) the standard state properties of all non-zirconium bearing liquid components and species will be adopted from Ghiorso and Sack (1995 [7]) as modified by Ghiorso and Gualda (2015 [6]). In addition, all regular solution interaction parameters not involving zirconium-bearing species will be adopted from the same source. By so doing we choose to render our Zr-liquid model

calibration internally consistent with rhyolite-MELTS 1.1 (Ghiorso and Gualda, 2015 [6]), which permits calculation of mixed H₂O-CO₂ fluid saturated melt, yet preserves phase equilibrium relations associated with the two-feldspar-quartz, water-saturated ternary minimum.

(2) There are 19 species interaction parameters like $W_{ZrSiO_4,i}$, another 19 like $W_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8,i}$, and another 19 like $W_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8,i}$. As there are not enough calibration data of sufficient compositional variability to constrain all but a few of them, we will assume that all 57 of these parameters have values of zero. This assumption is supported by the observation that all naturally occurring magmatic liquids have low concentrations of Zr, making it a trace species of low mole fraction. Consequently, energetic contributions to the Gibbs Free energy via the regular solution terms involving zirconium-bearing species will be minimal; Henrian non-ideality will be accounted solely by the standard state and entropic terms in Eqs (1) and (2).

(3) We will assume that $\mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o$ can be parameterized as

$$\mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o = \Delta H_{ZrSiO_4} - T\Delta S_{ZrSiO_4} + (P-1)\Delta V_{ZrSiO_4} + \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{o,zircon} \quad (5)$$

where ΔH_{ZrSiO_4} , ΔS_{ZrSiO_4} , and ΔV_{ZrSiO_4} are model parameters that account for the offset of the enthalpy, entropy and volume from the solid in the liquid state. Similarly, we will assume that $\mu_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o$ can be parameterized as

$$\mu_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o = \Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} - T\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} + (P-1)\Delta V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} + \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o + 2\mu_{Na_2SiO_3}^o - \mu_{SiO_2}^o \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are additional model parameters that account for the non-coplanarity of the standard state free energy of the reciprocal reaction:

Similarly, $\mu_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o$ can be parameterized as

$$\mu_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o = \Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8} - T\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8} + (P-1)\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8} + \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o + 4\mu_{KAlSiO_4}^o - 2\mu_{Al_2O_3}^o - 3\mu_{SiO_2}^o \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are model parameters that account for the non-coplanarity of the standard state free energy of the reciprocal reaction:

These simplifying assumptions yield a nine-parameter model expression for evaluation of the liquid chemical potential term in Eq (4). For the Zr-bearing solid phases, we adopt thermodynamic properties of zircon and badeleyite from Robie et al. (1995).

Method

The fitting procedure used to calibrate the model requires an initial guess of parameter values. We evaluate Eq (4) for each datum in Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) and Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]) using a data reduction workflow documented in the accompanying Jupyter notebook (*6-Calibration: MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*). Using a linear least squares procedure from the statmodels Python package (Seabold and Perktold, 2010 [14]), we estimate preliminary values of ΔH_{ZrSiO_4} , ΔS_{ZrSiO_4} , and ΔV_{ZrSiO_4} that minimize residuals of the chemical affinity and negate any temperature or pressure dependence to those residuals. Next, from the conditions of homogeneous equilibrium (Eq (3)) we estimate equilibrium concentrations of melt zirconium-bearing species and choose values of $\Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ and $\Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ so that all species have concentrations within three orders of magnitude of each other. The objective of this exercise is to construct an initial guess speciation model that does not embody a bias towards the dominance of a particular melt species. Initial values of $\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are set to zero.

Parameter refinement is obtained utilizing the trust region non-linear least squares method of the optimize module in the SciPy Python package (Virtanen et al., 2020 [15]). On initial refinement, two issues emerged. First, the parameter

correlation matrix confirmed our expectation that derived values of ΔS_{ZrSiO_4} , $\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are highly correlated; ΔV_{ZrSiO_4} , $\Delta V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ and $\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are also highly correlated. This data driven observation allows us to make the simplifying assumption that $\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are zero, which results in the temperature and pressure dependence of $\mu_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o$ and $\mu_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o$ to be modeled by ΔS_{ZrSiO_4} , and ΔV_{ZrSiO_4} , respectively, reducing the parameterization of the model to five unknowns. The second issue that emerged from initial refinement is that the relative abundance of Na₄ZrSi₂O₈ dominated that of K₄ZrSi₂O₈ by orders of magnitude, and did not reflect the relative abundance of Na and K in the experimental glass composition. This result runs contrary to the observation of Watson (1979 [17]) who concluded that alkali-zirconate speciation is independent of the identity of the alkali. Further parameter refinement clearly requires a constraint to be adopted that implements the priors observation of Watson (1979 [17]).

Parameter refinement proceeded by adding an additional residual for each experimental observation of the form:

$$w_p \log \left(\frac{\frac{2n_{12}}{n_{13}}}{\frac{y_{19}}{y_{20}}} \right) \quad (8)$$

which corresponds to a weighted (w_p) Bayesian logistics function that forces analytical vales of Na/K ($\frac{2n_{12}}{n_{13}}$) to reflect model estimates of (Na,K)-zirconate species abundance ($\frac{y_{19}}{y_{20}}$). The weighting is chosen to make the logistic residual the same oder of magnitude as the affinity residual, ~2500 J.

Calibration results in the parameter values provided in Table 2.1 and the variance-covariance matrix reported in Table 3.1. The standard deviation of recovery of zircon affinities is 3756 J/mol.

Quality of fit is evaluated in Fig. 5.1, Fig. 6.1 and Fig. 7.1. Fig. 5.1 demonstrates that residuals in zircon affinity show no correlation to alakli-content of the liquid, nor to temperature and pressure. The lack of temperature and pressure dependence of residuals supports our simplifying assumption that $\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ may be set to zero. The absence of residual correlation to alkali-content implies that alkli-zirconate speciation accounts for the alkali-effect on the “effective-concentration” (i.e., the activity) of ZrSiO₄ in alkali-rich liquids. Fig. 6.1 demonstrates recovery of Zr liquid concentration, calculated by adjusting liquid Zr-content in order to zero zircon affinity, plotted against measured values. Estimated Zr concentrations scatter about a 1:1 line plotted against reported concentrations. There is no systematic change in scatter of predicted versus measured value as a function of Zr-concentration over two orders of magnitude. Fig. 7.1 illustrates recovery of priors residuals for the regression data set. While priors residuals are small (fall close to the green line) for typical Na/K melt ratios, there is significant deviation at elevated Na/K. The consequences of these deviations may effect recovery of zircon phase relations in phonolitic or pantelleritic composition melts with high Na/K, and this issue will be further examined below.

Discussion

The model calibrated above is evaluated in this section by constructing zircon saturation curves for a variety of natural magma types and by examing zircon saturation in conjunction with phase equilibrium calculations using an augmented rhyolite-MELTS model.

Zircon Saturation Curves

Bulk compositions of a wide variety of silicic magma types are listed in Table 4.1. This tabulation includes determinations of Zr concentration. Bulk compositions listed in the first four columns of Table 4.1 are likely zircon saturated, whereas magma types listed in columns five through ten are not associated with a zircon solid phase. The madupite and wyomingite represent extreme compositions and are saturated with the zirconium-bearing mineral wadeite, Zr₂K₄Si₆O₁₈, which forms in lieu of zircon in these rocks.

For each magma type listed in Table 4.1 a zircon saturation curve is constructed and plotted in Fig. 4a *High-silica rhyolite* through Fig. 4j *Wyomingite*. For each sub-figure, the mean zircon saturation curve is plotted along with its 5% and 95%

quartile. Calculations are based on a Monte Carlo propagation of uncertainties using parameter estimates constructed from the variance-covariance matrix of Table 3.1. The right-most panels display abundances of zirconium-bearing species in the melt with equivalent quartile estimates.

At reported Zr concentrations, saturation conditions for fluid-saturated high-silica rhyolite (Bishop Tuff, Fig. 4a *High-silica rhyolite*) are similar to those estimated using the empirical geothermometer of Watson and Harrison (1983). Saturation conditions for the Iceland rhyolite (Thingmuli, Fig. 4b *Icelandic rhyolite*) are consistent with expected higher-temperatures of these lavas given their lower water contents. The Iceland rhyolite also has a higher Na/K ratio than its continental equivalent. The northern California rhyolite displayed in Fig. 4c *California rhyolite* has saturation conditions similar to the Bishop magma, and the dacite (Fig. 4d *Dacite*) is undersaturated with zircon at the expected storage temperature conditions, but Zr contents are consistent with saturation for a rhyolitic residuum of this bulk composition.

Despite their high Zr-concentrations, peralkaline rhyolites in Table 4.1 (a pantellerite from Pantelleria and a comendite from Mayor Island, NZ) are not saturated with zircon. Water contents for the pantellerite (Lowenstern and Mahood, 1991) are ~1.8 wt% and consequently the inferred solidus temperatures are high, perhaps comparable to Icelandic rhyolites. Reported Zr abundances in these lavas (1800 and 2300 PPM, respectively) suggest model zircon saturation temperature below ~750°C (Fig. 4e *Pantellerite*) and ~870°C (Fig. 4f *Comendite*). Arguing from the basis of phase relations for the ferromagesian silicates and the absence of Fe-Ti oxides associated with these lavas, Nicholls and Carmichael (1969 [11]) conclude that likely liquidus temperatures fall between 900°C and 1025°C. Given that water contents of the magma indicate strongly undersaturated conditions, the solidus is likely to be within 100°C of liquidus. Our model predictions of zircon saturation are consistent with these conclusions, indicating that Zr-concentration is barely sufficient to saturate these lavas with zircon prior to eruption.

Model saturation curves for trachyte (Fig. 4g *Trachyte*) and phonolite (Fig. 4h *Phonolite*) reveal that Zr-concentrations must be on the order of a weight percent in order to saturate these liquids with zircon. An additional observation is that the shape of the saturation curves is strongly influenced by temperature. To understand why, consider that these liquids simultaneously have higher absolute concentrations Zr and Na and higher Na/K ratios; the Na-zirconate species has abundance comparable to ZrSiO₄. Assuming x is the fraction of Na-zirconate species and $1 - x$ is the fraction of ZrSiO₄, the dissolution of zircon proceeds via the reaction:

The temperature dependence of zircon saturation is consequently a reflection of the entropy of this dissolution reaction, which is

$$\Delta S = x \bar{s}_{\text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8}^{\text{liquid}} + (1 - x) \bar{s}_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^{\text{liquid}} + x \bar{s}_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liquid}} - 2x \bar{s}_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liquid}} - \bar{s}_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^{\text{zircon}} \quad (9)$$

The standard state entropy change contribution to Eq (9) is zero under the model calibration assumptions made previously, so, this expression reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &\approx -xR \log X_{\text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8} - (1 - x) R \log X_{\text{ZrSiO}_4} - xR \log X_{\text{SiO}_2} + 2xR \log X_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3} \\ &\approx -R \log \left(\frac{X_{\text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8}^x X_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^{1-x} X_{\text{SiO}_2}^x}{X_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{2x}} \right) = -R \log \left(X_{\text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8}^x X_{\text{ZrSiO}_4}^{1-x} \right) - Rx \log \left(\frac{X_{\text{SiO}_2}}{X_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

if we consider non-ideal contributions to the Gibbs Free Energy to be second order. If z is the total mole fraction of all zirconate species, then $X_{\text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8}$ is approximately zx and X_{ZrSiO_4} is approximately $z(1 - x)$, and Eq (10) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &\approx -R \log \left[z^x x^x z^{1-x} (1 - x)^{1-x} \right] - Rx \log \left(\frac{X_{\text{SiO}_2}}{X_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^2} \right) \\ &= -R \log z - R \left[x^x (1 - x)^{1-x} \right] - Rx \log \left(\frac{X_{\text{SiO}_2}}{X_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The last logarithmic term in Eq (11) is a linear function of the fraction of Na-zirconate species (x) and for the trachyte bulk composition is approximately $-41x$ J. The first term has a value of approximately 40 J, but decreases as Zr concentration

in the melt increases. The central term has a positive maximum at $x = \frac{1}{2}$ of ~ 6 J and falls parabolically to zero at lower or higher Na-zirconate mole fractions.

This analysis allows us to better understand the shape of the zircon saturation curves for the trachyte and phonolite. A positive slope for these curves requires a positive ΔS , as the dissolution reaction must go to the right as temperature increases, and in previous cases, where the total mole fraction of Zr-bearing species in the liquid is very low, the first term in Eq (11) dominates and the saturation curves have a positive slope. However, as the Zr-concentration in the melt increases, the dominance of the first term diminishes, the contribution of the second and third terms become significant in determining the sign of the entropy change. In particular, if the fraction of Na-zirconate species decreases with increasing T , then the third term in Eq (11), which is negative, is more likely to dominate the expression and lead to a turnover in the saturation curve. The conclusion is that higher overall concentration of Zr in the liquid coupled with the presence of near equal abundances of Na-zirconate and ZrSiO₄ species, governs the unusual shape of the zircon saturation curves. If these magmas did saturate with zircon, its presence would lead to an unsatisfactory geothermometer.

The final magma types considered, maduïte (*Fig. 4i Maduïte*) and wyomingite (*Fig. 4j Wyomingite*), represent bulk compositions with extremely high K/Na ratios. Neither magma precipitates zircon, but both form a Zr-bearing phenocryst phase, wadeïte. Reported concentrations of Zr are at the 2000 PPM level. Our model calculations suggest that measured concentrations are about an order of magnitude below those required to saturate zircon, and that Zr is predominantly present as both K-zirconate and ZrSiO₄ species in the melt.

The calculations summarized in *Fig. 4a High-silica rhyolite* through *Fig. 4j Wyomingite* were performed at a pressure of 200 MPa. The effect of pressure on these results is insignificant, e.g. for the high-silica rhyolite assuming 100 PPM Zr in the liquid, the saturation temperature is 744.7°C at 100 MPa, 745.5°C at 200 MPa, 745.9°C at 300 MPa. This effect is typical for all compositions examined.

Phase Equilibria

As the calibrated model is compatible with rhyolite-MELTS (v. 1.1), we may use it to calculate phase equilibria in zircon-bearing assemblages. In *Fig. 9.1* phase proportions during crystallization of a high-silica rhyolite (*Table 4.1*) are illustrated. The workflow for this calculation is documented in *7-Phase equilibria: MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*.

The most notable feature of the phase diagram presented in *Fig. 9.1* is that the onset of zircon saturation is at 757.4°C in contrast to the calculated geothermometer temperature of 745.9°C (see below). This temperature difference is due largely to the effect of expulsion of fluid and the crystallization of two feldspars and quartz, which elevates the concentration of the incompatible element Zr in the liquid, permitting saturation of zircon at higher temperature. This temperature discrepancy highlights the likelihood that application of zircon geothermometry to bulk rock compositions is problematic, even when such compositions are representative of near eutectic melts. In practical terms, the uncertainty in calculated phase relations is large enough to encompass these temperature differences, but the relative offset is important to consider, and every effort should be made to utilize high quality glass analyses to avoid systematic bias.

Geothermometry

Software is available to utilize the model presented here as a geothermometer (*6-Calibration: MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*). In *Fig. 10.1* through *Fig. 10.4* we use this software to calculate apparent experimental temperatures for the calibration data set and for the data set of Gervasoni et al. (2016 [4]). These results provide an alternative measure of how well the model recovers the calibration data set, and suggests some potential problems with attainment of equilibrium in the data set of Gervasoni.

Temperature estimates for the calibration data set are plotted in *Fig. 10.1* with data from Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) isolated in *Fig. 10.2* and selected low-Zr experiments from Boehnke et al. (2103 [1]) displayed in *Fig. 10.3*. Experimental values with uncertainties are plotted in red and temperature estimates with model uncertainties are plotted as yellow polygons, with a green dot at the most likely value. The inset on each panel shows model temperature estimates

with associated 5% and 95% quartiles, computed using the average analytical Zr concentration, plotted against reported experimental temperature.

Model temperature estimates scatter about experimental temperatures for Zr liquid concentrations below 4000 PPM. Above that concentration, the model tends to overestimate temperature. This failure is probably related to our model formulation assumption that regular solution interaction parameters involving Zr-species are zero, implicitly rendering the model applicable to a Henrian concentration limit. This assumption could be relaxed in order to accommodate these data, but there are so few data points at higher Zr-concentrations available for calibration that the danger of overfitting does not warrant this extension. Model error in temperature estimates due to parameter error propagation is -7.3°C , $+8.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5%, 95%) for the Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) data set (Fig. 10.2), with the average error in recovered experimental temperature of -14°C ($\pm 35^{\circ}\text{C}$). Including measured uncertainty in Zr concentration brings the average recovered temperature within the range -34°C (Zr - 2 sigma) to 4°C (Zr + 2 sigma) with the standard deviation of the low and high estimates maintained at the same level as the average Zr value. For the Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]) data set (Fig. 10.3, ignoring the 4 data points above 4000 PPM Zr), the recovery of temperature estimates due to parameter error propagation is -11.6°C , $+10.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5%, 95%). The average error in recovered experimental temperature is -15°C ($\pm 41^{\circ}\text{C}$) with the range $-17^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 35^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Zr - 2 sigma) to $-5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 39^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Zr + 2 sigma).

Temperature recovery of the data set of Gervasoni et al (2016 [4]), which was not used in calibration, is shown in Fig. 10.3. Note that model temperatures are overestimated for glass compositions with > 6000 PPM Zr, as found with the data set of Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]). At experimental temperatures of 1200°C at Zr concentrations > 2500 PPM and < 6000 PPM, temperature recovery is comparable to the calibration data sets. At lower Zr concentrations and at lower temperatures, temperature recovery is systematically biased. The experimental data set of Gervasoni et al. (2016) differs from the calibration data sets in showing almost complete iron-loss to the experimental capsule. In addition, these experiments were conducted under nominally dry conditions (unlike the other two studies) and run durations were relatively short (24 hrs). Considering the absence of volatiles, which would aid reaction kinetics, all these factors support our contention that equilibrium was not achieved in the lower temperature, lower Zr-content runs. In fact, the partial agreement at 1200°C for the subset of “intermediate” Zr concentration experiments may simply be fortuitous.

Model Access

The model and dependent calculations presented here can be replicated in full utilizing the associated Jupyter notebooks: 1-Theory: *Adding Zr to the MELTS liquid model*, 1-Endmembers: *MELTS Liquid Components Standard State Code Generator*, 2-Coding: *MELTS liquid model with zirconium*, 4-Tests: *MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*, 5-Initial parameter estimates: *MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*, 6-Calibration: *MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*, 7-Phase equilibria: *MELTS liquid model with ZrSiO₄*. These notebooks will execute on an ENKI enabled server platform (<http://enki-portal.org/index.html>) or, more conveniently, within a containerized image implementation of the ThermoEngine software ecosystem (the ENKI software engine) that may be downloaded from GitLab’s Docker image container repository at <https://gitlab.com/ENKI-portal/ThermoEngine>. The container will execute on any computer that has a recent version of Docker (<https://www.docker.com>) installed.

Conclusions

This paper updates MELTS (v 1.1) to account for phase relations involving the trace element Zr. The saturation surface for zircon is calibrated using experimental data from Watson and Harrison (1983 [17]) and Boehnke et al. (2013 [1]). The model is formulated and optimized for Zr melt concentrations in the effective Henrian limit (< 4000 PPM) and accounts for the effect of alkalis on zircon saturation via the adoption of an associated solution formulation that incorporates three Zr-bearing melt species: ZrSiO₄, Na₄ZrSi₂O₈, and K₄ZrSi₂O₈. The model may be used (1) to calculate zircon phase relations in magmatic composition melts, (2) to construct zircon saturation diagrams for a given liquid bulk composition, and (3) as a geothermometer for zircon bearing igneous rocks.

Aknowledgements

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Part I

Tables

TABLE 1 SOLUTION MODEL: COMPONENTS, SPECIES AND MAPPINGS

Table 1.1: Solution model: Components, species and mappings

Components:	Species:	Component:	Species X:
SiO ₂	SiO ₂	n_1	$y_1 = n_1 + y_{18} + y_{19} + 3 y_{20}$
TiO ₂	TiO ₂	n_2	$y_2 = n_2$
Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	n_3	$y_3 = n_3 + 2 y_{20}$
Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	n_4	$y_4 = n_4$
MgCr ₂ O ₄	MgCr ₂ O ₄	n_5	$y_5 = n_5$
Fe ₂ SiO ₄	Fe ₂ SiO ₄	n_6	$y_6 = n_6$
MnSi _{1/2} O ₂	MnSi _{1/2} O ₂	n_7	$y_7 = n_7$
Mg ₂ SiO ₄	Mg ₂ SiO ₄	n_8	$y_8 = n_8$
NiSi _{1/2} O ₂	NiSi _{1/2} O ₂	n_9	$y_9 = n_9$
CoSi _{1/2} O ₂	CoSi _{1/2} O ₂	n_{10}	$y_{10} = n_{10}$
CaSiO ₃	CaSiO ₃	n_{11}	$y_{11} = n_{11} - y_{18}$
Na ₂ SiO ₃	Na ₂ SiO ₃	n_{12}	$y_{12} = n_{12} - 2 y_{19}$
KAlSiO ₄	KAlSiO ₄	n_{13}	$y_{13} = n_{13} - 4 y_{20}$
Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	n_{14}	$y_{14} = n_{14}$
H ₂ O	H ₂ O	n_{15}	$y_{15} = n_{15}$
CO ₂	CO ₂	n_{16}	$y_{16} = n_{16} - y_{18}$
ZrSiO ₄	ZrSiO ₄	n_{17}	$y_{17} = n_{17} - y_{19} - y_{20}$
	CaCO ₃		y_{18}
	Na ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈		y_{19}
	K ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈		y_{20}

TABLE 2 SOLUTION MODEL: PARAMETER ESTIMATES

Table 2.1: Solution model: Parameter estimates

Parameter:	Value:	Uncertainty:	Units:
ΔH_{ZrSiO_4}	163044	6506	J
ΔS_{ZrSiO_4}	69.24	5.26	J/K
ΔV_{ZrSiO_4}	0.10	0.0548	J/bar
$\Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	-267990	5511	J
$\Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	-74062	5371	J
$\Delta S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	0	5.26	J/K
$\Delta S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	0	5.26	J/K
$\Delta V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	0	0.0548	J/bar
$\Delta V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	0	0.0548	J/bar

TABLE 3 SOLUTION MODEL: VARIANCE-COVARIANCE MATRIX

Table 3.1: Solution model: Variance-covariance matrix

	$\Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	$\Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	ΔH_{ZrSiO_4}	ΔS_{ZrSiO_4}	ΔV_{ZrSiO_4}
$\Delta H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	3.03716421e+07	2.88194625e+07	3.43669687e+07	2.80147056e+04	1.24200080e+02
$\Delta H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$	2.88194625e+07	2.88456358e+07	3.37646855e+07	2.75552018e+04	1.36610058e+02
ΔH_{ZrSiO_4}	3.43669687e+07	3.37646855e+07	4.23270965e+07	3.40635609e+04	1. 76449856e+02
ΔS_{ZrSiO_4}	2.80147056e+04	2.75552018e+04	3.40635609e+04	2.76605628e+01	1.54646644e-01
ΔV_{ZrSiO_4}	1.24200080e+02	1.36610058e+02	1.76449856e+02	1.54646644e-01	3.00057280e-03

TABLE 4 BULK COMPOSITIONS OF LAVAS (WT%)

Table 4.1: Bulk compositions of lavas (wt%)

	High-silica rhyolite	Iceland rhyolite	California rhyolite	dacite	pan- tel- lerite	comen- dite	tra- chyte	phono- lite	madupite	wyoming- gite
	1	2	2	2	2,3	2	2	2	4	4
SiO ₂	77.5	74.96	75.04	63.58	69.81	73.06	57.73	54.55	43.56	50.23
TiO ₂	0.08	0.23	0.07	0.64	0.45	0.23	1.18	1.60	2.31	2.27
Al ₂ O ₃	12.5	12.55	12.29	16.67	8.59	9.76	17.05	19.00	7.85	11.22
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.207	1.72	0.33	2.24	2.28	2.74	2.55	1.75	5.57	3.34
Cr ₂ O ₃	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.04	-
FeO	0.473	0.71	0.71	3.00	5.76	2.70	4.35	3.78	0.85	1.84
MnO	-	0.04	0.05	0.11	0.28	0.13	0.28	0.16	0.15	0.05
MgO	0.03	0.02	0.04	2.12	0.10	0.10	1.11	1.76	11.03	7.09
CaO	0.43	0.90	0.58	5.53	0.42	0.32	3.10	4.07	11.89	5.99
Na ₂ O	3.98	4.41	4.03	3.98	6.46	5.64	6.81	9.06	0.74	1.37
K ₂ O	4.88	3.65	4.66	1.40	4.49	4.34	4.27	3.64	7.19	9.81
P ₂ O ₅	-	0.04	0.01	-	-	0.02	0.34	0.20	1.50	1.89
H ₂ O	5.5	5.5	5.5	3.00	2.5	2.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0
CO ₂	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Zr PPM	100	385	-	150	1800	-	-	-	2073	2073

¹ Gualda et al. (2012 [8])

² Carmichael et al. (1974 [3])

³ Lowenstern and Mahood (1991 [10])

⁴ Carmichael (1967 [2]) Madupite is LH.16 and contains appreciable wadeite, Zr₂K₄Si₆O₁₈. This rock has 0.27 wt% ZrO₂. The Wyomingite is LH.3. The rock has no Zr analysis but other wyomingites have 0.28 wt% ZrO₂. All the analyses are from Table 12 (page 50)

Part II

Figures

FIGURE 1 MODEL RESIDUALS

Fig. 5.1: Model Residuals (J) plotted against (upper left) sodium content of the liquid, as moles of Na₂SiO₃, (upper right) potassium content of the liquid, as moles of KAlSiO₄, (lower left) temperature (K), and (lower right) pressure (bars). Red crosses correspond to residuals in the chemical affinity for the zircon saturation reaction, and blue crosses correspond to residuals in the Na/K logistic function utilized to enforce the prior that the ratio of Na to K zirconate species abundance is strongly correlated to the measured Na/K ratio in the liquid.

FIGURE 2 ZR CONTENT RECOVERY

Fig. 6.1: Model Reported Zr concentrations (ordinate) plotted against model estimate Zr concentrations (abscissa) for the calibration data set. The estimate is constructed by finding the Zr concentration that zeros the chemical affinity for zircon saturation in the experimental liquid at fixed temperature and pressure.

FIGURE 3 NA/K PRIORS

Fig. 7.1: Model predicted Na/K ratios of alkali-zirconate species in the liquid (abscissa) plotted against measured bulk Na/K ratio in the liquid (ordinate). Green line refers to exact correlation. This constraint is imposed as a logistic on model calibration. See text.

FIGURE 4 ZIRCON SATURATION CURVES

Fig. 8.1: Fig. 4a High-silica rhyolite

Fig. 8.2: Fig. 4b Icelandic rhyolite

Fig. 8.3: Fig. 4c California rhyolite

Fig. 8.4: Fig. 4d Dacite

Fig. 8.5: Fig. 4e Pantellerite

Fig. 8.6: Fig. 4f Comendite

Fig. 8.7: Fig. 4g Trachyte

Fig. 8.8: Fig. 4h Phonolite

Fig. 8.9: Fig. 4i Madupite

Fig. 8.10: Fig. 4j Wyomingite

FIGURE 5 PHASE RELATIONS FOR HIGH-SILICA RHYOLITE

Fig. 9.1: Phase relations for high-silica rhyolite calculated using rhyolite-MELTS (v1.1) and the model presented in this paper. Equilibrium crystallization. Dashed line denotes the onset of zircon saturation at 757.4°C.

FIGURE 6 TEMPERATURE RECOVERY FROM ZIRCON SATURATION DATA SETS

Fig. 10.1: Fig. 6a Temperature recovery for the calibration data set. Red symbols denote reported temperatures and Zr concentration (with uncertainties), green symbols the most likely model temperature. Each green symbol is enclosed by a parallelogram (in yellow) whose vertices are defined by the 5% and 95% quartiles associated with Monte Carlo error propagation of model parameters. The reported and most likely model temperature are connected by a black dashed line for each experimental datum. The inset plots reported temperature against model temperature for the average Zr concentration with error brackets at the 5% and 95% quartile.

Fig. 10.2: Fig. 6b Temperature recovery for the Watson and Harrison (1983) data set. See legend for panel “a”.

Fig. 10.3: Fig. 6c Temperature recovery for the Boehnke et al. (2013) data set. See legend for panel “a”.

Fig. 10.4: Fig. 6d Temperature predictions for the Gervasoni et al. (2016) data set. Experiments are labeled, indicating Zr concentration. Otherwise, symbols are plotted as described for panel “a”.

Part III

Notebooks

1-THEORY: ADDING ZR TO THE MELTS LIQUID MODEL

```
%%html
<style>
  table {margin-left: 0 !important;}
</style>
```

11.1 Regular solution model in *c*-components

Ghiorso MS, Carmichael ISE, Rivers ML, Sack RO (1983) The Gibbs free energy of mixing of natural silicate liquids; an expanded regular solution approximation for the calculation of magmatic intensive variables. *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology* 84, 107-145 and Ghiorso MS, Sack RO (1995) Chemical Mass Transfer in Magmatic Processes IV. A revised and internally consistent thermodynamic model for the interpolation and extrapolation of liquid-solid equilibria in magmatic systems at elevated temperatures and pressures. *Contrib Mineral Petrology* 119, 197-212 and Gualda, G.A.R., Ghiorso, M.S., Lemons, R.V., Carley, T.L. (2012) Rhyolite-MELTS: A modified calibration of MELTS optimized for silica-rich, fluid-bearing magmatic systems. *Journal of Petrology*, 53, 875-890

Components:	Species:	Component:
SiO2	SiO2	n_1
TiO2	TiO2	n_2
Al2O3	Al2O3	n_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3	n_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4	n_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4	n_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2	n_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4	n_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2	n_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2	n_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3	n_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3	n_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4	n_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2	n_{14}
H2O	H2O	n_{15}

The Gibbs free energy of a *c*-component multicomponent regular solution is given by ($n_T = \sum_{i=1}^c n_i$):

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^c n_i \mu_i^o + RT \sum_{i=1}^c n_i \log \left(\frac{n_i}{n_T} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=i+1}^c W_{i,j} \frac{n_i n_j}{n_T}$$

and the chemical potential (the derivative of the above expression) is:

$$\mu_k = \mu_k^o + RT \log \left(\frac{n_k}{n_T} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^c W_{i,k} \frac{n_i}{n_T} - \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=i+1}^c W_{i,j} \frac{n_i n_j}{n_T^2}$$

11.1.1 Add water to this formulation

The MELTS liquid model makes the assumption that H₂O enters the melt completely dissociating to an OH species. That means that for every water molecule, two hydroxyl molecules are produced. The configurational entropy must account for this extra species, so we must modify the expression for the Gibbs Free Energy to account for this.

If n_w is the number of moles of H₂O in the liquid (n_w is one of c -components):

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^c n_i \mu_i^o + RT \sum_{i=1}^c n_i \log \left(\frac{n_i}{n_T} \right) + n_w RT \log \left(\frac{n_w}{n_T} \right) + (n_T - n_w) RT \log \left(\frac{n_T - n_w}{n_T} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=i+1}^c W_{i,j} \frac{n_i n_j}{n_T^2}$$

and the chemical potential (the derivative of the above expression) is:

$$\mu_k = \mu_k^o + RT \log \left(\frac{n_k(n_T - n_w)}{n_T^2} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^c W_{i,k} \frac{n_i}{n_T} - \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=i+1}^c W_{i,j} \frac{n_i n_j}{n_T^2}$$

$$\mu_w = \mu_w^o + RT \log \left(\frac{n_w}{n_T} \right)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^c W_{i,w} \frac{n_i}{n_T} - \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=i+1}^c W_{i,j} \frac{n_i n_j}{n_T^2}$$

11.2 Now add CO₂ to the model (associated solution)

Ghiorso, M.S., Gualda, G.A.R. (2015) An H₂O-CO₂ mixed fluid saturation model compatible with rhyolite-MELTS. Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology, doi:10.1007/s00410-015-1141-8

To do this we need to make an associated solution, using both CO₂ as a new component and CaCO₃ as a new dependent species.

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Component:	Species:
SiO2	SiO2		n_1	$y_1 = n_1 + y_{17}$
TiO2	TiO2		n_2	$y_2 = n_2$
Al2O3	Al2O3		n_3	$y_3 = n_3$
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		n_4	$y_4 = n_4$
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		n_5	$y_5 = n_5$
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		n_6	$y_6 = n_6$
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		n_7	$y_7 = n_7$
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		n_8	$y_8 = n_8$
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		n_9	$y_9 = n_9$
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		n_{10}	$y_{10} = n_{10}$
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		n_{11}	$y_{11} = n_{11} - y_{17}$
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		n_{12}	$y_{12} = n_{12}$
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		n_{13}	$y_{13} = n_{13}$
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		n_{14}	$y_{14} = n_{14}$
H2O	H2O		n_{15}	$y_{15} = n_{15}$
CO2	CO2		n_{16}	$y_{16} = n_{16} - y_{17}$
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$		y_{17}

Note that $n_T = \sum_{i=1}^c n_i = y_T = \sum_{i=1}^s y_i$

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \mu_i^o + RT \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \log\left(\frac{y_i}{y_T}\right) + y_w RT \log\left(\frac{y_w}{y_T}\right) + (y_T - y_w) RT \log\left(\frac{y_T - y_w}{y_T}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T}$$

and the chemical potential (the derivative of the above expression) is:

$$\mu_k = \mu_k^o + RT \log\left(\frac{y_k(y_T - y_w)}{y_T^2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,k} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2}$$

$$\mu_w = \mu_w^o + RT \log\left(\frac{y_w}{y_T}\right)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,w} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2}$$

$$\mu_{\text{CO}_2} = \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^o + RT \log\left(\frac{y_{\text{CO}_2}(y_T - y_w)}{y_T^2}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,\text{CO}_2} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2}$$

The species mole numbers, y_i , must be computed from the component moles, n_i , in conjunction with a condition for homogeneous equilibrium between CO2 and CaCO3.

11.3 Addition of Zr to the model

We posit an associated solution formulation with two alaki-zirconate species (after **Watson EB, 1979, Zircon Saturation in Felsic Liquids: Experimental Results and Applications to Trace Element Geochemistry. Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology, 70, 407-419**):

- Na₄ZrSi₂O₈
- K₄ZrSi₂O₈

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Component:	Species X:
SiO ₂	SiO ₂		n_1	$y_1 = n_1 + y_{18} + y_{19} + 3 y_{20}$
TiO ₂	TiO ₂		n_2	$y_2 = n_2$
Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃		n_3	$y_3 = n_3 + 2 y_{20}$
Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃		n_4	$y_4 = n_4$
MgCr ₂ O ₄	MgCr ₂ O ₄		n_5	$y_5 = n_5$
Fe ₂ SiO ₄	Fe ₂ SiO ₄		n_6	$y_6 = n_6$
MnSi _{1/2} O ₂	MnSi _{1/2} O ₂		n_7	$y_7 = n_7$
Mg ₂ SiO ₄	Mg ₂ SiO ₄		n_8	$y_8 = n_8$
NiSi _{1/2} O ₂	NiSi _{1/2} O ₂		n_9	$y_9 = n_9$
CoSi _{1/2} O ₂	CoSi _{1/2} O ₂		n_{10}	$y_{10} = n_{10}$
CaSiO ₃	CaSiO ₃		n_{11}	$y_{11} = n_{11} - y_{18}$
Na ₂ SiO ₃	Na ₂ SiO ₃		n_{12}	$y_{12} = n_{12} - 2 y_{19}$
KAlSiO ₄	KAlSiO ₄		n_{13}	$y_{13} = n_{13} - 4 y_{20}$
Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂		n_{14}	$y_{14} = n_{14}$
H ₂ O	H ₂ O		n_{15}	$y_{15} = n_{15}$
CO ₂	CO ₂		n_{16}	$y_{16} = n_{16} - y_{18}$
ZrSiO ₄	ZrSiO ₄		n_{17}	$y_{17} = n_{17} - y_{19} - y_{20}$
	CaCO ₃	CO ₂ + CaSiO ₃ = CaCO ₃ + SiO ₂		y_{18}
	Na ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈	ZrSiO ₄ + 2Na ₂ SiO ₃ = Na ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈ + SiO ₂		y_{19}
	K ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈	ZrSiO ₄ + 4KAlSiO ₄ = K ₄ ZrSi ₂ O ₈ + 2Al ₂ O ₃ + 3SiO ₂		y_{20}

The Gibbs Free Energy is formulated as before by the expression

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \mu_i^o + RT \sum_{i=1}^s y_i \log \left(\frac{y_i}{y_T} \right) + y_w RT \log \left(\frac{y_w}{y_T} \right) + (y_T - y_w) RT \log \left(\frac{y_T - y_w}{y_T} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T}$$

and the new chemical potential is given by

$$\mu_{ZrSiO_4} = \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o + RT \log \left(\frac{y_{ZrSiO_4} (y_T - y_w)}{y_T^2} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,ZrSiO_4} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2}$$

11.4 Zircon saturation and model simplification

The expression for the chemical potential of ZrSiO₄ can be rearranged to

$$\mu_{ZrSiO_4} = \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o + RT \log \left[\frac{(n_{ZrSiO_4} - y_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} - y_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}) (y_T - y_w)}{y_T^2} \right] + \sum_{i=1}^s W_{i,ZrSiO_4} \frac{y_i}{y_T} - \sum_{i=1}^s \sum_{j=i+1}^s W_{i,j} \frac{y_i y_j}{y_T^2}$$

This expression shows that stabilizing the alkali-zirconate species decreases the effective concentration of ZrSiO₄ and makes the logarithm term in the chemical potential more negative. Given that zircon saturation requires:

$$\mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{o,zircon} = \mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{liquid}$$

the effect of alkali concentration on the ZrSiO₄ liquid chemical potential is dominated by the logarithmic term if Zr is at low-concentration in the liquid.

Note also that because the alkali-zirconate species concentrations are determined by these two homogeneous equilibrium reactions:

- $ZrSiO_4 + 2Na_2SiO_3 = Na_4ZrSi_2O_8 + SiO_2$
- $ZrSiO_4 + 4KAlSiO_4 = K_4ZrSi_2O_8 + 2Al_2O_3 + 3SiO_2$

when the activity of silica in the melt is low, as is the case for alkali-rhyolites, trachytes, phonolites, etc., both reactions will be driven to the right, which will increase concentrations of the alkali-zirconate species, and lower the effective concentration of ZrSiO₄. The effect of this will be to make $\mu_{ZrSiO_4}^{liquid}$ more negative. Consequently, alkali-rich melts will require more Zr to saturate with zircon!

11.4.1 Now, we make some assumptions about which parameters in the model are likely to be important.

- We will assume that all standard state and regular solution interaction parameters calibrated previously are applicable to this model.
- There are 19 species interaction parameters like $W_{ZrSiO_4,i}$, another 19 like $W_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8,i}$, and another 19 like $W_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8,i}$. It is unlikely that we will have enough calibration data of sufficient compositional variability to constrain all but a few of them. We will assume that the speciation mole fractions in the logarithmic term will be sufficient for calibrating our experimental dataset and set all 57 W-terms to zero.
- We will assume that $\mu_{ZrSiO_4}^o = H_{ZrSiO_4} - TS_{ZrSiO_4} + (P - 1)V_{ZrSiO_4}$, where H_{ZrSiO_4} , S_{ZrSiO_4} , and V_{ZrSiO_4} are model parameters.
- We will assume that $\mu_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o = H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} - TS_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8} + (P - 1)V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, where $H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are model parameters.
- We will assume that $\mu_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}^o = H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8} - TS_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8} + (P - 1)V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, where $H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ are model parameters.

With these assumptions we have a model that requires values of the following nine parameters to be estimated and refined:

- H_{ZrSiO_4} , S_{ZrSiO_4} , and V_{ZrSiO_4}

- $H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$
- $H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$

H_{ZrSiO_4} , S_{ZrSiO_4} , and V_{ZrSiO_4} will be estimated from the properties of zircon and a guess as to the entropy of fusion of zircon.

$H_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{Na_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ will be estimated by assuming that the *standard state Gibbs Free Energy* change of the reaction $ZrSiO_4 + 2Na_2SiO_3 = Na_4ZrSi_2O_8 + SiO_2$ is zero at some average experimental temperature.

$H_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, $S_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$, and $V_{K_4ZrSi_2O_8}$ will be estimated by assuming that the *standard state Gibbs Free Energy* change of the reaction $ZrSiO_4 + 4KAlSi_3O_8 = K_4ZrSi_2O_8 + 2Al_2O_3 + 3SiO_2$ is zero at some average experimental temperature.

Now let's build code for the model and calibrate the parameters from experimental data

1-ENDMEMBERS: MELTS LIQUID COMPONENTS STANDARD STATE CODE GENERATOR

This notebook generates code to implement endmember component thermodynamic properties for a rhyolite-MELTS liquid model extended to include CO₂ and ZrSiO₄

after:Ghiorso MS, Sack RO (1995) Chemical Mass Transfer in Magmatic Processes IV. A revised and internally consistent thermodynamic model for the interpolation and extrapolation of liquid-solid equilibria in magmatic systems at elevated temperatures and pressures. Contrib Mineral Petrology 119, 197-212 and Gualda, G.A.R., Ghiorso, M.S., Lemons, R.V., Carley, T.L. (2012) Rhyolite-MELTS: A modified calibration of MELTS optimized for silica-rich, fluid-bearing magmatic systems. Journal of Petrology, 53, 875-890 and Ghiorso, M.S., Gualda, G.A.R. (2015) An H₂O-CO₂ mixed fluid saturation model compatible with rhyolite-MELTS. Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology, doi:10.1007/s00410-015-1141-8

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import sympy as sym
import math
sym.init_printing()
from thermoengine import coder, phases
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)
```

12.1 Special case SiO₂

```
model = coder.StdStateModel()
model.set_module_name('rMELTS_ZR')
model_type = "calib"
T = model.get_symbol_for_t()
P = model.get_symbol_for_p()
Tr = model.get_symbol_for_tr()
Pr = model.get_symbol_for_pr()
```

G(liquid) Tr, Pr -> G(liquid) Tg, Pr

```
h0, s0 = sym.symbols('h0 s0')
params = [('h0', 'J', h0), ('s0', 'J/K', s0)]
GPr = h0 - T*s0
model.add_expression_to_model(GPr, params)
```

```
al,b1,c1,d1,tg = sym.symbols('al b1 c1 d1 tg')
params = [('al', 'J/K', al), ('b1', 'J/K^2', b1), ('c1', 'J-K^2', c1), ('d1', 'J-K^1/2',
    ↪', d1), ('tg', 'K', tg)]
Cpg = al + b1*T + c1/T**2 + d1/sym.sqrt(T)
GPr = sym.integrate(Cpg, (T,Tr,T)) - T*sym.integrate(Cpg/T, (T,Tr,T))
model.add_expression_to_model(GPr, params, exp_type='restricted', lower_limits=(Tr,
    ↪None), upper_limits=(tg,None))
```

```
dummy = sym.symbols('dummy')
params = [('dummy', 'J', dummy)]
model.add_expression_to_model(GPr.subs(T,tg), params, exp_type='restricted', lower_
    ↪limits=(tg,None), upper_limits=(None,None))
```

```
cpl = sym.symbols('cpl')
params = [('cpl', 'J/K', cpl)]
GPr = sym.integrate(cpl, (T,tg,T)) - T*sym.integrate(cpl/T, (T,tg,T))
model.add_expression_to_model(GPr, params, exp_type='restricted', lower_limits=(tg,
    ↪None), upper_limits=(None,None))
```

```
v,dvdt,dvdp,d2vdtdp,d2vdp2,tr1 = sym.symbols('v dvdt dvdp d2vdtdp d2vdp2 tr1')
params = [('v', 'J/bar', v), ('dvdt', 'J/bar-K', dvdt), ('dvdp', 'J/bar^2', dvdp), (
    ↪'d2vdtdp', 'J/bar^2-K', d2vdtdp),
    ('d2vdp2', 'J/bar^3', d2vdp2), ('tr1', 'K', tr1)]
GPrP = sym.integrate(v + dvdt*(T-tr1) + (dvdp + d2vdtdp*(T-tr1))*(P-Pr) + d2vdp2*(0.
    ↪5*P**2 - Pr*(P-Pr)), (P,Pr,P))
model.add_expression_to_model(GPrP, params)
```

12.1.1 Build instance

```
model_working_dir = "working"
!mkdir -p {model_working_dir}
%cd {model_working_dir}
```

Parameters from Ghiorso and Sack (1995)

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'SiO2',
    'Formula': 'Si(1)O(2)',
    'h0': -901554.0,
    's0': 48.475,
    'al': 127.200,
    'b1': -10.777e-3,
    'c1': 4.3127e5,
    'd1': -1463.8,
    'tg': 1480.0,
    'cpl': 81.373,
    'v': 2.690,
    'dvdt': 0.0,
    'dvdp': -1.89e-5,
    'd2vdtdp': 1.3e-8,
    'd2vdp2': 3.6e-10,
    'T_r': 298.15,
```

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```
'P_r':      1.0,
'tr1':     1673.15,
'dummy':   1.0
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cp rMELTS_ZR.pyx endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list = ['SiO2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c']
endmember_name_list = ['SiO2']
```

12.2 General case (Berman solids -> liquid)

```
model = coder.StdStateModel()
model.set_module_name('rMELTS_ZR')
model_type = "calib"
T = model.get_symbol_for_t()
P = model.get_symbol_for_p()
Tr = model.get_symbol_for_tr()
Pr = model.get_symbol_for_pr()
```

G(solid) at T, Pr: lattice heat capacity G(Solid) -> G(liquid)

```
k0,k1,k2,k3,tFusion,sFusion,cpLiq = sym.symbols('k0 k1 k2 k3 tFusion sFusion cpLiq')
CpPr = k0 + k1/sym.sqrt(T) + k2/T**2 + k3/T**3
STrPr,HTrPr = sym.symbols('S_TrPr H_TrPr')
params = [('H_TrPr','J',HTrPr), ('S_TrPr','J/K',STrPr), ('k0','J/K-m',k0), ('k1','J-K^
    ↪(1/2)-m',k1),
          ('k2','J-K/m',k2), ('k3','J-K^2',k3), ('tFusion','J',tFusion), ('sFusion',
    ↪'J/K', sFusion), ('cpLiq','J/K', cpLiq)]
GPr = HTrPr + sym.integrate(CpPr, (T,Tr,tFusion)) - T*(STrPr + sym.integrate(CpPr/T, (T,
    ↪Tr,tFusion))) \
      + sFusion*tFusion + cpLiq*(T-tFusion) - T*(sFusion + cpLiq*sym.log(T/tFusion))
model.add_expression_to_model(GPr, params)
```

GPr

G(solid) at T, Pr: lambda transition

```
l1,l2 = sym.symbols('l1 l2')
Tl, Tlr = sym.symbols('T_lambda_Pr T_lambda_ref')
params = [('l1','(J/m)^(1/2)-K', l1), ('l2','(J/m)^(1/2)/K^2', l2), ('T_lambda_Pr',
    ↪'K', Tl), ('T_lambda_ref','K', Tlr)]
Cpl = T*(l1+l2*T)**2
Gl = sym.integrate(Cpl, (T,Tlr,Tl)) - T*sym.integrate(Cpl/T, (T,Tlr,Tl))
model.add_expression_to_model(Gl, params, exp_type='restricted', lower_limits=(Tr,
    ↪None), upper_limits=(None, None))
```

G(solid) at T, Pr: first order phase transition

```
deltaHt = sym.symbols('H_t')
params = [('H_t','J/m', deltaHt)]
```

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```
GaboveT1 = -(T-T1)*deltaHt/T1
model.add_expression_to_model(GaboveT1 , params, exp_type='restricted', lower_
↳limits=(Tr, None), upper_limits=(None, None))
```

G(liquid) at T, Pr -> G(liquid) at T, P

```
Vtrl, dvdt, dvdp, d2vdt dp, d2vdp2, trl = sym.symbols('Vtrl dvdt dvdp d2vdt dp d2vdp2 trl')
params = [('Vtrl', 'J/bar', Vtrl), ('dvdt', 'J/bar-K', dvdt), ('dvdp', 'J/bar^2', dvdp),
↳('d2vdt dp', 'J/bar^2-K', d2vdt dp), ('d2vdp2', 'J/bar^3', d2vdp2), ('trl', 'K',
↳trl)]
GTPrToP = (Vtrl + dvdt*(T-trl))*(P-Pr) + (dvdp + (T-trl)*d2vdt dp)*(P*P-Pr*Pr)/2 -
↳(dvdp + (T-trl)*d2vdt dp)*Pr*(P-Pr) \
↳+ d2vdp2*( (P*P*P-Pr*Pr*Pr)/6 - Pr*(P*P-Pr*Pr)/2 + Pr*Pr*(P-Pr)/2 )
model.add_expression_to_model(GTPrToP, params)
```

GTPrToP

12.2.1 Build instances

Parameters from Ghiorso and Sack (1995), unless noted.

TiO2

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'TiO2',
    'Formula': 'Ti(1)O(2)',
    'H_TrPr': -944750.0,
    'S_TrPr': 50.460,
    'k0': 77.84,
    'k1': 0.0,
    'k2': -33.678e5,
    'k3': 40.294e7,
    'l1': 0.0,
    'l2': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
    'H_t': 0.0,
    'Vtrl': 2.316,
    'dvdt': 7.246e-4,
    'dvdp': -2.310e-5,
    'd2vdt dp': 0.0,
    'd2vdp2': 5.0e-10,
    'tFusion': 1870.0,
    'sFusion': 35.824,
    'cpLiq': 109.2,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↳'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
```

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```
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('TiO2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('TiO2')
```

Al2O3

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'Al2O3',
    'Formula': 'Al(2)O(3)',
    'H_TrPr': -1675700.0,
    'S_TrPr': 50.82,
    'k0': 155.02,
    'k1': -8.284E2,
    'k2': -38.614E5,
    'k3': 40.908E7,
    'l1': 0.0,
    'l2': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
    'H_t': 0.0,
    'Vtrl': 3.711,
    'dvdT': 2.62e-4,
    'dvdP': -2.26e-5,
    'd2vdTdp': 2.7e-8,
    'd2vdP2': 4.0e-10,
    'tFusion': 2319.65,
    'sFusion': 48.61,
    'cpLiq': 170.3,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↵'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Al2O3_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Al2O3')
```

Fe2O3

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'Fe2O3',
    'Formula': 'Fe(2)O(3)',
    'H_TrPr': -822000.0,
    'S_TrPr': 87.40,
    'k0': 146.86,
    'k1': 0.0,
    'k2': -55.768E5,
    'k3': 52.563E7,
    'l1': -7.403E-2,
    'l2': 27.921E-5,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 955.0,
```

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```

'T_lambda_ref': 298.15,
'H_t':          1287.0,
'Vtrl':         4.213,
'dvdt':         9.09E-4,
'dvdp':         -2.53E-5,
'd2vdt dp':    3.1E-8,
'd2vdp2':       4.4e-10,
'tFusion':     1895.0,
'sFusion':     60.41,
'cpLiq':       240.9,
'T_r':         298.15,
'P_r':         1.0,
'trl':         1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↪ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Fe2O3_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Fe2O3')

```

MgCr2O4

```

param_dict = {
'Phase': 'MgCr2O4',
'Formula': 'Mg(1)Cr(2)O(4)',
'H_TrPr': -1783640.0,
'S_TrPr': 106.02,
'k0':     201.981,
'k1':     -5.519E2,
'k2':     -57.844E5,
'k3':     57.729E7,
'l1':     0.0,
'l2':     0.0,
'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
'H_t':     0.0,
'Vtrl':    5.358,
'dvdt':    11.71e-4,
'dvdp':    -2.26e-5,
'd2vdt dp': 1.8e-8,
'd2vdp2':  4.67e-10,
'tFusion': 2673.15,
'sFusion': 73.22,
'cpLiq':   335.1,
'T_r':     298.15,
'P_r':     1.0,
'trl':     1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↪ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('MgCr2O4_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('MgCr2O4')

```

Fe2SiO4

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'Fe2SiO4',
  'Formula': 'Fe(2)Si(1)O(4)',
  'H_TrPr': -1479360.0,
  'S_TrPr': 150.930,
  'k0': 248.93,
  'k1': -19.239E2,
  'k2': 0.0,
  'k3': -13.910E7,
  'l1': 0.0,
  'l2': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
  'H_t': 0.0,
  'Vtrl': 5.420,
  'dvdt': 5.84e-4,
  'dvdp': -2.79e-5,
  'd2vdt dp': -2.3e-8,
  'd2vdp2': 14.6e-10,
  'tFusion': 1490.0,
  'sFusion': 59.9,
  'cpLiq': 240.2,
  'T_r': 298.15,
  'P_r': 1.0,
  'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↪ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Fe2SiO4_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Fe2SiO4')

```

MnSi0.5O2

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'MnSi1d2O2',
  'Formula': 'Mn(1)Si(0.5)O(2)',
  'H_TrPr': -1732000.0/2.0,
  'S_TrPr': 155.9/2.0,
  'k0': 219.89/2.0,
  'k1': -12.710E2/2.0,
  'k2': -20.496E5/2.0,
  'k3': 17.652E7/2.0,
  'l1': 0.0,
  'l2': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
  'H_t': 0.0,
  'Vtrl': 2.84,
  'dvdt': 5.84e-4/2.0,
  'dvdp': -2.79e-5/2.0,
  'd2vdt dp': -2.3e-8/2.0,
  'd2vdp2': 14.6e-10/2.0,

```

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```
'tFusion':      1620.0,
'sFusion':      27.6,
'cpLiq':        121.6,
'T_r':          298.15,
'P_r':          1.0,
'trl':          1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('MnSi1d2O2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('MnSi1d2O2')
```

Mg₂SiO₄

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'Mg2SiO4',
    'Formula': 'Mg(2)Si(1)O(4)',
    'H_TrPr': -2174420.0,
    'S_TrPr': 94.010,
    'k0': 238.64,
    'k1': -20.013E2,
    'k2': 0.0,
    'k3': -11.624E7,
    'l1': 0.0,
    'l2': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
    'H_t': 0.0,
    'Vtrl': 4.980,
    'dvdt': 5.24e-4,
    'dvdp': -1.35e-5,
    'd2vdt dp': -1.3e-8,
    'd2vdp2': 4.14e-10,
    'tFusion': 2163.0,
    'sFusion': 57.2,
    'cpLiq': 271.0,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Mg2SiO4_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Mg2SiO4')
```

NiSi0.5O2

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'NiSi1d2O2',
  'Formula': 'Ni(1)Si(0.5)O(2)',
  'H_TrPr': -1395300.0/2.0,
  'S_TrPr': 128.1/2.0,
  'k0': 214.997/2.0,
  'k1': -10.3075E2/2.0,
  'k2': -49.4453E5/2.0,
  'k3': 62.375E7/2.0,
  'l1': 0.0,
  'l2': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
  'H_t': 0.0,
  'Vtrl': 2.48,
  'dvdt': 5.84e-4/2.0,
  'dvdp': -2.79e-5/2.0,
  'd2vdt dp': -2.3e-8/2.0,
  'd2vdp2': 14.6e-10/2.0,
  'tFusion': 1923.0,
  'sFusion': 29.0,
  'cpLiq': 119.3,
  'T_r': 298.15,
  'P_r': 1.0,
  'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↵'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('NiSi1d2O2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('NiSi1d2O2')

```

CoSi0.5O2

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'CoSi1d2O2',
  'Formula': 'Co(1)Si(0.5)O(2)',
  'H_TrPr': -1414100.0/2.0,
  'S_TrPr': 142.6/2.0,
  'k0': 201.048/2.0,
  'k1': -0.369E2/2.0,
  'k2': -71.81E5/2.0,
  'k3': 90.05E7/2.0,
  'l1': 0.0,
  'l2': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
  'H_t': 0.0,
  'Vtrl': 2.30,
  'dvdt': 5.84e-4/2.0,
  'dvdp': -2.79e-5/2.0,
  'd2vdt dp': -2.3e-8/2.0,
  'd2vdp2': 14.6e-10/2.0,

```

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```

'tFusion':      1688.0,
'sFusion':      29.0,
'cpLiq':        125.3,
'T_r':          298.15,
'P_r':          1.0,
'trl':          1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('CoSi1d202_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('CoSi1d202')

```

CaSiO3

```

param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'CaSiO3',
    'Formula': 'Ca(1)Si(1)O(3)',
    'H_TrPr': -1627427.0,
    'S_TrPr': 85.279,
    'k0': 141.16,
    'k1': -4.172e2,
    'k2': -58.576e5,
    'k3': 94.074e7,
    'l1': 0.0,
    'l2': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
    'H_t': 0.0,
    'Vtrl': 4.347,
    'dvdt': 2.92e-4,
    'dvdp': -1.55e-5,
    'd2vdt dp': -1.6e-8,
    'd2vdp2': 3.89e-10,
    'tFusion': 1817.0,
    'sFusion': 31.5,
    'cpLiq': 172.4,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('CaSiO3_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('CaSiO3')

```

Na₂SiO₃

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'Na2SiO3',
  'Formula': 'Na(2)Si(1)O(3)',
  'H_TrPr': -373190.0*4.184,
  'S_TrPr': 27.21*4.184,
  'k0': 234.77,
  'k1': -22.189E2,
  'k2': 0.0,
  'k3': 13.530E7,
  'l1': 0.0,
  'l2': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
  'H_t': 0.0,
  'Vtrl': 5.568,
  'dvdt': 7.41e-4,
  'dvdp': -4.29e-5,
  'd2vdt dp': -5.3e-8,
  'd2vdp2': 8.4e-10,
  'tFusion': 1361.0,
  'sFusion': 38.34,
  'cpLiq': 180.2,
  'T_r': 298.15,
  'P_r': 1.0,
  'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↵ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Na2SiO3_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Na2SiO3')

```

KAlSiO₄

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'KAlSiO4',
  'Formula': 'K(1)Al(1)Si(1)O(4)',
  'H_TrPr': -2111813.55,
  'S_TrPr': 133.9653,
  'k0': 186.0,
  'k1': 0.0,
  'k2': -131.067E5,
  'k3': 213.893E7,
  'l1': -7.096454E-2,
  'l2': 21.682E-5,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 800.15,
  'T_lambda_ref': 298.15,
  'H_t': 1154.0,
  'Vtrl': 6.8375,
  'dvdt': 7.265e-4,
  'dvdp': -6.395e-5,
  'd2vdt dp': -4.6e-8,
  'd2vdp2': 12.1e-10,

```

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```

'tFusion':      2023.15,
'sFusion':      24.5,
'cpLiq':        217.0,
'T_r':          298.15,
'P_r':          1.0,
'trl':          1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↳'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('KAlSiO4_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('KAlSiO4')

```

Ca₃(PO₃)₂

```

param_dict = {
  'Phase': 'Ca3P2O8',
  'Formula': 'Ca(3)P(2)O(8)',
  'H_TrPr': -4097169.0,
  'S_TrPr': 235.978,
  'k0': 402.997,
  'k1': -28.0835E2,
  'k2': 0.0,
  'k3': -32.6230E7,
  'l1': 2.5427E-2,
  'l2': 19.255E-5,
  'T_lambda_Pr': 1373.0,
  'T_lambda_ref': 298.15,
  'H_t': 14059.0,
  'Vtrl': 10.7382,
  'dvdt': 0.0,
  'dvdp': 0.0,
  'd2vdt dp': 0.0,
  'd2vdp2': 0.0,
  'tFusion': 1943.15,
  'sFusion': 35.690,
  'cpLiq': 574.67,
  'T_r': 298.15,
  'P_r': 1.0,
  'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↳'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('Ca3P2O8_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('Ca3P2O8')

```

H2O

This is a placeholder model for the one described in Ghiorso and Gualda (2015). The real code is copied into the working directory.

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'H2O',
    'Formula': 'H(2)O(1)',
    'H_TrPr': -99999.0,
    'S_TrPr': 0.0,
    'k0': 0.0,
    'k1': 0.0,
    'k2': 0.0,
    'k3': 0.0,
    'l1': 0.0,
    'l2': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
    'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
    'H_t': 0.0,
    'Vtrl': 0.0,
    'dvdT': 0.0,
    'dvdP': 0.0,
    'd2vdTdp': 0.0,
    'd2vdP2': 0.0,
    'tFusion': 1000.0,
    'sFusion': 0.0,
    'cpLiq': 0.0,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
%cp ../H2O_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c .
%cp ../H2O_rMELTS_ZR_calib.h .
endmember_file_list.append('H2O_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('H2O')
```

CO2

The enthalpy, entropy, heat capacity and dCpDt entries are correction terms that should be added to Duan's pure CO2. This is a placeholder model for the one described in Ghiorso and Gualda (2015). The real code is copied into the working directory.

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'CO2',
    'Formula': 'C(1)O(2)',
    'H_TrPr': -6.3093193811701e-01*1000.0,
    'S_TrPr': -1.0939331414050e+02,
    'k0': 0.0,
    'k1': 0.0,
    'k2': 0.0,
    'k3': 0.0,
    'l1': 0.0,
```

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```

'l2':          0.0,
'T_lambda_Pr': 0.0,
'T_lambda_ref': 0.0,
'H_t':        0.0,
'Vtrl':       4.0157994267547e+00,
'dvdt':       1.2131890000000e+00/1000.0,
'dvdp':       -4.2673870000000e-01/10000.0,
'd2vdt dp':  0.0,
'd2vdp2':    0.0,
'tFusion':    1000.0,
'sFusion':    0.0,
'cpLiq':     0.0,
'T_r':       298.15,
'P_r':       1.0,
'trl':       1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↪ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
%cp ../CO2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c .
%cp ../CO2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.h .
endmember_file_list.append('CO2_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('CO2')

```

12.3 Special case ZrSiO₄

New component, not in previously published material. Properties are derived from Robie and Hemingway, 1995: Robie RA, Hemingway BS (1995) Thermodynamic Properties of Minerals and Related Substances at 298.15 K and 1 Bar (105 Pascals) Pressure and at Higher Temperatures. US Geological Survey Bulletin 2131, 461pp.

```

model = coder.StdStateModel()
model.set_module_name('rMELTS_ZR')
model_type = "calib"
T = model.get_symbol_for_t()
P = model.get_symbol_for_p()
Tr = model.get_symbol_for_tr()
Pr = model.get_symbol_for_pr()

```

$$C_P = A_1 + A_2 T + \frac{A_3}{T^2} + \frac{A_4}{\sqrt{T}} + A_5 T^2$$

```

h0,s0,v0,a1,a2,a3,a4,a5 = sym.symbols('h0 s0 v0 a1 a2 a3 a4 a5')
params = [('h0', 'J', h0), ('s0', 'J/K', s0), ('v0', 'J/bar', v0),
          ('a1', 'J/K', a1), ('a2', 'J/K^2', a2), ('a3', 'J-K', a3), ('a4', 'J/K^1/2',
↪ a4), ('a5', 'J/K^3', a5)]
Cp = a1 + a2*T + a3/T**2 + a4/sym.sqrt(T) + a5*T**2
H = h0 + sym.integrate(Cp, (T, Tr, T))
S = s0 + sym.integrate(Cp/T, (T, Tr, T))
GPrP = sym.integrate(v0, (P, Pr, P))
G = H - T*S + GPrP
G

```

```

model.add_expression_to_model(G, params)

```

```

param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'ZrSiO4',
    'Formula': 'Zr(1)Si(1)O(4)',
    'h0': -2034200.0,          # Robie and Hemingway
    's0': 84.0,               # Robie and Hemingway
    'v0': 3.926,             # Robie and Hemingway
    'a1': 2.370e2,           # Robie and Hemingway
    'a2': -1.788e-2,         # Robie and Hemingway
    'a3': -1.496e5,          # Robie and Hemingway
    'a4': -2.268e3,          # Robie and Hemingway
    'a5': 0.0,               # Robie and Hemingway
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat rMELTS_ZR.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('ZrSiO4_rMELTS_ZR_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('ZrSiO4')

```

12.4 Import the module

First, update the cython build file to include all of the endmember modules

```

with open('rMELTS_ZR.pyxbld', 'r') as f:
    fold = f.read()
    f.close()
old_file_list = "" + endmember_file_list[-1] + ""
new_file_list = ''
sep = ''
for x in endmember_file_list:
    new_file_list += sep + "" + x + ""
    sep = ", "
fnew = fold.replace(old_file_list, new_file_list)
with open('rMELTS_ZR.pyxbld', 'w') as f:
    f.write(fnew)
    f.close()
%cp endmembers.pyx rMELTS_ZR.pyx

```

```

import rMELTS_ZR
%cd ..

```

12.5 Testing

Evaluate test functions at temperature (K) and pressure (bars)

```
t = 1000.0
p = 1000.0
```

Generic testing method, utilized here and below

```
from rubicon.objc import ObjCClass
src_cls = ObjCClass('LiquidMeltsPlusOldH2OandNewCO2')
src_obj = src_cls.alloc().init()

def compare_model_and_timers(new_model='SiO2', old_model_index=0, print_results=True,
    ←time_g=True):
    def cmp_output(ref, x, y):
        fmt = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} {2:13.6e} {3:13.6e} {4:6.2f}%"
        if print_results:
            print(fmt.format(ref, x, y, x-y, 100.0*math.fabs((x-y)/y)))
        else:
            assert 100.0*math.fabs((x-y)/y) < 0.01, ref+' fails comparison!'
    def tst_output(ref, x):
        fmts = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e}"
        if print_results:
            print(fmts.format(ref, x))
    refPhase = src_obj.endmembers[old_model_index]
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_g')(t,p)
    y = refPhase.getGibbsFreeEnergyFromT_andP_(t,p)
    cmp_output('G', x, y)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdt')(t,p)
    y = -refPhase.getEntropyFromT_andP_(t,p)
    cmp_output('dGdT', x, y)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdp')(t,p)
    y = refPhase.getVolumeFromT_andP_(t,p)
    cmp_output('dGdP', x, y)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdT2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2dp')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdTdP', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdp2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdP2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt3')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdT3', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdT2dP', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdTdP2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdp3')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdP3', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_s')(t,p)
    y = refPhase.getEntropyFromT_andP_(t,p)
    cmp_output('S', x, y)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_v')(t,p)
    y = refPhase.getVolumeFromT_andP_(t,p)
    cmp_output('V', x, y)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cv')(t,p)
```

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```
tst_output('Cv', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cp')(t,p)
y = refPhase.getHeatCapacityFromT_andP_(t,p)
cmp_output('Cp', x, y)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dcpdt')(t,p)
tst_output('dCpdT', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_alpha')(t,p)
tst_output('alpha', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_beta')(t,p)
tst_output('beta', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_K')(t,p)
tst_output('K', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_Kp')(t,p)
tst_output('Kp', x)
if time_g:
    print ('Time coder generated function ...')
    method = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_g')
    %timeit method(t, p)
    print ('Time provided Objective-C function ...')
    %timeit refPhase.getGibbsFreeEnergyFromT_andP_(t,p)
```

Test and time code

```
for i,x in enumerate(endmember_name_list):
    if x != 'ZrSiO4':
        print ('Testing code for', x, '...')
        compare_model_and_timers(new_model=x, old_model_index=i, print_results=True,
    ←time_g=False)
        print ('')
```

```
def output_model_and_timers(new_model='SiO2', print_results=True, time_g=True):
    def tst_output(ref, x):
        fmts = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e}"
        if print_results:
            print (fmts.format(ref, x))
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_g')(t,p)
    tst_output('G', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdt')(t,p)
    tst_output('dGdT', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdp')(t,p)
    tst_output('dGdP', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdT2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2dp')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdTdP', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdp2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d2GdP2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt3')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdT3', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdT2dP', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp2')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdTdP2', x)
    x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdp3')(t,p)
    tst_output('d3GdP3', x)
```

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```
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_s')(t,p)
tst_output('S', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_v')(t,p)
tst_output('V', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cv')(t,p)
tst_output('Cv', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cp')(t,p)
tst_output('Cp', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dcpdt')(t,p)
tst_output('dCpdT', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_alpha')(t,p)
tst_output('alpha', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_beta')(t,p)
tst_output('beta', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_K')(t,p)
tst_output('K', x)
x = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_Kp')(t,p)
tst_output('Kp', x)
if time_g:
    print('Time coder generated function ...')
    method = getattr(rMELTS_ZR, 'cy_'+new_model+'_rMELTS_ZR_calib_g')
    %timeit method(t, p)
```

12.6 Timing the ZrSiO4 code

```
output_model_and_timers(new_model='ZrSiO4', print_results=True, time_g=True)
```

2-CODING: MELTS LIQUID MODEL WITH ZIRCONIUM

Model formulation and code generation notebook. Run Endmembers-MELTS notebook first!

Proposed associated solution model:

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Variable:	Component:	Species X:
SiO2	SiO2			n_1	X_1
TiO2	TiO2		r_1	n_2	X_2
Al2O3	Al2O3		r_2	n_3	X_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		r_3	n_4	X_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		r_4	n_5	X_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		r_5	n_6	X_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		r_6	n_7	X_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		r_7	n_8	X_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		r_8	n_9	X_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		r_9	n_{10}	X_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		r_{10}	n_{11}	X_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		r_{11}	n_{12}	X_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		r_{12}	n_{13}	X_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		r_{13}	n_{14}	X_{14}
H2O	H2O		r_{14}	n_{15}	X_{15}
CO2	CO2		r_{15}	n_{16}	X_{16}
ZrSiO4	ZrSiO4		r_{16}	n_{17}	X_{17}
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_1		X_{18}
	Na4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 2\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 = \text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_2		X_{19}
	K4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 4\text{KAlSiO}_4 = \text{K}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{SiO}_2$	s_3		X_{20}

```

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import sympy as sym
sym.init_printing()
from thermoengine import core, coder
from thermoengine.model import Database
db = Database()
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)

```

- Number of components = 17
- Number of species = 20
- Number of “ordering parameters” (i.e., dependent species) = 3

```
nc = 17
nw = 20
ns = 3
```

13.1 Create solution model

```
model = coder.ComplexSolnModel(nc=nc, ns=ns, nw=nw)
```

- n is a vector of moles of solution components
- nT is a sum of all n
- s is a vector of *moles* of dependent species

```
n = model.n
nT = model.nT
s = model.s
```

Set up ancillary compositional variables

- X is a vector of *moles* of all species (components + dependent species in solution)

Note that the zeroth index of X is ignored

```
X = [sym.S.Zero]
for i in range(1, nw+1):
    X.append(sym.symbols('X_'+str(i)))
```

Moles of elements are accumulated in the dictionary *elm*. See table above.

```
elm = {}
```

```
O_n = 2*n[0]+2*n[1]+3*n[2]+3*n[3]+4*n[4]+4*n[5]+2*n[6]+4*n[7]+2*n[8]+2*n[9]+3*n[10]+3*n[11]+4*n[12]+8*n[13]+8*n[14]+8*n[15]+2*n[16]+4*n[17]+3*n[18]+8*n[19]+8*n[20]
O_X = 2*X[1]+2*X[2]+3*X[3]+3*X[4]+4*X[5]+4*X[6]+2*X[7]+4*X[8]+2*X[9]+2*X[10]+3*X[11]+3*X[12]+4*X[13]+8*X[14]+8*X[15]+2*X[16]+4*X[17]+3*X[18]+8*X[19]+8*X[20]
eqn_O = O_n - O_X
elm['O'] = O_n
```

```
Si_n = n[0]+n[5]+n[6]/2+n[7]+n[8]/2+n[9]/2+n[10]+n[11]+n[12]+n[16]
Si_X = X[1]+X[6]+X[7]/2+X[8]+X[9]/2+X[10]/2+X[11]+X[12]+X[13]+X[17]+2*X[19]+2*X[20]
eqn_Si = Si_n - Si_X
elm['Si'] = Si_n
```

```
Ti_n = n[1]
Ti_X = X[2]
eqn_Ti = Ti_n - Ti_X
elm['Ti'] = Ti_n
```

```
Al_n = 2*n[2] + n[12]
Al_X = 2*X[3] + X[13]
eqn_Al = Al_n - Al_X
elm['Al'] = Al_n
```

```
Fe_n = 2*n[3] + 2*n[5]
Fe_X = 2*X[4] + 2*X[6]
eqn_Fe = Fe_n - Fe_X
elm['Fe'] = Fe_n
```

```
Cr_n = 2*n[4]
Cr_X = 2*X[5]
eqn_Cr = Cr_n - Cr_X
elm['Cr'] = Cr_n
```

```
Mn_n = n[6]
Mn_X = X[7]
eqn_Mn = Mn_n - Mn_X
elm['Mn'] = Mn_n
```

```
Mg_n = 2*n[7]
Mg_X = 2*X[8]
eqn_Mg = Mg_n - Mg_X
elm['Mg'] = Mg_n
```

```
Ni_n = n[8]
Ni_X = X[9]
eqn_Ni = Ni_n - Ni_X
elm['Ni'] = Ni_n
```

```
Co_n = n[9]
Co_X = X[10]
eqn_Co = Co_n - Co_X
elm['Co'] = Co_n
```

```
Ca_n = n[10] + 3*n[13]
Ca_X = X[11] + 3*X[14] + X[18]
eqn_Ca = Ca_n - Ca_X
elm['Ca'] = Ca_n
```

```
Na_n = 2*n[11]
Na_X = 2*X[12] + 4*X[19]
eqn_Na = Na_n - Na_X
elm['Na'] = Na_n
```

```
K_n = n[12]
K_X = X[13] + 4*X[20]
eqn_K = K_n - K_X
elm['K'] = K_n
```

```
P_n = 2*n[13]
P_X = 2*X[14]
eqn_P = P_n - P_X
elm['P'] = P_n
```

```
H_n = 2*n[14]
H_X = 2*X[15]
eqn_H = H_n - H_X
elm['H'] = H_n
```

```
C_n = n[15]
C_X = X[16] + X[18]
eqn_C = C_n - C_X
elm['C'] = C_n
```

```
Zr_n = n[16]
Zr_X = X[17] + X[19] + X[20]
eqn_Zr = Zr_n - Zr_X
elm['Zr'] = Zr_n
```

Solve this system for species mole numbers

```
system = [eqn_O, eqn_Si, eqn_Ti, eqn_Al, eqn_Fe, eqn_Cr, eqn_Mn, eqn_Mg, eqn_Ni, eqn_
    Co, eqn_Ca, eqn_Na, eqn_K, eqn_P, eqn_H, eqn_C, eqn_Zr,
    s[0]-X[18], s[1]-X[19], s[2]-X[20]]
X_soln = list(sym.linsolve(system, X[1:nw+1]).args[0])
```

Compute the total number of moles of all species, XT . Note that this quantity is not necessarily equal to nT .

```
XT = sym.S.Zero
for i,x in enumerate(X_soln):
    print ('X['+str(i+1)+'] = ', end='')
    sym.pprint (x)
    XT += x
XT
```

Retrieve model symbols for the temperature, pressure, and standard state chemical potentials

- T is temperature in K
- P is pressure in $bars$
- μ^o in Joules

```
T = model.get_symbol_for_t()
P = model.get_symbol_for_p()
mu = model.mu
```

Initialize lists to store model parameter names, units and symbols

```
params = []
units = []
symparams = []
```

Known values of parameters that are not allowed to change (rhyolite-MELTS, 1.1, old water saturation model, new carbon dioxide model)

```
include_excess_parameters = False
if not include_excess_parameters:
    param_subst_1 = []
known_w_values = [
    26266.7, # 0 W(TiO2 ,SiO2 ) 0
    -39120.0, # 1 W(Al2O3 ,SiO2 )
    8110.3, # 2 W(Fe2O3 ,SiO2 )
    27886.3, # 3 W(MgCr2O4 ,SiO2 )
    23660.9, # 4 W(Fe2SiO4 ,SiO2 )
    18393.9, # 5 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,SiO2 )
    3421.0, # 6 W(Mg2SiO4 ,SiO2 )
    25197.4, # 7 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,SiO2 )
    14802.8, # 8 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,SiO2 )
    -863.7, # 9 W(CaSiO3 ,SiO2 )
    -99039.0, # 10 W(Na2SiO3 ,SiO2 ) 10
    -33921.7, # 11 W(KAlSiO4 ,SiO2 )
    61891.6, # 12 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,SiO2 )
    30967.3, # 13 W(H2O ,SiO2 )
    0.0, # 14 W(CO2 ,SiO2 )
    6.3281206517489e+01*1000.0, # 15 W(CaCO3 ,SiO2 )
    -29449.8, # 16 W(Al2O3 ,TiO2 )
    -84756.9, # 17 W(Fe2O3 ,TiO2 )
    -72303.4, # 18 W(MgCr2O4 ,TiO2 )
    5209.1, # 19 W(Fe2SiO4 ,TiO2 )
    -16123.5, # 20 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,TiO2 ) 20
    -4178.3, # 21 W(Mg2SiO4 ,TiO2 )
    3614.8, # 22 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,TiO2 )
    -1640.0, # 23 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,TiO2 )
    -35372.5, # 24 W(CaSiO3 ,TiO2 )
    -15415.6, # 25 W(Na2SiO3 ,TiO2 )
    -48094.6, # 26 W(KAlSiO4 ,TiO2 )
    25938.8, # 27 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,TiO2 )
    81879.1, # 28 W(H2O ,TiO2 )
    -1.9265668647972e+01*1000.0, # 29 W(CO2 ,TiO2 )
    -7.9202707514741e+01*1000.0, # 30 W(CaCO3 ,TiO2 ) 30
    -17089.4, # 31 W(Fe2O3 ,Al2O3 )
    -31770.3, # 32 W(MgCr2O4 ,Al2O3 )
    -30509.0, # 33 W(Fe2SiO4 ,Al2O3 )
    -53874.9, # 34 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3 )
    -32880.3, # 35 W(Mg2SiO4 ,Al2O3 )
    2985.2, # 36 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3 )
    -2677.4, # 37 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3 )
    -57917.9, # 38 W(CaSiO3 ,Al2O3 )
    -130785.0, # 39 W(Na2SiO3 ,Al2O3 )
    -25859.2, # 40 W(KAlSiO4 ,Al2O3 ) 40
    52220.8, # 41 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Al2O3 )
    -16098.1, # 42 W(H2O ,Al2O3 )
    0.0, # 43 W(CO2 ,Al2O3 )
    4.6716121152125e+01*1000.0, # 44 W(CaCO3 ,Al2O3 )
```

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Zircon Geothermometry and Zr-mineral saturation in natural magmas using rhyolite-MELTS

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```

21605.9, # 45 W(MgCr2O4 ,Fe2O3 )
-179064.9, # 46 W(Fe2SiO4 ,Fe2O3 )
3907.9, # 47 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3 )
-71518.6, # 48 W(Mg2SiO4 ,Fe2O3 )
408.7, # 49 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3 )
-223.7, # 50 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3 ) 50
12076.6, # 51 W(CaSiO3 ,Fe2O3 )
-149662.2, # 52 W(Na2SiO3 ,Fe2O3 )
57555.9, # 53 W(KAlSiO4 ,Fe2O3 )
-4213.9, # 54 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Fe2O3 )
31405.5, # 55 W(H2O ,Fe2O3 )
-3.1868817914962e+00*1000.0, # 56 W(CO2 ,Fe2O3 )
6.5508729974818e+01*1000.0, # 57 W(CaCO3 ,Fe2O3 )
-82971.8, # 58 W(Fe2SiO4 ,MgCr2O4 )
182.4, # 59 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,MgCr2O4 )
46049.2, # 60 W(Mg2SiO4 ,MgCr2O4 ) 60
-266.0, # 61 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,MgCr2O4 )
-384.0, # 62 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,MgCr2O4 )
30704.7, # 63 W(CaSiO3 ,MgCr2O4 )
113646.0, # 64 W(Na2SiO3 ,MgCr2O4 )
75709.1, # 65 W(KAlSiO4 ,MgCr2O4 )
5341.8, # 66 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,MgCr2O4 )
0.0, # 67 W(H2O ,MgCr2O4 )
0.0, # 68 W(CO2 ,MgCr2O4 )
0.0, # 69 W(CaCO3 ,MgCr2O4 )
-6823.9, # 70 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,Fe2SiO4 ) 70
-37256.7, # 71 W(Mg2SiO4 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-17019.8, # 72 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-11746.3, # 73 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-12970.8, # 74 W(CaSiO3 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-90533.8, # 75 W(Na2SiO3 ,Fe2SiO4 )
23649.4, # 76 W(KAlSiO4 ,Fe2SiO4 )
87410.3, # 77 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
28873.6, # 78 W(H2O ,Fe2SiO4 )
-3.2464545980393e+01*1000.0, # 79 W(CO2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-7.2996815311226e+01*1000.0, # 80 W(CaCO3 ,Fe2SiO4 ) 80
-13040.1, # 81 W(Mg2SiO4 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
785.8, # 82 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
-50.6, # 83 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
2934.6, # 84 W(CaSiO3 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
-15780.8, # 85 W(Na2SiO3 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
23727.4, # 86 W(KAlSiO4 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
0.0, # 87 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
0.0, # 88 W(H2O ,MnSi0.5O2 )
0.0, # 89 W(CO2 ,MnSi0.5O2 )
0.0, # 90 W(CaCO3 ,MnSi0.5O2 ) 90
-21175.5, # 91 W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-14994.9, # 92 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-31731.9, # 93 W(CaSiO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-41876.9, # 94 W(Na2SiO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
22323.1, # 95 W(KAlSiO4 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-23208.8, # 96 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
35633.7, # 97 W(H2O ,Mg2SiO4 )
-4.0853595138597e+01*1000.0, # 98 W(CO2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-2.4872562549739e+01*1000.0, # 99 W(CaCO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
258.9, # 100 W(CoSi0.5O2 ,NiSi0.5O2 ) 100

```

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```

7027.5, # 101 W(CaSiO3      ,NiSi0.502 )
-3647.8, # 102 W(Na2SiO3     ,NiSi0.502 )
4261.4, # 103 W(KAlSiO4     ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 104 W(Ca3(PO4)2    ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 105 W(H2O          ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 106 W(CO2          ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 107 W(CaCO3       ,NiSi0.502 )
-26685.7, # 108 W(CaSiO3     ,CoSi0.502 )
531.2, # 109 W(Na2SiO3     ,CoSi0.502 )
265.7, # 110 W(KAlSiO4     ,CoSi0.502 ) 110
0.0, # 111 W(Ca3(PO4)2    ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 112 W(H2O          ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 113 W(CO2          ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 114 W(CaCO3       ,CoSi0.502 )
-13247.1, # 115 W(Na2SiO3     ,CaSiO3      )
17111.1, # 116 W(KAlSiO4     ,CaSiO3      )
37070.3, # 117 W(Ca3(PO4)2    ,CaSiO3      )
20374.6, # 118 W(H2O          ,CaSiO3      )
3.0012481472120e+01*1000.0, # 119 W(CO2          ,CaSiO3      )
3.7534127781795e+01*1000.0, # 120 W(CaCO3       ,CaSiO3      ) 120
6522.8, # 121 W(KAlSiO4     ,Na2SiO3     )
15571.9, # 122 W(Ca3(PO4)2    ,Na2SiO3     )
-96937.6, # 123 W(H2O          ,Na2SiO3     )
0.0, # 124 W(CO2          ,Na2SiO3     )
-3.1101129932991e+02*1000.0, # 126 W(CaCO3       ,Na2SiO3     )
17100.6, # 127 W(Ca3(PO4)2    ,KAlSiO4     )
10374.2, # 128 W(H2O          ,KAlSiO4     )
0.0, # 129 W(CO2          ,KAlSiO4     )
-2.7864967599360e+01*1000.0, # 130 W(CaCO3       ,KAlSiO4     )
43451.3, # 131 W(H2O          ,Ca3(PO4)2   ) 130
-3.4728165916175e+00*1000.0, # 132 W(CO2          ,Ca3(PO4)2   )
2.0119124588637e+00*1000.0, # 133 W(CaCO3       ,Ca3(PO4)2   )
2.3255499914663e+01*1000.0, # 134 W(CO2          ,H2O          )
7.8729683594722e+00*1000.0, # 135 W(CaCO3       ,H2O          )
0.0, # 180 W(CaCO3       ,CO2          )
]

```

13.2 Define extensive standard state contribution to solution properties

```

G_ss = sym.S.Zero
for i,x in enumerate(X_soln):
    if i < nc:
        G_ss += x*mu[i]
    else:
        h = sym.symbols('hd_'+str(i+1))
        params.append('hd_'+str(i+1))
        units.append('J')
        symparams.append(h)
        ss = sym.symbols('sd_'+str(i+1))
        symparams.append(ss)
        params.append('sd_'+str(i+1))

```

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```

units.append('J/K')
v = sym.symbols('vd_'+str(i+1))
params.append('vd_'+str(i+1))
units.append('J/bar')
symparams.append(v)
G_ss += x*(h-T*ss+(P-sym.S.One)*v)
h = sym.symbols('hZrSiO4')
params.append('hZrSiO4')
units.append('J')
symparams.append(h)
ss = sym.symbols('sZrSiO4')
symparams.append(ss)
params.append('sZrSiO4')
units.append('J/K')
v = sym.symbols('vZrSiO4')
params.append('vZrSiO4')
units.append('J/bar')
symparams.append(v)
G_ss += X_soln[16]*(h-T*ss+(P-sym.S.One)*v)
G_ss

```

13.3 Define extensive configurational Gibbs free energy

R is the gas constant. Note that species mole fractions are computed using XT rather than nT

```
eps = np.finfo(float).eps
```

```

R = sym.symbols('R')
S_config = sym.S.Zero
for x in X_soln:
    S_config += x*sym.log(x/XT+eps)
S_config += X_soln[14]*sym.log(X_soln[14]/XT) + (XT-X_soln[14])*sym.log(sym.S.One-X_
    soln[14]/XT) # extra entropy from hydroxyl term
S_config *= -R
G_config = -T*S_config

```

13.4 Non-configurational extensive molar Gibbs free energy

These are the regular solution terms. Zirconium species are assumed to not contribute to the excess Gibbs free energy. The flag, `include_excess_parameters` is used to perform direct substitution of excess solution parameters, removing them from the list of “calibration” parameters in order to save code generation and compilation time.

```

G_ex = sym.S.Zero
for i,x in enumerate(X_soln):
    istr = '{0:02d}'.format(i+1)
    for j,y in enumerate(X_soln):
        jstr = '{0:02d}'.format(j+1)
        if j > i and i<nc-1 and j<nc-1: #skip the last component, ZrSiO4
            w = sym.symbols('Wc'+istr+'c'+jstr)

```

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```

    if include_excess_parameters:
        params.append('Wc'+istr+'c'+jstr)
        units.append('J')
        symparams.append(w)
    else:
        param_subst_l.append(w)
        G_ex += x*y*w
if i<nc-1:
    w = sym.symbols('Wc'+istr+'s1')
    if include_excess_parameters:
        params.append('Wc'+istr+'s1')
        units.append('J')
        symparams.append(w)
    else:
        param_subst_l.append(w)
        G_ex += x*s[0]*w
G_ex /= XT

```

```

print(params)
print(units)
print(symparams)

```

13.5 Define the extensive Gibbs free energy of solution

```
G = G_ss + G_config + G_ex
```

```
ll = list(zip(param_subst_l, known_w_values))
```

```

if not include_excess_parameters:
    G = G.subs(list(zip(param_subst_l, known_w_values)))

```

13.6 Find the condition of homogeneous equilibrium: $\frac{\partial \hat{G}}{\partial s_i} = 0$

```

dgds = []
for x in s:
    dgds.append(G.diff(x))

```

13.7 Identify bounds on the ordering parameter

Construct a set of inequality constraints on the lower bound of species mole fractions. If all the mole fractions are guaranteed to be positive, then the sum of all those moles, XT , is positive. Note that the upper bound on X_i is guaranteed to be feasible, because in use that quantity is always smaller than XT .

```
ineq_l = [
    0 <= X_soln[ 0],
    0 <= X_soln[ 1],
    0 <= X_soln[ 2],
    0 <= X_soln[ 3],
    0 <= X_soln[ 4],
    0 <= X_soln[ 5],
    0 <= X_soln[ 6],
    0 <= X_soln[ 7],
    0 <= X_soln[ 8],
    0 <= X_soln[ 9],
    0 <= X_soln[10],
    0 <= X_soln[11],
    0 <= X_soln[12],
    0 <= X_soln[13],
    0 <= X_soln[14],
    0 <= X_soln[15],
    0 <= X_soln[16],
    0 <= X_soln[17],
    0 <= X_soln[18],
    0 <= X_soln[19]
]
insym_l = [x for x in n]
out = sym.reduce_inequalities(inequalities=ineq_l, symbols=insym_l)
out
```

13.8 Identity initial guess values of the order parameters

```
initial_guess_l = []
initial_guess_l.append( sym.Min(n[10]/6,n[15]/2) )
initial_guess_l.append( sym.Min(n[11]/2,n[16]/4) )
initial_guess_l.append( sym.Min(n[12]/4,n[16]/4) )
```

```
initial_guess_l
```

13.9 Identify null values of ordering parameters

```
nullValues = [sym.S.Zero, sym.S.Zero, sym.S.Zero]
```

13.10 Add the Gibbs free energy of solution to the model

```
model.add_expression_to_model(G, list(zip(params, units, symparams)), ordering_
↳functions=(dgds,s,initial_guess_l,out,nullValues))
```

13.11 Name the module that will hold the liquid model

```
model.module = "rMELTS_ZR"
```

13.12 Composition conversion and bound constraints

Develop expressions that convert solution composition expressed as moles of elements into moles of components

```
ineq_l = []
insym_l = []
for key,value in elm.items():
    y = sym.symbols(key)
    ineq_l.append(value - y)
    insym_l.append(y)
sol = sym.solve(ineq_l, tuple(n))
for i,x in enumerate(n):
    print ('n['+str(i+1)+'] = ', end='')
    print(sol[x])
```

Construct a formula string for the model

```
repl_s = {}
for key in elm.keys():
    if key[0:1] != ' ':
        repl_s[key] = '[' + key + ']'
for key in elm.keys():
    if key[0:1] == ' ':
        repl_s[key[1:]] = '[' + key[1] + ']'
formula_string = ''
for x,y in repl_s.items():
    formula_string += x + y
formula_string
```

Compute a list of conversion strings to cast element abundances to component mole numbers

```
def process_str(z):
    while True:
        l1 = z.find('[[')
        if l1 == -1:
            return z
        else:
            l2 = l1+3
            z = z[:l2] + z[l2+1:]
            z = z[:l1] + z[l1+1:]
```

```
conversion_string = []
for i,zz in enumerate(sol):
    z = str(sol[zz]).replace(' ', '')
    for x,y in repl_s.items():
        z = z.replace(x,y)
    z = process_str(z)
    conversion_string.append('['+str(i)+']='+z)
conversion_string
```

Compute a test string to insure a feasible solution; these constraints insure that the moles of each element is greater than zero

```
test_string = []
for x,y in elm.items():
    z = str(y).replace('/2 +', ']/2+')
    z = z.replace(' +', ' ] +')
    z = z.replace('\n', '[')
    z = z.replace(' ', '')
    z += ' ] >= 0.0'
    z = z.replace('/2]', ']/2')
    for i in range(1,nc+1):
        z = z.replace('['+str(i)+']', '['+str(i-1)+']')
    test_string.append(z)
```

13.13 Add these bound constraints to the model

```
model.formula_string = formula_string
model.conversion_string = conversion_string
model.test_string = test_string
```

13.14 Assign parameter values

```
depen_species_values = [
    0.0, 0.0, 0.0, # H, S, V, CaCO3
    0.0, 0.0, 0.0, # H, S, V, Na4ZrSi2O8
    0.0, 0.0, 0.0, # H, S, V, K4ZrSi2O8
    0.0, 0.0, 0.0 # H, S, V, ZrSiO4
]
```

Parameter values are consistent with rhyolite-MELTS version 1.1

```
if include_excess_parameters:
    w_values = [
        26266.7, # 0 W(TiO2 ,SiO2 ) 0
        -39120.0, # 1 W(Al2O3 ,SiO2 )
        8110.3, # 2 W(Fe2O3 ,SiO2 )
        27886.3, # 3 W(MgCr2O4 ,SiO2 )
        23660.9, # 4 W(Fe2SiO4 ,SiO2 )
        18393.9, # 5 W(MnSi0.5O2 ,SiO2 )
```

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	3421.0, #	6	W(Mg2SiO4 ,SiO2)	
	25197.4, #	7	W(NiSi0.5O2 ,SiO2)	
	14802.8, #	8	W(CoSi0.5O2 ,SiO2)	
	-863.7, #	9	W(CaSiO3 ,SiO2)	
	-99039.0, #	10	W(Na2SiO3 ,SiO2)	10
	-33921.7, #	11	W(KAlSiO4 ,SiO2)	
	61891.6, #	12	W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,SiO2)	
	30967.3, #	13	W(H2O ,SiO2)	
	0.0, #	14	W(CO2 ,SiO2)	
6.3281206517489e+01	*1000.0, #	15	W(CaCO3 ,SiO2)	
	-29449.8, #	16	W(Al2O3 ,TiO2)	
	-84756.9, #	17	W(Fe2O3 ,TiO2)	
	-72303.4, #	18	W(MgCr2O4 ,TiO2)	
	5209.1, #	19	W(Fe2SiO4 ,TiO2)	
	-16123.5, #	20	W(MnSi0.5O2 ,TiO2)	20
	-4178.3, #	21	W(Mg2SiO4 ,TiO2)	
	3614.8, #	22	W(NiSi0.5O2 ,TiO2)	
	-1640.0, #	23	W(CoSi0.5O2 ,TiO2)	
	-35372.5, #	24	W(CaSiO3 ,TiO2)	
	-15415.6, #	25	W(Na2SiO3 ,TiO2)	
	-48094.6, #	26	W(KAlSiO4 ,TiO2)	
	25938.8, #	27	W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,TiO2)	
	81879.1, #	28	W(H2O ,TiO2)	
-1.9265668647972e+01	*1000.0, #	29	W(CO2 ,TiO2)	
-7.9202707514741e+01	*1000.0, #	30	W(CaCO3 ,TiO2)	30
	-17089.4, #	31	W(Fe2O3 ,Al2O3)	
	-31770.3, #	32	W(MgCr2O4 ,Al2O3)	
	-30509.0, #	33	W(Fe2SiO4 ,Al2O3)	
	-53874.9, #	34	W(MnSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3)	
	-32880.3, #	35	W(Mg2SiO4 ,Al2O3)	
	2985.2, #	36	W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3)	
	-2677.4, #	37	W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Al2O3)	
	-57917.9, #	38	W(CaSiO3 ,Al2O3)	
	-130785.0, #	39	W(Na2SiO3 ,Al2O3)	
	-25859.2, #	40	W(KAlSiO4 ,Al2O3)	40
	52220.8, #	41	W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Al2O3)	
	-16098.1, #	42	W(H2O ,Al2O3)	
	0.0, #	43	W(CO2 ,Al2O3)	
4.6716121152125e+01	*1000.0, #	44	W(CaCO3 ,Al2O3)	
	21605.9, #	45	W(MgCr2O4 ,Fe2O3)	
	-179064.9, #	46	W(Fe2SiO4 ,Fe2O3)	
	3907.9, #	47	W(MnSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3)	
	-71518.6, #	48	W(Mg2SiO4 ,Fe2O3)	
	408.7, #	49	W(NiSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3)	
	-223.7, #	50	W(CoSi0.5O2 ,Fe2O3)	50
	12076.6, #	51	W(CaSiO3 ,Fe2O3)	
	-149662.2, #	52	W(Na2SiO3 ,Fe2O3)	
	57555.9, #	53	W(KAlSiO4 ,Fe2O3)	
	-4213.9, #	54	W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Fe2O3)	
	31405.5, #	55	W(H2O ,Fe2O3)	
-3.1868817914962e+00	*1000.0, #	56	W(CO2 ,Fe2O3)	
6.5508729974818e+01	*1000.0, #	57	W(CaCO3 ,Fe2O3)	
	-82971.8, #	58	W(Fe2SiO4 ,MgCr2O4)	
	182.4, #	59	W(MnSi0.5O2 ,MgCr2O4)	
	46049.2, #	60	W(Mg2SiO4 ,MgCr2O4)	60
	-266.0, #	61	W(NiSi0.5O2 ,MgCr2O4)	

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Zircon Geothermometry and Zr-mineral saturation in natural magmas using rhyolite-MELTS

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```

-384.0, # 62 W(CoSi0.502 ,MgCr204 )
30704.7, # 63 W(CaSiO3 ,MgCr204 )
113646.0, # 64 W(Na2SiO3 ,MgCr204 )
75709.1, # 65 W(KAlSiO4 ,MgCr204 )
5341.8, # 66 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,MgCr204 )
0.0, # 67 W(H2O ,MgCr204 )
0.0, # 68 W(CO2 ,MgCr204 )
0.0, # 69 W(CaCO3 ,MgCr204 )
-6823.9, # 70 W(MnSi0.502 ,Fe2SiO4 ) 70
-37256.7, # 71 W(Mg2SiO4 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-17019.8, # 72 W(NiSi0.502 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-11746.3, # 73 W(CoSi0.502 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-12970.8, # 74 W(CaSiO3 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-90533.8, # 75 W(Na2SiO3 ,Fe2SiO4 )
23649.4, # 76 W(KAlSiO4 ,Fe2SiO4 )
87410.3, # 77 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
28873.6, # 78 W(H2O ,Fe2SiO4 )
-3.2464545980393e+01*1000.0, # 79 W(CO2 ,Fe2SiO4 )
-7.2996815311226e+01*1000.0, # 80 W(CaCO3 ,Fe2SiO4 ) 80
-13040.1, # 81 W(Mg2SiO4 ,MnSi0.502 )
785.8, # 82 W(NiSi0.502 ,MnSi0.502 )
-50.6, # 83 W(CoSi0.502 ,MnSi0.502 )
2934.6, # 84 W(CaSiO3 ,MnSi0.502 )
-15780.8, # 85 W(Na2SiO3 ,MnSi0.502 )
23727.4, # 86 W(KAlSiO4 ,MnSi0.502 )
0.0, # 87 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,MnSi0.502 )
0.0, # 88 W(H2O ,MnSi0.502 )
0.0, # 89 W(CO2 ,MnSi0.502 )
0.0, # 90 W(CaCO3 ,MnSi0.502 ) 90
-21175.5, # 91 W(NiSi0.502 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-14994.9, # 92 W(CoSi0.502 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-31731.9, # 93 W(CaSiO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-41876.9, # 94 W(Na2SiO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
22323.1, # 95 W(KAlSiO4 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-23208.8, # 96 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
35633.7, # 97 W(H2O ,Mg2SiO4 )
-4.0853595138597e+01*1000.0, # 98 W(CO2 ,Mg2SiO4 )
-2.4872562549739e+01*1000.0, # 99 W(CaCO3 ,Mg2SiO4 )
258.9, # 100 W(CoSi0.502 ,NiSi0.502 ) 100
7027.5, # 101 W(CaSiO3 ,NiSi0.502 )
-3647.8, # 102 W(Na2SiO3 ,NiSi0.502 )
4261.4, # 103 W(KAlSiO4 ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 104 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 105 W(H2O ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 106 W(CO2 ,NiSi0.502 )
0.0, # 107 W(CaCO3 ,NiSi0.502 )
-26685.7, # 108 W(CaSiO3 ,CoSi0.502 )
531.2, # 109 W(Na2SiO3 ,CoSi0.502 )
265.7, # 110 W(KAlSiO4 ,CoSi0.502 ) 110
0.0, # 111 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 112 W(H2O ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 113 W(CO2 ,CoSi0.502 )
0.0, # 114 W(CaCO3 ,CoSi0.502 )
-13247.1, # 115 W(Na2SiO3 ,CaSiO3 )
17111.1, # 116 W(KAlSiO4 ,CaSiO3 )
37070.3, # 117 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,CaSiO3 )

```

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```

                20374.6, # 118 W(H2O      ,CaSiO3   )
3.0012481472120e+01*1000.0, # 119 W(CO2      ,CaSiO3   )
3.7534127781795e+01*1000.0, # 120 W(CaCO3     ,CaSiO3   ) 120
                6522.8, # 121 W(KAlSiO4   ,Na2SiO3  )
                15571.9, # 122 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,Na2SiO3  )
                -96937.6, # 123 W(H2O      ,Na2SiO3  )
                0.0, # 124 W(CO2      ,Na2SiO3  )
-3.1101129932991e+02*1000.0, # 126 W(CaCO3     ,Na2SiO3  )
                17100.6, # 127 W(Ca3(PO4)2 ,KAlSiO4   )
                10374.2, # 128 W(H2O      ,KAlSiO4   )
                0.0, # 129 W(CO2      ,KAlSiO4   )
-2.7864967599360e+01*1000.0, # 130 W(CaCO3     ,KAlSiO4   )
                43451.3, # 131 W(H2O      ,Ca3(PO4)2 ) 130
-3.4728165916175e+00*1000.0, # 132 W(CO2      ,Ca3(PO4)2 )
2.0119124588637e+00*1000.0, # 133 W(CaCO3     ,Ca3(PO4)2 )
2.3255499914663e+01*1000.0, # 134 W(CO2      ,H2O       )
7.8729683594722e+00*1000.0, # 135 W(CaCO3     ,H2O       )
                0.0, # 180 W(CaCO3     ,CO2       )
    ]
else:
    w_values = []

```

```
paramValues = dict(zip(params, depen_species_values+w_values))
```

```
paramValues['T_r'] = 298.15
paramValues['P_r'] = 1.0
```

13.15 Generate code, load and compile the module

```

model_working_dir = "working"
!mkdir -p {model_working_dir}
%cd {model_working_dir}
model_type = "calib"

```

```

model.verbose = True
model.de_minimis = True
model.create_code_module(phase="Liquid",
                        params=paramValues,
                        endmembers=[
                            'SiO2_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'TiO2_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'Al2O3_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'Fe2O3_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'MgCr2O4_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'Fe2SiO4_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'MnSi1d2O2_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'Mg2SiO4_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'NiSi1d2O2_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'CoSi1d2O2_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'CaSiO3_rMELTS_ZR',
                            'Na2SiO3_rMELTS_ZR',

```

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```
        'KAlSiO4_rMELTS_ZR',  
        'Ca3P2O8_rMELTS_ZR',  
        'H2O_rMELTS_ZR',  
        'CO2_rMELTS_ZR',  
        'ZrSiO4_rMELTS_ZR'  
    ],  
    prefix="cy",  
    module_type=model_type,  
    silent=False,  
    add_code_to_access_order_paramater=True,  
    minimal_deriv_set=True)
```

```
import rMELTS_ZR  
%cd ..
```

13.16 Test identifier routines

```
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_identifier())  
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_name())
```


4-TESTS: MELTS LIQUID MODEL WITH ZRSIO4

API tests.Run Endmembers-MELTS and Liquid-MELTS-codegen notebooks first!

Proposed associated solution model:

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Variable:	Component:	Species X:
SiO2	SiO2			n_1	X_1
TiO2	TiO2		r_1	n_2	X_2
Al2O3	Al2O3		r_2	n_3	X_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		r_3	n_4	X_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		r_4	n_5	X_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		r_5	n_6	X_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		r_6	n_7	X_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		r_7	n_8	X_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		r_8	n_9	X_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		r_9	n_{10}	X_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		r_{10}	n_{11}	X_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		r_{11}	n_{12}	X_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		r_{12}	n_{13}	X_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		r_{13}	n_{14}	X_{14}
H2O	H2O		r_{14}	n_{15}	X_{15}
CO2	CO2		r_{15}	n_{16}	X_{16}
ZrSiO4	ZrSiO4		r_{16}	n_{17}	X_{17}
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_1		X_{18}
	Na4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 2\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 = \text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_2		X_{19}
	K4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 4\text{KAlSiO}_4 = \text{K}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{SiO}_2$	s_3		X_{20}

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from thermoengine import core
from thermoengine.model import Database
db = Database()
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)
```

- Number of components = 17

- Number of species = 24
- Number of “ordering parameters” (i.e., dependent species) = 7

```
nc = 17
nw = 20
ns = 3
```

```
model_working_dir = "working"
%cd {model_working_dir}
from pyximport import install
install()
import rMELTS_ZR
%cd ..
```

14.1 Test (T in K, P in bars)

```
t = 1000.00
p = 1000.0
```

Test identifier routines

```
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_identifier())
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_name())
```

14.2 Adjust parameters to initial estimates

```
mu0_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(0, t, p)
mu0_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(2, t, p)
mu0_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(3, t, p)
mu0_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(5, t, p)
mu0_CaSiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(10, t, p)
mu0_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(11, t, p)
mu0_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(12, t, p)
mu0_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(15, t, p)
mu0_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(16, t, p)
#
mu0dT_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(0, t, p)
mu0dT_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(2, t, p)
mu0dT_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(3, t, p)
mu0dT_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(5, t, p)
mu0dT_CaSiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(10, t, p)
mu0dT_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(11, t, p)
mu0dT_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(12, t, p)
mu0dT_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(15, t, p)
mu0dT_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(16, t, p)
#
mu0dP_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(0, t, p)
mu0dP_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(2, t, p)
mu0dP_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(3, t, p)
```

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```
mu0dP_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(5, t, p)
mu0dP_CaSiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(10, t, p)
mu0dP_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(11, t, p)
mu0dP_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(12, t, p)
mu0dP_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(15, t, p)
mu0dP_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(16, t, p)
```

Compute properties of CaCO₃:

- CaCO₃ calibration adjustments are from Ghiorso and Gualda (2015)

```
known_depen_species_values = [
    -1.7574497522747e+01*1000.0, 0.0, -1.9034060173857e+00, # H, S, V, CaCO3
]
```

```
h_delta_calib_CaCO3 = -1.7574497522747e+01*1000.0
s_delta_calib_CaCO3 = 0.0
v_delta_calib_CaCO3 = -1.9034060173857e+00
mu0_CaCO3 = mu0_CO2 + mu0_CaSiO3 - mu0_SiO2
mu0dT_CaCO3 = mu0dT_CO2 + mu0dT_CaSiO3 - mu0dT_SiO2
mu0dP_CaCO3 = mu0dP_CO2 + mu0dP_CaSiO3 - mu0dP_SiO2
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(2, mu0_CaCO3 - t*mu0dT_CaCO3 + h_delta_
↳calib_CaCO3)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(3, -mu0dT_CaCO3 + s_delta_calib_CaCO3)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(4, mu0dP_CaCO3 + v_delta_calib_CaCO3)
mu0_CaCO3 + h_delta_calib_CaCO3, mu0_CaCO3 - t*mu0dT_CaCO3 + h_delta_calib_CaCO3, -
↳mu0dT_CaCO3 + s_delta_calib_CaCO3, mu0dP_CaCO3 + v_delta_calib_CaCO3
```

Properties of the zirconium species are estimated by choosing a value for h, s, and v that zeros the delta difference of the exchange reaction

Na₄ZrSi₂O₈

```
mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0_Na2SiO3 - mu0_SiO2
mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dT_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0dT_Na2SiO3 - mu0dT_SiO2
mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dP_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0dP_Na2SiO3 - mu0dP_SiO2
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 -
↳(p-1.0)*mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, -mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8)
mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8, mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 - (p-1.0)*mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8, -
↳mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8, mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8
```

```
mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0_Al2O3
mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dT_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0dT_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0dT_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0dT_Al2O3
mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dP_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0dP_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0dP_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0dP_Al2O3
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 -
↳(p-1.0)*mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, -mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8)
mu0_K4ZrSi2O8, mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 - (p-1.0)*mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8, -mu0dT_
↳K4ZrSi2O8, mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8
```

```
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
```

14.3 Input composition and retrieve the ordering parameter

```
wtZrSiO4 = 183.31*0.001 # weight of ZrSiO4 equal to 0.001 moles of Zr
```

```
elm_sys = ['H', 'O', 'Na', 'Mg', 'Al', 'Si', 'P', 'K', 'Ca', 'Ti', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Fe', 'Co', 'Ni']
grm_oxides = {
    'SiO2': 77.5,
    'TiO2': 0.08,
    'Al2O3': 12.5,
    'Fe2O3': 0.207,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.473,
    'MnO': 0.0,
    'MgO': 0.03,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.43,
    'Na2O': 3.98,
    'K2O': 4.88,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
}
tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
for key in grm_oxides.keys():
    tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_moles=True)
mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
elm = np.zeros(107)
for i, sym in enumerate(
    ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P', 'H',
    ↪ 'C', 'O']):
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
    elm[index] = mol_elm[i]
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrSiO4/183.31
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Si')] += wtZrSiO4/183.31
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrSiO4*4.0/183.31
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
for i, x in enumerate(n):
    print ("{0:<12.12s} {1:10.6f} {2:10.6f}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_
    ↪ calib_endmember_name(i), x, mol_oxides[i] if i<16 else 0))
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for permissible_
    ↪ values.')
```

```
def print_species(n, s):
    fmt = '{0:>10s} {1:13.6g}'
    print (fmt.format(' SiO2', n[0]+s[0]+s[1]+3*s[2]))
    print (fmt.format(' TiO2', n[1]))
    print (fmt.format(' Al2O3', n[2]+2*s[2]))
    print (fmt.format(' Fe2O3', n[3]))
    print (fmt.format(' Cr2O3', n[4]))
    print (fmt.format(' Fe2SiO4', n[5]))
    print (fmt.format(' MnSi1/2O2', n[6]))
    print (fmt.format(' Mg2SiO4', n[7]))
```

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```
print (fmt.format(' NiSi1/2O2', n[8]))
print (fmt.format(' CoSi1/2O2', n[9]))
print (fmt.format('   CaSiO3', n[10]-s[0]))
print (fmt.format('   Na2SiO3', n[11]-2*s[1]))
print (fmt.format('   KAlSiO4', n[12]-4*s[2]))
print (fmt.format(' Ca3(PO4)2', n[13]))
print (fmt.format('   H2O', n[14]))
print (fmt.format('   CO2', n[15]-s[0]))
print (fmt.format('   ZrSiO4', n[16]-s[1]-s[2]))
print (fmt.format('   CaCO3', s[0]))
print (fmt.format('Na4ZrSi2O8', s[1]))
print (fmt.format(' K4ZrSi2O8', s[2]))
```

Speciation results

```
s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
print_species(n, s)
```

14.4 Test calls to API

Test some composition retrieval functions

```
e = np.zeros(106)
sum = np.sum(n)
for index in range(0,nc):
    end = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_elements(index)
    for i in range(0,106):
        e[i] += end[i]*n[index]/sum
nConv = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(e)
for i in range(0,nc):
    print ('X[{0:2d}] input {1:13.6e}, calc {2:13.6e}, diff {3:13.6e}'.format(
        i, n[i]/sum, nConv[i], nConv[i]-n[i]/sum))
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(nConv):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for permissible_
    ↪values.')
```

Test various conversion routines ...

```
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_moles_to_tot_moles(n))
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_moles_to_mole_frac(n))
e = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_moles_to_elm(n)
print (e)
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(e))
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_tot_moles(e))
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_tot_grams(e))
```

14.4.1 Execute the standard thermodynamic property retrieval functions:

```

fmt = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} {2:<10.10s}"
print(fmt.format('G', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_g(t,p,n), 'J'))
print(fmt.format('dGdT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdt(t,p,n), 'J/K'))
print(fmt.format('dGdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdp(t,p,n), 'J/bar'))
print(fmt.format('d2GdT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2(t,p,n), 'J/K^2
↳'))
print(fmt.format('d2GdTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdt2dp(t,p,n), 'J/K-
↳bar'))
print(fmt.format('d2GdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdp2(t,p,n), 'J/bar^2
↳'))
print(fmt.format('d3GdT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt3(t,p,n), 'J/K^3
↳'))
print(fmt.format('d3GdT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp(t,p,n), 'J/
↳K^2-bar'))
print(fmt.format('d3GdTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdt2dp2(t,p,n), 'J/
↳K-bar^2'))
print(fmt.format('d3GdP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdp3(t,p,n), 'J/bar^3
↳'))
print(fmt.format('S', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_s(t,p,n), 'J/K'))
print(fmt.format('V', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_v(t,p,n), 'J/bar'))
print(fmt.format('Cv', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cv(t,p,n), 'J/K'))
print(fmt.format('Cp', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_cp(t,p,n), 'J/K'))
print(fmt.format('dCpdT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dcpdt(t,p,n), 'J/K^2'))
print(fmt.format('alpha', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_alpha(t,p,n), '1/K'))
print(fmt.format('beta', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_beta(t,p,n), '1/bar'))
print(fmt.format('K', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_K(t,p,n), 'bar'))
print(fmt.format('Kp', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_Kp(t,p,n), ''))

```

14.4.2 Execute functions that access endmember properties:

```

fmt = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} {2:<15.15s}"
print("number of components", rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_number())
for index in range(0, nc):
    print("{0:<20.20s}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳name(index)), end=' ')
    print("{0:<20.20s}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳formula(index)), end=' ')
    print("mw: {0:10.2f}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳mw(index)))
    print(fmt.format('mu0', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(index,
↳t,p), 'J/mol'))
    print(fmt.format('dmu0dT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳dmu0dT(index,t,p), 'J/K-mol'))
    print(fmt.format('dmu0dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳dmu0dP(index,t,p), 'J/bar-mol'))
    print(fmt.format('d2mu0dT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳d2mu0dT2(index,t,p), 'J/K^2-mol'))
    print(fmt.format('d2mu0dTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳d2mu0dTdP(index,t,p), 'J/K-bar-mol'))
    print(fmt.format('d2mu0dP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳d2mu0dP2(index,t,p), 'J/bar^2-mol'))
    print(fmt.format('d3mu0dT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↳d3mu0dT3(index,t,p), 'J/K^3-mol'))

```

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```

print (fmt.format('d3mu0dT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↪d3mu0dT2dP(index,t,p), 'J/K^2-bar-mol'))
print (fmt.format('d3mu0dTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↪d3mu0dTdP2(index,t,p), 'J/K-bar^2-mol'))
print (fmt.format('d3mu0dP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_
↪d3mu0dP3(index,t,p), 'J/bar^3-mol'))
print ("Element array:")
print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_elements(index))
print ()

```

14.4.3 Execute functions that access species properties:

```

fmt = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} {2:<15.15s}"
print ("number of species", rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_species_number())
for index in range(0, nc):
    print ("{0:<20.20s}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_species_
↪name(index)), end=' ')
    print ("{0:<20.20s}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_species_
↪formula(index)), end=' ')
    print ("mw: {0:10.2f}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_species_
↪mw(index)))
    print ("Element array:")
    print (rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_species_elements(index))
    print ()

```

14.4.4 Execute functions for molar derivatives

First derivative vectors:

```

def printResult(name, result, units):
    print ("{0:<10.10s}".format(name), end=' ')
    [print ("{0:13.6e}".format(x), end=' ') for x in result]
    print ("{0:<10.10s}".format(units))
def printLabels(n):
    print ("{0:<18.18s}".format(''), end=' ')
    [print ("[{0:3d}] {1:<8.8s}".format(idx, ''), end=' ') for idx in range(len(n))]
    print ()
printLabels(n)
printResult('dGdn', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n), 'J/m')
printResult('d2GdndT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdndt(t,p,n), 'J/K-m')
printResult('d2GdndP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdndp(t,p,n), 'J/bar-m')
printResult('d3GdndT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdndt2(t,p,n), 'J/K^2-m
↪')
printResult('d3GdndTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdndtdp(t,p,n), 'J/K-
↪bar-m')
printResult('d3GdndP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdndp2(t,p,n), 'J/bar^2-
↪m')
printResult('d4GdndT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdndt3(t,p,n), 'J/K^3-m
↪')
printResult('d4GdndT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdndt2dp(t,p,n), 'J/K^
↪2-bar-m')

```

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```
printResult('d4GdndTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdndtdp2(t,p,n), 'J/K-
↪bar^2-m')
printResult('d4GdndP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdndp3(t,p,n), 'J/bar^3-
↪m')
```

The Hessian matrix (molar second derivative matrix) is stored as a compact linear array

A function is provided to map matrix indices to compact storage 1-D array indices

```
def printResult(name, result, units):
    print ("{0:<10.10s}".format(name), end=' ')
    [print ("{0:13.6e}".format(x), end=' ') for x in result]
    print ("{0:<10.10s}".format(units))
def printLabels(n):
    print ("{0:<18.18s}".format(''), end=' ')
    maxIdx = int(len(n)*(len(n)-1)/2 + len(n))
    [print ("[{0:3d}] {1:<8.8s}".format(idx, ''), end=' ') for idx in range(maxIdx)]
    print ()
printLabels(n)
printResult('d2Gdn2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d2gdn2(t,p,n), 'J/m^2')
printResult('d3Gdn2dT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdn2dt(t,p,n), 'J/K-m^2
↪')
printResult('d3Gdn2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdn2dp(t,p,n), 'J/bar-m^
↪2')
printResult('d4Gdn2dT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdn2dt2(t,p,n), 'J/K^2-
↪m^2')
printResult('d4Gdn2dTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdn2dtdp(t,p,n), 'J/K-
↪bar-m^2')
printResult('d4Gdn2dP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdn2dp2(t,p,n), 'J/bar^
↪2-m^2')
printResult('d5Gdn2dT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn2dt3(t,p,n), 'J/K^3-
↪m^2')
printResult('d5Gdn2dT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn2dt2dp(t,p,n), 'J/
↪K^2-bar-m^2')
printResult('d5Gdn2dTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn2dt2dp2(t,p,n), 'J/
↪K-bar^2-m^2')
printResult('d5Gdn2dP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn2dp3(t,p,n), 'J/bar^
↪3-m^2')
```

The 3-D Tensor (molar third derivative tensor) is stored as a compact linear array

A function is provided to map matrix indices to compact storage 1-D array indices: If n_c represents the number of components in the solution, and if n_d represents the dimensionality of molar derivative (in this case 3), then the number of numerically ordered permutations of n_c molar derivatives taken n_d at a time is:

```
def printResult(name, result, units):
    print ("{0:<10.10s}".format(name), end=' ')
    [print ("{0:10.3e}".format(x), end=' ') for x in result]
    print ("{0:<14.14s}".format(units))
def printLabels(n):
    print ("{0:<15.15s}".format(''), end=' ')
    maxIdx = int(len(n)*(len(n)+1)*(len(n)+2)/6)
```

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```
[print ("{0:3d} {1:<5.5s}".format(idx, ''), end=' ') for idx in range(maxIdx)]
print ()
printLabels(n)
printResult('d3Gdn3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d3gdn3(t,p,n), 'J/m^3')
printResult('d4Gdn3dT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdn3dt(t,p,n), 'J/K-m^3
↵')
printResult('d4Gdn3dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d4gdn3dp(t,p,n), 'J/bar-m^
↵3')
printResult('d5Gdn3dT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn3dt2(t,p,n), 'J/K^2-
↵m^3')
printResult('d5Gdn3dTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn3dtdp(t,p,n), 'J/K-
↵bar-m^3')
printResult('d5Gdn3dP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d5gdn3dp2(t,p,n), 'J/bar^
↵2-m^3')
printResult('d6Gdn3dT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d6gdn3dt3(t,p,n), 'J/K^3-
↵m^3')
printResult('d6Gdn3dT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d6gdn3dt2dp(t,p,n), 'J/
↵K^2-bar-m^3')
printResult('d6Gdn3dTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d6gdn3dtdp2(t,p,n), 'J/
↵K-bar^2-m^3')
printResult('d6Gdn3dP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_d6gdn3dp3(t,p,n), 'J/bar^
↵3-m^3')
```

```
nparam = 0
```

```
nparam = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_number()
names = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_names()
units = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_units()
values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
fmt = "{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} {2:13.6e} {3:<10.10s}"
for i in range(0,nparam):
    print(fmt.format(names[i], values[i], rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_
↵value(i), units[i]))
```

14.4.5 Functions that evaluate parameter derivatives ...

```
fmt = "    {0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e}"
for i in range(0, nparam):
    print ('Derivative with respect to parameter: ', names[i], ' of')
    print (fmt.format('G', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_g(t, p, n, i)))
    print (fmt.format('dGdT', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_dgdt(t, p, n, i)))
    print (fmt.format('dGdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_dgdp(t, p, n, i)))
    print (fmt.format('d2GdT2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d2gdt2(t, p, n,
↵i)))
    print (fmt.format('d2GdTdP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d2gtdp(t, p, n,
↵i)))
    print (fmt.format('d2GdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d2gdp2(t, p, n,
↵i)))
    print (fmt.format('d3GdT3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d3gdt3(t, p, n,
↵i)))
    print (fmt.format('d3GdT2dP', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d3gdt2dp(t, p,
↵n, i)))
```

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```
print (fmt.format('d3GdTdP2', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d3gtdp2(t, p, n, i)))
print (fmt.format('d3GdP3', rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_d3gdp3(t, p, n, i)))
```

14.4.6 Parameter derivatives of the chemical potential

```
def printResult(name, result, units):
    print ("dmu[*]/d {0:<10.10s}".format(name), end=' ')
    [print ("{0:13.6e}".format(x), end=' ') for x in result]
    print ("{0:<12.12s}".format(units))
def printLabels(n):
    print ("          {0:<18.18s}".format(''), end=' ')
    [print ("[{0:3d}] {1:<8.8s}".format(idx, ''), end=' ') for idx in range(len(n))]
    print ()
printLabels(n)
for i in range(0, nparam):
    result = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_dgdn(t,p,n, i)
    printResult(names[i], result, 'J/m^2/p-unit')
```


5-INITIAL PARAMETER ESTIMATES: MELTS LIQUID MODEL WITH ZRSIO4

Parameter and calibration exploration notebook. Run Endmembers-MELTS and Liquid-MELTS-codegen notebooks first!

Proposed associated solution model:

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Variable:	Component:	Species X:
SiO2	SiO2			n_1	X_1
TiO2	TiO2		r_1	n_2	X_2
Al2O3	Al2O3		r_2	n_3	X_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		r_3	n_4	X_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		r_4	n_5	X_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		r_5	n_6	X_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		r_6	n_7	X_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		r_7	n_8	X_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		r_8	n_9	X_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		r_9	n_{10}	X_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		r_{10}	n_{11}	X_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		r_{11}	n_{12}	X_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		r_{12}	n_{13}	X_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		r_{13}	n_{14}	X_{14}
H2O	H2O		r_{14}	n_{15}	X_{15}
CO2	CO2		r_{15}	n_{16}	X_{16}
ZrSiO4	ZrSiO4		r_{16}	n_{17}	X_{17}
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_1		X_{18}
	Na4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 2\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 = \text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_2		X_{19}
	K4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 4\text{KAlSiO}_4 = \text{K}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{SiO}_2$	s_3		X_{20}

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from thermoengine import core
from thermoengine.model import Database
db = Database()
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)
```

- Number of components = 17

- Number of species = 20
- Number of “ordering parameters” (i.e., dependent species) = 3

```
nc = 17
nw = 20
ns = 3
```

Import previously generated and compiled model

```
model_working_dir = "working"
%cd {model_working_dir}
from pyximport import install
install()
import rMELTS_ZR
%cd ..
```

Test identifier routines

```
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_identifier())
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_name())
```

Set a default temperature and pressure (T in K, P in bars)

```
t = 1000.00
p = 1000.0
```

15.1 Read common scripts

Execute scripts in the Jupyter notebook namespace so that methods have access to notebook variables.

```
%run -i support_scripts.py
```

15.2 Construct initial parameter estimates

Standard state properties of endmember components

```
for x,y in zip(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_names(), rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_
↳rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()):
    print ("{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6g}".format(x,y))
```

```
mu0_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(0, t, p)
mu0_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(2, t, p)
mu0_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(3, t, p)
mu0_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(5, t, p)
mu0_CaSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(10, t, p)
mu0_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(11, t, p)
mu0_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(12, t, p)
mu0_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(15, t, p)
mu0_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0(16, t, p)
```

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```
#
mu0dT_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(0, t, p)
mu0dT_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(2, t, p)
mu0dT_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(3, t, p)
mu0dT_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(5, t, p)
mu0dT_CaSiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(10, t, p)
mu0dT_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(11, t, p)
mu0dT_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(12, t, p)
mu0dT_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(15, t, p)
mu0dT_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT(16, t, p)
#
mu0dP_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(0, t, p)
mu0dP_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(2, t, p)
mu0dP_Fe2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(3, t, p)
mu0dP_Fe2SiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(5, t, p)
mu0dP_CaSiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(10, t, p)
mu0dP_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(11, t, p)
mu0dP_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(12, t, p)
mu0dP_CO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(15, t, p)
mu0dP_ZrSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP(16, t, p)
```

Compute properties of the CaCO₃ dependent species:

- CaCO₃ calibration adjustments are from Ghiorso and Gualda (2015)

```
known_depen_species_values = [
    -1.7574497522747e+01*1000.0, 0.0, -1.9034060173857e+00, # H, S, V, CaCO3
]
```

Set these parameter values in the model

```
h_delta_calib_CaCO3 = -1.7574497522747e+01*1000.0
s_delta_calib_CaCO3 = 0.0
v_delta_calib_CaCO3 = -1.9034060173857e+00
mu0_CaCO3 = mu0_CO2 + mu0_CaSiO3 - mu0_SiO2
mu0dT_CaCO3 = mu0dT_CO2 + mu0dT_CaSiO3 - mu0dT_SiO2
mu0dP_CaCO3 = mu0dP_CO2 + mu0dP_CaSiO3 - mu0dP_SiO2
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(2, mu0_CaCO3 - t*mu0dT_CaCO3 + h_delta_
↪calib_CaCO3)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(3, -mu0dT_CaCO3 + s_delta_calib_CaCO3)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(4, mu0dP_CaCO3 + v_delta_calib_CaCO3)
mu0_CaCO3 + h_delta_calib_CaCO3, mu0_CaCO3 - t*mu0dT_CaCO3 + h_delta_calib_CaCO3, -
↪mu0dT_CaCO3 + s_delta_calib_CaCO3, mu0dP_CaCO3 + v_delta_calib_CaCO3
```

15.2.1 Properties of the zirconium species are estimated by choosing a value for h, s, and v that zeros the delta difference of the exchange reaction


```
mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0_Na2SiO3 - mu0_SiO2
mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dT_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0dT_Na2SiO3 - mu0dT_SiO2
mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dP_ZrSiO4 + 2.0*mu0dP_Na2SiO3 - mu0dP_SiO2
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 -
↪(p-1.0)*mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8)
```

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```
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, -mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8)
mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8, mu0_Na4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8 - (p-1.0)*mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8, -
↳mu0dT_Na4ZrSi2O8, mu0dP_Na4ZrSi2O8
```



```
mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0_Al2O3
mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dT_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0dT_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0dT_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0dT_Al2O3
mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8 = mu0dP_ZrSiO4 + 4.0*mu0dP_KAlSiO4 - 3.0*mu0dP_SiO2 - 2.0*mu0dP_Al2O3
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 -
↳(p-1.0)*mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, -mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8)
mu0_K4ZrSi2O8, mu0_K4ZrSi2O8 - t*mu0dT_K4ZrSi2O8 - (p-1.0)*mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8, -mu0dT_
↳K4ZrSi2O8, mu0dP_K4ZrSi2O8
```

Summary of parameter estimates

```
for x,y in zip(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_names(), rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_
↳rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()):
    print ("{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6g}".format(x,y))
```

15.3 Specify an input composition

```
wtZrSiO4 = 183.31*0.001 # weight of ZrSiO4 equal to 0.001 moles of Zr
```

```
elm_sys = ['H', 'O', 'Na', 'Mg', 'Al', 'Si', 'P', 'K', 'Ca', 'Ti', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Fe', 'Co', 'Ni']
grm_oxides = {
    'SiO2': 77.5,
    'TiO2': 0.08,
    'Al2O3': 12.5,
    'Fe2O3': 0.207,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.473,
    'MnO': 0.0,
    'MgO': 0.03,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.43,
    'Na2O': 3.98,
    'K2O': 4.88,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
}
tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
for key in grm_oxides.keys():
    tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_moles=True)
mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
```

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```

elm = np.zeros(107)
for i,sym in enumerate(
    ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P', 'H',
    ↪ 'C', 'O']):
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
    elm[index] = mol_elm[i]
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrSiO4/183.31
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Si')] += wtZrSiO4/183.31
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrSiO4*4.0/183.31
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
for i,x in enumerate(n):
    print ("{0:<12.12s} {1:10.6f} {2:10.6f}".format(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_
    ↪calib_endmember_name(i), x, mol_oxides[i] if i<16 else 0))
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for permissible_
    ↪values.')
```

Modify the input composition to create

- the most oxidized state (all ferric iron and sulfate)
- or, the most reduced state (all ferrous iron and sulfide)

15.4 Speciate the solution

Print equilibrium results

```

s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
print_species(n, s)
```

15.5 Save revised parameter values

```

param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
param_values
```

```

import pickle

with open('params.pickle', 'wb') as f:
    pickle.dump(param_values, f, pickle.HIGHEST_PROTOCOL)
```

```

import pickle

with open('params.pickle', 'rb') as f:
    params_stored = pickle.load(f)
```

```

params_stored
```

6-CALIBRATION: MELTS LIQUID MODEL WITH ZRSIO4

Parameter and calibration exploration notebook. Run Endmembers-MELTS, Liquid-MELTS-codegen, Liquid-MELTS-API-tests and Liquid=MELTS-calib-1 notebooks first!

Proposed associated solution model:

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Variable:	Component:	Species X:
SiO2	SiO2			n_1	X_1
TiO2	TiO2		r_1	n_2	X_2
Al2O3	Al2O3		r_2	n_3	X_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		r_3	n_4	X_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		r_4	n_5	X_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		r_5	n_6	X_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		r_6	n_7	X_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		r_7	n_8	X_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		r_8	n_9	X_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		r_9	n_{10}	X_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		r_{10}	n_{11}	X_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		r_{11}	n_{12}	X_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		r_{12}	n_{13}	X_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		r_{13}	n_{14}	X_{14}
H2O	H2O		r_{14}	n_{15}	X_{15}
CO2	CO2		r_{15}	n_{16}	X_{16}
ZrSiO4	ZrSiO4		r_{16}	n_{17}	X_{17}
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_1		X_{18}
	Na4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 2\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 = \text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_2		X_{19}
	K4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 4\text{KAlSiO}_4 = \text{K}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{SiO}_2$	s_3		X_{20}

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from thermoengine import core, coder, phases
import sympy as sym
import math
sym.init_printing()
from thermoengine.model import Database
db = Database()
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

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```
import scipy as sci
%matplotlib inline
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)
```

- Number of components = 17
- Number of species = 20
- Number of “ordering parameters” (i.e., dependent species) = 3

```
nc = 17
nw = 20
ns = 3
```

Import previously generated and compiled model

```
model_working_dir = "working"
%cd {model_working_dir}
from pyximport import install
install()
import rMELTS_ZR
%cd ..
```

Test identifier routines

```
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_identifier())
print(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_name())
```

16.1 Read in parameter estimates from first calibration notebook

```
import pickle
with open('params.pickle', 'rb') as f:
    params_stored = pickle.load(f)
for i,x in enumerate(params_stored):
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(i, x)
```

16.2 Create models for zirconium-bearing minerals

```
model = coder.StdStateModel()
model.set_module_name('zirconium_minerals')
model_type = "calib"
T = model.get_symbol_for_t()
P = model.get_symbol_for_p()
Tr = model.get_symbol_for_tr()
Pr = model.get_symbol_for_pr()
```

16.2.1 Formulation, Robie RA, Hemingway BS, 1995

Thermodynamic Properties of Minerals and Related Substances at 298.15 K and 1 Bar (105 Pascals) Pressure and at Higher Temperatures. U.S. Geological Survey, Bulletin 2131, 461pp

- $\Delta H_f, S, V, C_p$
- $C_p = A_1 + A_2T + \frac{A_3}{T^2} + \frac{A_4}{\sqrt{T}} + A_5T^2$

```
h0,s0,a1,a2,a3,a4,a5,v = sym.symbols('h0 s0 a1 a2 a3 a4 a5 v')
params = [
    ('h0', 'J', h0),
    ('s0', 'J/K', s0),
    ('a1', 'J/K', a1),
    ('a2', 'J/K^2', a2),
    ('a3', 'J-K', a3),
    ('a4', 'J/K^1/2', a4),
    ('a5', 'J/K^3', a5),
    ('v', 'J/bar', v)
]
Cp = a1 + a2*T + a3/T**2 + a4/sym.sqrt(T) + a5*T**2
G = h0 + sym.integrate(Cp, (T,Tr,T)) - T*(s0 + sym.integrate(Cp/T, (T,Tr,T))) + sym.
↳integrate(v, (P,Pr,P))
model.add_expression_to_model(G, params)
```

```
model_working_dir = "working"
!mkdir -p {model_working_dir}
%cd {model_working_dir}
```

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'zircon',
    'Formula': 'Zr(1)Si(1)O(4)',
    'h0': -2034200.0,
    's0': 84.0,
    'v': 3.926,
    'a1': 2.370e2,
    'a2': -1.788e-2,
    'a3': -1.496e5,
    'a4': -2.268e3,
    'a5': 0.0,
    'T_r': 298.15,
    'P_r': 1.0,
    'trl': 1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
↳'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cp zirconium_minerals.pyx endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list = ['zircon_zirconium_minerals_calib.c']
endmember_name_list = ['zircon']
```

```
param_dict = {
    'Phase': 'baddeleyite',
    'Formula': 'Zr(1)O(2)',
    'h0': -1100600.0,
    's0': 50.4,
    'a1': 1.073e2,
```

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```
'a2':      -5.011e-3,
'a3':      -2.203e5,
'a4':      -8.141e2,
'a5':      0.0,
'v':      2.115,
'T_r':     298.15,
'P_r':     1.0,
'trl':     1673.15
}
result = model.create_code_module(phase=param_dict['Phase'], formula=param_dict[
    ↪ 'Formula'], params=param_dict, module_type=model_type)
%cat zirconium_minerals.pyx >> endmembers.pyx
endmember_file_list.append('baddeleyite_zirconium_minerals_calib.c')
endmember_name_list.append('baddeleyite')
```

```
with open('zirconium_minerals.pyxbld', 'r') as f:
    fold = f.read()
    f.close()
old_file_list = "" + endmember_file_list[-1] + ""
new_file_list = ''
sep = ''
for x in endmember_file_list:
    new_file_list += sep + "" + x + ""
    sep = ", "
fnew = fold.replace(old_file_list, new_file_list)
with open('zirconium_minerals.pyxbld', 'w') as f:
    f.write(fnew)
    f.close()
%cp endmembers.pyx zirconium_minerals.pyx
```

```
import zirconium_minerals
%cd ..
```

16.3 Read common scripts

Execute scripts in the Jupyter notebook namespace so that methods have access to notebook variables.

```
%run -i support_scripts.py
```

16.4 Function to calculate affinities for these reactions:

$\text{ZrSiO}_4 = \text{ZrSiO}_4$ (zircon)
 $\text{ZrSiO}_4 = \text{ZrO}_2$ (baddeleyite) + SiO_2

```
def zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=True):
    global zirconium_minerals
    G0zirc = zirconium_minerals.cy_zircon_zirconium_minerals_calib_g(t,p)
    G0badd = zirconium_minerals.cy_baddeleyite_zirconium_minerals_calib_g(t,p)
    affinities = []
    affinities.append(mu[16] - G0zirc)
```

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```
affinities.append(mu[16] - G0badd - mu[0])
if print_results:
    print ('Affinity {0:<12.12s} {1:12.3f}'.format('zircon', affinities[0]))
    print ('Affinity {0:<12.12s} {1:12.3f}'.format('baddeleyite', affinities[1]))
return tuple(affinities)
```

16.5 Guess some parameter values (from a first pass through the primary calibration data)

- Exchange entropies and volumes are maintained at zero
- Free parameters are enthalpies of ZrSiO₄, Na₄ZrSi₂O₈ and K₄ZrSi₂O₈, and the entropy and volume of ZrSiO₄

These estimates are arrived at by guess work minimization of residuals. They are not final values.

```
ref_param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
ref_param_values
```

```
adj_H_ZrSiO4 = 100000.0 + 22020.0 + 107500.0 - 32110.0
adj_S_ZrSiO4 = 40.0242 + 83.7465 - 27.8937
adj_V_ZrSiO4 = 0.5448 - 0.2236 - 0.110
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_H_ZrSiO4_
↳- 225000.0) # Na4ZrSi2O8
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_H_ZrSiO4_
↳- 75000.0) # K4ZrSi2O8
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, ref_param_values[10] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(11, ref_param_values[11] + adj_H_
↳ZrSiO4) # ZrSiO4
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(12, ref_param_values[12] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(13, ref_param_values[13] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
```

```
param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
param_values
```

16.6 Evaluate zircon saturation data

- two primary sources:
 - Watson EB and Harrison TM (1983) Zircon saturation revisited: temperature and composition effects in a variety of crustal magma types. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 64, 295-304
 - Boehnke P, Watson EB, Trail D, Harrison TM, Schmitt AK (2013) Zircon saturation re-visited. *Chemical Geology*, 351, 324-334

Read data sources (Excel files) as Pandas dataframes

```
df1 = pd.read_csv('Watson_and_Harrison.csv')
df1.fillna(0)
```

```
for i,x in enumerate(df1.columns):
    print (i+1, x)
```

```
df2 = pd.read_csv('Boehnke_et_al.csv')
df2.fillna(0)
```

```
for i,x in enumerate(df2.columns):
    print (i+1, x)
```

Process the two data sets and store residual information and other results in the following Python lists:

- x_data[] - data index
- y_data[] - residual
- n_liq[] - liquid compositional vector
- s_liq[] - liquid species concentration vector
- t_data[] - temperature in Kelvins
- p_data[] - pressure in bars
- name[] - source string or experimental descriptor
- s_data[] - source author id (1, 2)
- y_est[] - estimated value of Zr liquid concentration in PPM (value that zeros residuals)
- y_con[] - True or False regarding convergence of y_est
- y_ref[] - measured value of Zr liquid concentration

```
name = []
x_data = []
y_data = []
n_liq = []
s_liq = []
t_data = []
p_data = []
s_data = []
y_est = []
y_con = []
y_ref = []
auth_dat = []
for df in [df1, df2]:
    df_iterator = df.itertuples()
    #
    for row_indx,data in enumerate(df_iterator):
        auth_id = data[3]
        t = data[25 if auth_id == 1 else 17] + 273.15
        p = data[26 if auth_id == 1 else 18]*10000.0
        if data[4] != 'Liquid':
            continue
        grm_oxides = {
```

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```

'SiO2': data[5 if auth_id == 1 else 5],
'TiO2': data[7 if auth_id == 1 else 6],
'Al2O3': data[9 if auth_id == 1 else 7],
'Fe2O3': 0.0,
'Cr2O3': 0.0,
'FeO': data[11 if auth_id == 1 else 8],
'MnO': 0.0,
'MgO': data[13 if auth_id == 1 else 9],
'NiO': 0.0,
'CoO': 0.0,
'CaO': data[15 if auth_id == 1 else 10],
'Na2O': data[17 if auth_id == 1 else 11],
'K2O': data[19 if auth_id == 1 else 12],
'P2O5': 0.0,
'H2O': data[24 if auth_id == 1 else 15],
'CO2': 0.01
}
tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
for key in grm_oxides.keys():
    tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_
↪moles=True)
#
NNO = db.redox_buffer(t, p, buffer='NNO', method='LEPR')
ox_moles = mol_oxides.reshape(1,nc-1)
db.redox_state(t, p,
               oxide_comp={'Liq':ox_moles},
               logfO2=np.array(NNO),
               phase_of_interest='Liq', method='Kress91')
#print ('n Fe2O3 at NNO moles = {0:10.8f}'.format(ox_moles[0,3]))
#print ('n FeO at NNO moles = {0:10.8f}'.format(ox_moles[0,5]))
mol_oxides[3] = ox_moles[0,3]
mol_oxides[5] = ox_moles[0,5]
#
mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
elm = np.zeros(107)
for i,sym in enumerate(
    ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P
↪', 'H', 'C', 'O']):
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
    elm[index] = mol_elm[i]
#
wtZrO2 = data[22 if auth_id == 1 else 13]
if wtZrO2 > 1.0:
    continue
auth_dat.append(auth_id)
y_ref.append(wtZrO2)
elm_ref = np.copy(elm)
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for_
↪permissible values.')
    continue
s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)

```

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```

mu = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n)
y = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=False)[0]
#
# Estimate zirconium content by zeroing the residuals
def residual(log_wtZrO2_est, doprint=False):
    global elm_ref, t, p
    wtZrO2_est = np.exp(log_wtZrO2_est)
    elm_est = np.copy(elm_ref)
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2_est/123.
↪218
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2_est*2.0/
↪123.218
    n_est = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm_est)
    mu_est= rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n_est)
    result = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu_est, print_results=False)[0]
    if doprint:
        print (wtZrO2_est, result)
    return result
#
try:
    sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(residual,
                                  #x0=np.log(wtZrO2),
                                  #x1=np.log(wtZrO2*10.),
                                  rtol=1.e-5,
                                  bracket=[-5,2.3],
                                  method='brentq',
                                  maxiter=50)

    print (sol)
    y_est.append(np.exp(sol.root))
    y_con.append(sol.converged)
except ValueError:
    print ('Solution not within brackets')
    y_est.append(0.0)
    y_con.append(False)
#
print (auth_id, data[2], y)
s_data.append(auth_id)
name.append(data[2])
x_data.append(row_indx)
y_data.append(y)
n_liq.append(n)
s_liq.append(s)
t_data.append(t)
p_data.append(p)

```

Residual statistics and a linear regression that provides rough estimates of H, S and V for ZrSiO₄

```

print ('Average residual:', np.mean(np.array(y_data)))
print ('Std Dev residual:', np.std(np.array(y_data)))

```

```

import statsmodels.api as sm

```

```

X = sm.add_constant(np.column_stack((t_data, p_data)))
results = sm.OLS(np.array(y_data), X).fit()
results.summary()

```

16.6.1 Analysis of residuals

Back calculation of Zr concentrations made by zeroing residuals

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if y_con[i]]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if y_con[i]]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if not y_con[i]]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if not y_con[i]]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([0,1]), np.array([0,1]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('wt ZrO2 est')
plt.xlabel('wt ZrO2 data')
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.plot(np.array([91.224*1000000.0*x/100.0/123.218 for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if y_
->con[i]]),
         np.array([91.224*1000000.0*x/100.0/123.218 for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if y_
->con[i]]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([0,7000]), np.array([0,7000]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('ppm ZrO2 est')
plt.xlabel('ppm ZrO2 data')
#axes = plt.gca()
#axes.set_xlim(0,1)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show
```

Residuals from fitting the two data sets (red is Watson and Harrison, blue is Boehnke et al.)

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,3,1)
plt.plot([min(x_data),max(x_data)], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.subplot(1,3,2)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,0]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,0])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,0] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,0] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X SiO2')
plt.subplot(1,3,3)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,16]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,16])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,16] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,16] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X ZrSiO4')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Examine residual (zircon affinity) dependence on alkali and water concentrations

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,3,1)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,11] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,11] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X Na2SiO3')
plt.subplot(1,3,2)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,12] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,12] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X KAlSiO4')
plt.subplot(1,3,3)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,14]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,14])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,14] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([np.array(n_liq)[i,14] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X H2O')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Examine residual (zircon affinity) dependence on temperature

```
plt.plot([min(t_data),max(t_data)], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([t_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([t_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('T K')
plt.show()
```

Examine residual (zircon affinity) dependence on pressure

```
plt.plot([min(p_data),max(p_data)], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array([p_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([p_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]),
         np.array([y_data[i] for i,x in enumerate(s_data) if x == 2]), 'b+')

plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('P (GPa)')
plt.show()
```

Examine Zr-speciation of the liquid

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,3,1)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+')
```

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```
plt.ylabel('n ZrSiO4')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.subplot(1,3,2)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'r+')
plt.ylabel('n Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.subplot(1,3,3)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'r+')
plt.ylabel('n K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('n Na2SiO3')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('n KAlSiO4')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

Remember these results before lists are over written with the peralkaline dataset

```
name_all = [] + name
x_data_all = [] + x_data
y_data_all = [] + y_data
n_liq_all = [] + n_liq
s_liq_all = [] + s_liq
t_data_all = [] + t_data
p_data_all = [] + p_data
s_data_all = [] + s_data
y_est_all = [] + y_est
y_con_all = [] + y_con
y_ref_all = [] + y_ref
```

16.7 Evaluate peralkaline compositions reported in Watson (1979)

```
df3 = pd.read_excel('Watson_1979.xlsx')
df3.fillna(0)
```

```
for i,x in enumerate(df3.columns):
    print (i+1, x)
```

Re-estimate “optimal” parameters for this data set

```
print (ref_param_values)
```

```
adj_H_ZrSiO4 = 100000.0 + 22020.0 + 107500.0 - 32110.0
adj_S_ZrSiO4 = 40.0242 + 83.7465 - 27.8937
adj_V_ZrSiO4 = 0.5448 - 0.2236 - 0.110
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_H_ZrSiO4_
↳ 225000.0 - 50000.0) # Na4ZrSi2O8
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_H_ZrSiO4_
↳ 75000.0 - 50000.0) # K4ZrSi2O8
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, ref_param_values[10] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(11, ref_param_values[11] + adj_H_
↳ ZrSiO4) # ZrSiO4
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(12, ref_param_values[12] + adj_S_ZrSiO4)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(13, ref_param_values[13] + adj_V_ZrSiO4)
```

```
param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
print (param_values)
```

Analyze the data set

```
df_iterator = df3.itertuples()
name = []
x_data = []
y_data = []
n_liq = []
s_liq = []
t_data = []
p_data = []
s_data = []
y_est = []
y_con = []
y_ref = []
jacobian = []
for row_idx,data in enumerate(df_iterator):
    auth_id = data[1]
    t = data[4] + 273.15
    p = data[5]
    grm_oxides = {
        'SiO2': data[6],
        'TiO2': 0.0,
```

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```

    'Al2O3': data[7],
    'Fe2O3': max(data[8], 0.01),
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.0,
    'MnO': 0.0,
    'MgO': 0.0,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': max(data[9], 0.01),
    'Na2O': data[10],
    'K2O': data[11],
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 6.5,
    'CO2': 0.01
}
auth_dat.append(3)
tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
for key in grm_oxides.keys():
    tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_
↪moles=True)
#
if data[8] > 0.0:
    NNO = db.redox_buffer(t, p, buffer='NNO', method='LEPR')
    ox_moles = mol_oxides.reshape(1,nc-1)
    db.redox_state(t, p,
                    oxide_comp={'Liq':ox_moles},
                    logfO2=np.array(NNO),
                    phase_of_interest='Liq', method='Kress91')
    #print ('n Fe2O3 at NNO moles = {0:10.8f}'.format(ox_moles[0,3]))
    #print ('n FeO at NNO moles = {0:10.8f}'.format(ox_moles[0,5]))
    mol_oxides[3] = ox_moles[0,3]
    mol_oxides[5] = ox_moles[0,5]
#
mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
elm = np.zeros(107)
for i,sym in enumerate(
    ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P',
↪'H', 'C', 'O']):
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
    elm[index] = mol_elm[i]
#
wtZrO2 = 100.0*123.218*data[2]/91.224/1000000.0
y_ref.append(wtZrO2)
elm_ref = np.copy(elm)
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for_
↪permissible values.')
    continue
s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
mu = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t, p, n)
y = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=False)[0]
#

```

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```

# Estimate zirconium content by zeroing the residuals
def residual(log_wtZrO2_est, doprint=False):
    global elm_ref, t, p
    wtZrO2_est = np.exp(log_wtZrO2_est)
    elm_est = np.copy(elm_ref)
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2_est/123.218
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2_est*2.0/123.
↪218
    n_est = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm_est)
    mu_est= rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n_est)
    result = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu_est, print_results=False)[0]
    if doprint:
        print (wtZrO2_est, result)
    return result

#
try:
    sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(residual,
                                  #x0=np.log(wtZrO2),
                                  #x1=np.log(wtZrO2*10.),
                                  rtol=1.e-5,
                                  bracket=[-5,2.3],
                                  method='brentq',
                                  maxiter=50)

    print (sol)
    y_est.append(np.exp(sol.root))
    y_con.append(sol.converged)
except ValueError:
    print ('Solution not within brackets')
    y_est.append(0.0)
    y_con.append(False)

#
dparam = []
for i in range(0,rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_number()):
    D2gDnDparam = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_dparam_dgdn(t, p, n, i)
    dparam.append(D2gDnDparam[16])

#
print (auth_id, data[2], y)
s_data.append(auth_id)
name.append(data[12])
x_data.append(row_indx)
y_data.append(y)
n_liq.append(n)
s_liq.append(s)
t_data.append(t)
p_data.append(p)
jacobian.append(dparam)

```

Residual statistics

```

print ('Average residual:', np.mean(np.array(y_data)))
print ('Std Dev residual:', np.std(np.array(y_data)))

```

```

for i,y in enumerate(y_data):
    if y > 40000.0 or y < -20000.0:
        print ('{0:10.2f} {1:5s} {2:<10s} {3:10.2f} {4:10.2f} {5:7.3f}'.format(y,
↪str(s_data[i]), name[i], t_data[i], p_data[i], y_ref[i]))

```

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```
results = sm.OLS(np.array(y_data), np.array(t_data)).fit()
results.summary()
```

Select a subset of data points to identify in plots (these are “natural” compositions - with iron and calcium)

```
selection = [name.index('PPK(g)'), name.index('PK(g)'), name.index('KPK(g)'), name.
    ↪index('K(g)')]
```

Estimated Zr concentration plotted against measured concentration

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if y_con[i]]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if y_con[i]]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if not y_con[i]]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if not y_con[i]]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([y_ref[i] for i in selection]),
         np.array([y_est[i] for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.plot(np.array([0,max(y_ref)]), np.array([0,max(y_ref)]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('wt ZrO2 est')
plt.xlabel('wt ZrO2 data')
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.plot(np.array([91.224*1000000.0*x/100.0/123.218 for i,x in enumerate(y_ref) if y_
    ↪con[i]]),
         np.array([91.224*1000000.0*x/100.0/123.218 for i,x in enumerate(y_est) if y_
    ↪con[i]]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([0,91.224*1000000.0*max(y_ref)/100.0/123.218]), np.array([0,91.
    ↪224*1000000.0*max(y_ref)/100.0/123.218]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('ppm ZrO2 est')
plt.xlabel('ppm ZrO2 data')
#axes = plt.gca()
#axes.set_xlim(0,1)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show
```

Examine residuals (zircon affinity) for the Watson (1979) data set

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,3,1)
plt.plot([min(x_data),max(x_data)], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([y_data[i] for i in_
    ↪selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.subplot(1,3,2)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,0]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,0])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array(n_liq)[: ,0]), np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array(n_liq[i] for i in selection)[: ,0]), np.array([y_data[i]_
    ↪for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X SiO2')
plt.subplot(1,3,3)
```

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```
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,16]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,16])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array(n_liq)[: ,16]), np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,16]), np.array([y_data[i]_
↳for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X ZrSiO4')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Examine residuals (zircon affinity) dependence on alkali content

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11]), np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,11]), np.array([y_data[i]_
↳for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X Na2SiO3')
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.plot([min(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12]),max(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12])], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12]), np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,12]), np.array([y_data[i]_
↳for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('X KAlSiO4')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Examine residuals (zircon affinity) dependence on temperature

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.plot([min(t_data)-273.15,max(t_data)-273.15], [0.0,0.0], 'g-')
plt.plot(np.array(t_data)-273.15, np.array(y_data), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([t_data[i] for i in selection])-273.15, np.array([y_data[i] for i_
↳in selection]), 'ko')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.xlabel('T °C')
plt.show()
```

Examine Zr-speciation

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,3,1)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([n_liq[i] for i in_
↳selection])[: ,16], 'ko')
plt.ylabel('n ZrSiO4')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.subplot(1,3,2)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([s_liq[i] for i in_
↳selection])[: ,1], 'ko')
plt.ylabel('n Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('index')
```

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```

plt.subplot(1,3,3)
plt.plot(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳selection])[: ,2], 'ko')
plt.ylabel('n K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([n_liq[i] for i in
↳selection])[: ,16], 'ro')
plt.semilogy(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳selection])[: ,1], 'go')
plt.semilogy(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳selection])[: ,2], 'bo')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.semilogy(np.array(x_data), np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+')
plt.semilogy(np.array([x_data[i] for i in selection]), np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳selection])[: ,1], 'go')
plt.ylabel('n Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('index')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,11], np.array([n_liq[i] for i
↳in selection])[: ,16], 'ro')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,11], np.array([s_liq[i] for i
↳in selection])[: ,1], 'go')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,11], np.array([s_liq[i] for i
↳in selection])[: ,2], 'bo')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('n Na2SiO3')
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,11], np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,11], np.array([s_liq[i] for i
↳in selection])[: ,1], 'go')
plt.ylabel('n Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('n Na2SiO3')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(n_liq)[: ,16], 'r+', label='ZrSiO4')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(s_liq)[: ,1], 'g+', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,12], np.array([n_liq[i] for i in
↳in selection])[: ,16], 'ro')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,12], np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳in selection])[: ,1], 'go')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,12], np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳in selection])[: ,2], 'bo')
plt.ylabel('n Zr species')
plt.xlabel('n KAlSiO4')
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.semilogy(np.array(n_liq)[: ,12], np.array(s_liq)[: ,2], 'b+')
plt.semilogy(np.array([n_liq[i] for i in selection])[: ,12], np.array([s_liq[i] for i in
↳in selection])[: ,2], 'bo')
plt.ylabel('n K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('n KAlSiO4')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Select Watson (1979) data points for inclusion in final data fit

```
#selection = [name.index('PPK(g)'), name.index('PK(g)'), name.index('KPK(g)'), name.
↳index('K(g)')]
selection = []
```

```
name_all += [name[i] for i in selection]
x_data_all += [x_data[i] for i in selection]
y_data_all += [y_data[i] for i in selection]
n_liq_all += [n_liq[i] for i in selection]
s_liq_all += [s_liq[i] for i in selection]
t_data_all += [t_data[i] for i in selection]
p_data_all += [p_data[i] for i in selection]
s_data_all += [s_data[i] for i in selection]
y_est_all += [y_est[i] for i in selection]
y_con_all += [y_con[i] for i in selection]
y_ref_all += [y_ref[i] for i in selection]
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.plot(np.array([2*x[11]/x[12] for x in n_liq_all]), np.array([y[1]/y[2] for y in s_
↳liq_all]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([0,5]), np.array([0,5]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('n Na4ZrSi2O8 / n K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.xlabel('n 2*Na2SiO3 / n KAlSiO4')
plt.show()
```

16.8 Optimize parameters from experimental data sets

Note that this process resets the parameter array to the resulting optimization

```
def res_func(x, t_data, p_data, n_liq,
            ref_param_values, rMELTS_ZR, adj_H_ZrSiO4, adj_S_ZrSiO4, adj_V_ZrSiO4,
            use_weighting,
            use_priors, prior_weight,
            zirconium_min_affinities):
    y = []
    priors = []
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_H_
    ↪ZrSiO4 - 225000.0 + x[0]) # Na4ZrSi2O8
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_S_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_V_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[4])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_H_
    ↪ZrSiO4 - 75000.0 + x[1]) # K4ZrSi2O8
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_S_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, ref_param_values[10] + adj_V_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[4])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(11, ref_param_values[11] + adj_H_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[2]) # ZrSiO4
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(12, ref_param_values[12] + adj_S_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(13, ref_param_values[13] + adj_V_
    ↪ZrSiO4 + x[4])
    for t, p, n in zip(t_data, p_data, n_liq):
        mu = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t, p, n)
        s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
        affinity = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=False)[0]
        weight = 1.0
        if use_weighting:
            weight = ((2*n[11]/n[12])/(s[1]/s[2]) + (s[1]/s[2])/(2*n[11]/n[12]))/2 #_
    ↪+= (2*n[11]/n[12] - s[1]/s[2])**2
        y.append(affinity*weight)
        if use_priors:
            priors.append(prior_weight*np.log((2*n[11]/n[12])/(s[1]/s[2])))
    return np.array(y+priors)
```

Bayesian prior: $w_p \log \left(\frac{2n_{12}}{\frac{n_{13}}{y_{13}} \frac{y_{20}}{y_{20}}} \right)$ to impose Watson's Na/K observation

```
use_weighting = False
use_priors = True
prior_weight = 2500.0
#
# perform fit
fit_res = sci.optimize.least_squares(res_func,
                                   [0.0, 0.0, -50000.0, 0, 0],
                                   bounds=(np.array([ -np.inf, -np.inf, -np.inf, -
    ↪np.inf, -np.inf]),
                                   np.array([ np.inf, np.inf, np.inf,
    ↪np.inf, np.inf])
                                   ),
```

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```

jac='3-point',
method='trf',
ftol=None, gtol=1.0e-8,
args=(t_data_all, p_data_all, n_liq_all, ref_
↳param_values, rMELTS_ZR,
adj_H_ZrSiO4, adj_S_ZrSiO4, adj_V_ZrSiO4,
↳use_weighting, use_priors,
prior_weight, zirconium_min_affinities),
verbose=2)
#
# recalculate residuals associated with the reaction affinity
y_data_rev = res_func(fit_res.x, t_data_all, p_data_all, n_liq_all,
ref_param_values, rMELTS_ZR, adj_H_ZrSiO4, adj_S_ZrSiO4, adj_V_
↳ZrSiO4, False, False,
prior_weight, zirconium_min_affinities)
rms_residuals = np.sqrt(np.mean(y_data_rev**2))
#
# sigma is calculated from the full Jacobian, including rows associated with priors
sigma = np.sqrt(np.diagonal(np.linalg.inv(2*np.matmul(fit_res.jac.T, fit_res.
↳jac)))*rms_residuals**2)
print ('X:', fit_res.x)
print ('grad', fit_res.grad)
print ('Optimality:', fit_res.optimality)
print ('nfev:', fit_res.nfev)
print ('njev:', fit_res.njev)
print ('status:', fit_res.status)
print ('message:', fit_res.message)
print ('success:', fit_res.success)
print ('rms of affinity residuals', rms_residuals)
print ('H Na4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 225000.0,
ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 225000.0 + fit_res.x[0],
fit_res.x[0], - 225000.0 + fit_res.x[0], sigma[0]))
print ('H K4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 75000.0,
ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 75000.0 + fit_res.x[1],
fit_res.x[1], - 75000.0 + fit_res.x[1], sigma[1]))
print ('H ZrSiO4 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
ref_param_values[11] + adj_H_ZrSiO4,
ref_param_values[11] + adj_H_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[2],
fit_res.x[2], adj_H_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[2], sigma[2]))
print ('S ZrSiO4 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
ref_param_values[12] + adj_S_ZrSiO4,
ref_param_values[12] + adj_S_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[3],
fit_res.x[3], adj_S_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[3], sigma[3]))
print ('V ZrSiO4 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
ref_param_values[13] + adj_V_ZrSiO4,
ref_param_values[13] + adj_V_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[4],
fit_res.x[4], adj_V_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[4], sigma[4]))
print ('S Na4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(

```

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```

    ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_S_ZrSiO4,
    ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_S_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[3],
    fit_res.x[3], 0.0, sigma[3]))
print ('V Na4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}↳
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
    ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_V_ZrSiO4,
    ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_V_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[4],
    fit_res.x[4], 0.0, sigma[4]))
print ('S K4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}↳
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
    ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_S_ZrSiO4,
    ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_S_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[3],
    fit_res.x[3], 0.0, sigma[3]))
print ('V K4ZrSi2O8 old: {0:12.2f} new: {1:12.2f} dif: {2:12.2f} param: {3:12.2f}↳
↳sigma: {4:12.5g}'.format(
    ref_param_values[10] + adj_V_ZrSiO4,
    ref_param_values[10] + adj_V_ZrSiO4 + fit_res.x[4],
    fit_res.x[4], 0.0, sigma[4]))

```

Construct a parameter correlation matrix from the Jacobian evaluated at the optimal solution

```

print ('Estimated parameter correlation matrix:')
cov_mat = np.linalg.inv(2*np.matmul(fit_res.jac.T, fit_res.jac))*rms_residuais**2
labl = ['', 'H Na4', 'H K4', 'H Zr', 'S Zr', 'V Zr']
for x in labl:
    print ('{0:>12.12s}'.format(x), end=' ')
print ('')
for i,row in enumerate(cov_mat):
    print ('{0:>12.12s}'.format(labl[i+1]), end=' ')
    for j,col in enumerate(row):
        print ('{0:12.6g}'.format(col/sigma[i]/sigma[j]), end=' ')
    print ('')

```

Decompose the Jacobian (evaluated at the optimal solution) using singular value analysis

```

u,s,vT = np.linalg.svd(fit_res.jac)
for col in s:
    print ('{0:13.6g}'.format(col), end=' ')
print ('')
print ('')
for row in vT.T:
    for col in row:
        print ('{0:13.6g}'.format(col), end=' ')
    print ('')

```

Residual statistics (compared to guessed parameter fit)

```

print ('Average residual before: {0:13.6g} fit: {1:13.6g} fit+prior: {2:13.6g}'.
↳format(np.mean(np.array(y_data_all)), np.mean(y_data_rev), np.mean(fit_res.fun)))
print ('Std Dev residual before: {0:13.6g} fit: {1:13.6g} fit+prior: {2:13.6g}'.
↳format(np.std(np.array(y_data_all)), np.std(y_data_rev), np.std(fit_res.fun)))

```

Monte Carlo analysis of parameter variance

```

deviates = np.random.multivariate_normal(fit_res.x, cov_mat, size=100)
plt.figure(figsize=(20,5))
plt.subplot(1,5,1)
plt.hist(deviates[:,0], orientation='horizontal')
plt.title('H Na4ZrSi2O8')
plt.subplot(1,5,2)
plt.hist(deviates[:,1], orientation='horizontal')
plt.title('H K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.subplot(1,5,3)
plt.hist(deviates[:,2], orientation='horizontal')
plt.title('H ZrSiO4')
plt.subplot(1,5,4)
plt.hist(deviates[:,3], orientation='horizontal')
plt.title('S ZrSiO4')
plt.subplot(1,5,5)
plt.hist(deviates[:,4], orientation='horizontal')
plt.title('V ZrSiO4')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Recompute speciation and plot Na/K ratio of Zr species against Na/K bulk composition ratio

```

s_revised = []
for t, p, n in zip(t_data_all, p_data_all, n_liq_all):
    s_revised.append(rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n))
s_revised = s_revised
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
plt.loglog(np.array([2*x[11]/x[12] for x in n_liq_all]), np.array([y[1]/y[2] for y in
    s_revised]), 'r+')
plt.loglog(np.array([0,5]), np.array([0,5]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('Na/K species ratio')
plt.xlabel('Na/K reported ratio')
plt.grid(True)
plt.xticks([0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9,1,2,3,4,5],
    ['', '0.6', '0.7', '0.8', '0.9', '1', '2', '3', '4', '5'])
plt.yticks([0.1,0.2,0.3,0.4,0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,20,30,40,50,60,
    70,80,90,100],
    ['0.1', '', '', '', '0.5', '', '', '', '1', '', '', '', '5', '', '', '', '10', '', '',
    '50', '', '', '100'])
#plt.ylim(0,5)
plt.show()
fig.savefig("Figure_Na_K.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')

```

Estimate zirconium content by zeroing the residuals

```

Zr_meas = []
Zr_pred = []
def residual(log_Zr_est, t, p, nLiq):
    Zr_est = np.exp(log_Zr_est)
    wtZrO2_est = 100.0*123.218*Zr_est/91.224/1000000.0
    elm_est = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_moles_to_elm(nLiq)
    Zr_old = elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')]
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] -= Zr_old
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] -= 2.0*Zr_old
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2_est/123.218
    elm_est[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2_est*2.0/123.218

```

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```
n_est = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm_est)
mu_est= rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n_est)
result = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu_est, print_results=False)[0]
return result
#
for t_in, p_in, n_in, y_ref in zip(t_data_all, p_data_all, n_liq_all, y_ref_all):
    try:
        sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(residual,
                                      args=(t_in, p_in, n_in),
                                      rtol=1.e-5,
                                      bracket=[0,10],
                                      method='brentq',
                                      maxiter=50)

        print (sol)
        Zr_pred.append(np.exp(sol.root))
        Zr_meas.append(91.224*1000000.0*y_ref/123.218/100.0)
    except ValueError:
        print ('Solution not within brackets')
```

```
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
#plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.loglog(np.array(Zr_meas), np.array(Zr_pred), 'r+')
plt.loglog(np.array([100,10000]), np.array([100, 10000]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('Zr PPM predicted value')
plt.xlabel('Zr PPM reported value')
plt.grid(True)
plt.xticks([100,200,300,400,500,600,700,800,900,1000,2000,3000,4000,5000,6000,7000,
            ↪8000,9000,10000],
            ['100',' ',' ',' ','500',' ',' ',' ',' ','1000',' ',' ',' ','5000',' ',' ',' ',' ','10000
            ↪'])
plt.yticks([100,200,300,400,500,600,700,800,900,1000,2000,3000,4000,5000,6000,7000,
            ↪8000,9000,10000],
            ['100',' ',' ',' ','500',' ',' ',' ',' ','1000',' ',' ',' ','5000',' ',' ',' ',' ','10000
            ↪'])
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
fig.savefig("Figure_Zr_Zr.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
```

If the priors constraints are imposed, compare affinity residuals and prior residuals

```
if use_priors:
    jac_rows = int(fit_res.fun.shape[0]/2)
    fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
    plt.subplot(2,2,1)
    plt.plot(np.array(n_liq_all)[: ,11], fit_res.fun[:jac_rows], 'r+', label='affin')
    plt.plot(np.array(n_liq_all)[: ,11], fit_res.fun[jac_rows:], 'b+', label='prior')
    plt.xlabel('n Na2SiO3')
    plt.ylabel('residual')
    plt.grid(True)
    plt.legend()
    plt.subplot(2,2,2)
    plt.plot(np.array(n_liq_all)[: ,12], fit_res.fun[:jac_rows], 'r+', label='affin')
    plt.plot(np.array(n_liq_all)[: ,12], fit_res.fun[jac_rows:], 'b+', label='prior')
    plt.xlabel('n KAlSiO4')
    plt.ylabel('residual')
```

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```
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(2,2,3)
plt.plot(np.array(t_data_all), fit_res.fun[:jac_rows], 'r+', label='affin')
plt.plot(np.array(t_data_all), fit_res.fun[jac_rows:], 'b+', label='prior')
plt.xlabel('T (K)')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(2,2,4)
plt.plot(np.array(p_data_all), fit_res.fun[:jac_rows], 'r+', label='affin')
plt.plot(np.array(p_data_all), fit_res.fun[jac_rows:], 'b+', label='prior')
plt.xlabel('P (bars)')
plt.ylabel('residual')
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show
fig.savefig("Figure_Residuals.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
```

Compared guessed parameter residuals (x axis) against optimized parameter residuals (y axis)

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
#plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 2]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 3]), 'k+')
plt.plot(np.array([y_data_all[i] for i in selection]),
         np.array([fit_res.fun[i] for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.plot(np.array([-10000,10000]), np.array([-10000, 10000]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('fit residual')
plt.xlabel('inp residual')
#plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Compare temperature correlation to residuals (zircon affinities) calculated using parameter guesses and parameter fit

```
plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]),
         np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]), 'k+')
plt.plot(np.array([t_data_all[i] for i in selection]),
         np.array([y_data_all[i] for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.plot(np.array([min(t_data_all), max(t_data_all)]), np.array([0, 0]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('fit residual')
plt.xlabel('T (K)')
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]),
```

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```

        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 2]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(t_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 3]), 'k+')
plt.plot(np.array([t_data_all[i] for i in selection]),
        np.array([fit_res.fun[i] for i in selection]), 'ko')
plt.plot(np.array([min(t_data_all), max(t_data_all)]), np.array([0, 0]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('fit residual')
plt.xlabel('T (K)')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Compare pressure correlation to residuals (zircon affinities) calculated using parameter guesses and parameter fit

```

plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]), 'k+')
plt.plot(np.array([min(p_data_all), max(p_data_all)]), np.array([0, 0]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('fit residual')
plt.xlabel('P (bars)')
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 1]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 1]), 'r+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 2]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 2]), 'b+')
plt.plot(np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(p_data_all) if auth_dat[i] == 3]),
        np.array([x for i,x in enumerate(y_data_rev) if auth_dat[i] == 3]), 'k+')
plt.plot(np.array([min(p_data_all), max(p_data_all)]), np.array([0, 0]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('fit residual')
plt.xlabel('P (bars)')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

16.9 Plot zircon saturation surface

Assemble a dictionary of interesting compositions

- Bishop Tuff rhyolite composition is LBT from Gualda
- Pantellerite composition is from Carmichael ISA, Turner FJ, Verhoogen J (1974) *Igneous Petrology*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 739pp; page 237, Table 5-1, column 1. Water content estimated at 2.5 wt% from ion-probe data reported in Lowenstern JB, Mahood GA (1991) New data on magmatic H₂O contents of pantellerites, with implications for petrogenesis and eruptive dynamics of Pantelleria. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 54, 78-83
- Carmichael reports Zr concentration in the pantellerite is 1800 PPM
- Trachyte, Phonolite in Carmichael, Turner and Verhoogen (1974), p36, Table 2-3
- Dacite, in Carmichael, Turner and Verhoogen (1974), page 9

- Madupite is LH.16 in Carmichael ISE (1967) The Mineralogy and Petrology of the Volcanic Rocks from the Leucite Hills, Wyoming. Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology, 15, 24-66. It contains appreciable wadeite, $Zr_2K_4Si_6O_{18}$. This rock has 0.27 wt% ZrO_2 . The Wyomingite is LH.3 . The rock has no Zr analysis but other wyomingites have 0.28 wt% ZrO_2 . All the analyses are from Table 12 (page 50).

```
composition_d = {
  'rhyolite': { # Bishop Tuff
    'SiO2': 77.5,
    'TiO2': 0.08,
    'Al2O3': 12.5,
    'Fe2O3': 0.207,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.473,
    'MnO': 0.0,
    'MgO': 0.03,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.43,
    'Na2O': 3.98,
    'K2O': 4.88,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'Iceland-rhyolite': { # Carmichael, Turner and Verhoogen, p 237; 385 PPM Zr (p. 75)
    'SiO2': 74.96,
    'TiO2': 0.23,
    'Al2O3': 12.55,
    'Fe2O3': 1.72,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.71,
    'MnO': 0.04,
    'MgO': 0.02,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.90,
    'Na2O': 4.41,
    'K2O': 3.65,
    'P2O5': 0.04,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'California-rhyolite': { # Carmichael, Turner and Verhoogen, p 237
    'SiO2': 75.04,
    'TiO2': 0.07,
    'Al2O3': 12.29,
    'Fe2O3': 0.33,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.71,
    'MnO': 0.05,
    'MgO': 0.04,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.58,
    'Na2O': 4.03,
    'K2O': 4.66,
  }
}
```

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```

    'P2O5': 0.01,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'dacite': {
    'SiO2': 63.58,
    'TiO2': 0.64,
    'Al2O3': 16.67,
    'Fe2O3': 2.24,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 3.00,
    'MnO': 0.11,
    'MgO': 2.12,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 5.53,
    'Na2O': 3.98,
    'K2O': 1.40,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 3.00,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'pantellerite': { # Pantellerite, Carmichael Turner and Verhoogen, p 237
    'SiO2': 69.81,
    'TiO2': 0.45,
    'Al2O3': 8.59,
    'Fe2O3': 2.28,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 5.76,
    'MnO': 0.28,
    'MgO': 0.10,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.42,
    'Na2O': 6.46,
    'K2O': 4.49,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 2.5,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'comendite': { # Comendite, Carmichael Turner and Verhoogen, p 237
    'SiO2': 73.06,
    'TiO2': 0.23,
    'Al2O3': 9.76,
    'Fe2O3': 2.74,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 2.70,
    'MnO': 0.13,
    'MgO': 0.10,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.32,
    'Na2O': 5.64,
    'K2O': 4.34,
    'P2O5': 0.02,
    'H2O': 2.5,

```

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```

    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'trachyte': {
    'SiO2': 57.73,
    'TiO2': 1.18,
    'Al2O3': 17.05,
    'Fe2O3': 2.55,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 4.35,
    'MnO': 0.28,
    'MgO': 1.11,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 3.10,
    'Na2O': 6.81,
    'K2O': 4.27,
    'P2O5': 0.34,
    'H2O': 1.0,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'phonolite': {
    'SiO2': 54.55,
    'TiO2': 1.60,
    'Al2O3': 19.00,
    'Fe2O3': 1.75,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 3.78,
    'MnO': 0.16,
    'MgO': 1.76,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 4.07,
    'Na2O': 9.06,
    'K2O': 3.64,
    'P2O5': 0.20,
    'H2O': 1.0,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },
  'madupite': { # Leucite Hills, Wyoming
    'SiO2': 43.56,
    'TiO2': 2.31,
    'Al2O3': 7.85,
    'Fe2O3': 5.57,
    'Cr2O3': 0.04,
    'FeO': 0.85,
    'MnO': 0.15,
    'MgO': 11.03,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 11.89,
    'Na2O': 0.74,
    'K2O': 7.19,
    'P2O5': 1.50,
    'H2O': 1.0,
    'CO2': 0.05
  },

```

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```
'wyomingite': { # Leucite Hills, Wyoming
    'SiO2': 50.23,
    'TiO2': 2.27,
    'Al2O3': 11.22,
    'Fe2O3': 3.34,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 1.84,
    'MnO': 0.05,
    'MgO': 7.09,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 5.99,
    'Na2O': 1.37,
    'K2O': 9.81,
    'P2O5': 1.89,
    'H2O': 2.0,
    'CO2': 0.05
}
}
```

Define a function to generate a zircon or badeyelite saturation plot

```
def generate_saturation_plot(phase='zircon',
                             use_composition='rhyolite',
                             p=2000.0,
                             tmin=700.0,
                             tmax=1000.0,
                             tinc=25,
                             ref_Zr_l=None, # list
                             Zr_PPM_root_min=10.0,
                             Zr_PPM_root_max=500000.0,
                             print_steps=True,
                             debug=False,
                             deviates=None,
                             deviate_plot_quantiles=False
                             ):
    global composition_d, core, plt, sci, np, rMELTS_ZR
    #
    grm_oxides = composition_d[use_composition]
    elm_sys = ['H', 'O', 'Na', 'Mg', 'Al', 'Si', 'P', 'K', 'Ca', 'Ti', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Fe', 'Co', 'Ni']
    tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
    for key in grm_oxides.keys():
        tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
    mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_
    moles=True)
    mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
    elm_ref = np.zeros(107)
    for i, sym in enumerate(
        ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P',
        'H', 'C', 'O']):
        index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
        elm_ref[index] = mol_elm[i]
    #
    # Function used by minimizer
    def zero(x):
        global rMELTS_ZR
```

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```

elm = np.copy(elm_ref)
Zr_ppm = x
wtZrO2 = 123.218*Zr_ppm/91.224/1000000.0
wtZrO2 *= tot_grm_oxides + wtZrO2
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
    print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for
↳permissible values.')
    mu = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n)
    y = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=False)[0 if phase ==
↳'zircon' else 1]
    if debug:
        print (t, Zr_ppm, y)
        print (n)
    return y
#
T_array = np.linspace(tmin, tmax, tinc, endpoint=True)
if deviates is not None:
    remember_param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
    yPlot_all = []
    species_all = []
    for irow, row in enumerate(deviates):
        if np.mod(irow,10) == 0:
            print ('Processing deviate:', irow)
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, ref_param_values[ 5] +
↳adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 225000.0 + row[0]) # Na4ZrSi2O8
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, ref_param_values[ 6] +
↳adj_S_ZrSiO4
            + row[3])
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, ref_param_values[ 7] +
↳adj_V_ZrSiO4
            + row[4])
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, ref_param_values[ 8] +
↳adj_H_ZrSiO4 - 75000.0 + row[1]) # K4ZrSi2O8
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, ref_param_values[ 9] +
↳adj_S_ZrSiO4
            + row[3])
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, ref_param_values[10] +
↳adj_V_ZrSiO4
            + row[4])
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(11, ref_param_values[11] +
↳adj_H_ZrSiO4
            + row[2]) # ZrSiO4
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(12, ref_param_values[12] +
↳adj_S_ZrSiO4
            + row[3])
            rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(13, ref_param_values[13] +
↳adj_V_ZrSiO4
            + row[4])
        yPlot = []
        species = []
        for tc in T_array:
            t = tc + 273.15
            y = zero(100)
            sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(zero, bracket=[Zr_PPM_root_min, Zr_PPM_
↳root_max])
            yPlot.append(sol.root)
            elm = np.copy(elm_ref)
            wtZrO2 = 123.218*sol.root/91.224/1000000.0
            wtZrO2 *= tot_grm_oxides + wtZrO2
            elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218

```

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```

elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.
↪218
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
tot = n[16] + s[1] + s[2]
species.append(np.array([100*n[16]/tot, 100*s[1]/tot, 100*s[2]/tot]))
#
yPlot_all.append(np.array(yPlot))
species_all.append(np.array(species))
yPlot = np.transpose(np.array(yPlot_all))
species = np.array(species_all)
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_values(remember_param_values)
else:
yPlot = []
species = []
for tc in T_array:
if print_steps:
print('{0:7.1f}'.format(tc), end=' ')
t = tc + 273.15
y = zero(100)
sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(zero, bracket=[Zr_PPM_root_min, Zr_PPM_
↪root_max])
yPlot.append(sol.root)
#
elm = np.copy(elm_ref)
wtZrO2 = 123.218*sol.root/91.224/1000000.0
wtZrO2 *= tot_grm_oxides + wtZrO2
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elm_to_moles(elm)
s = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_order_params(t, p, n)
tot = n[16] + s[1] + s[2]
species.append(np.array([100*n[16]/tot, 100*s[1]/tot, 100*s[2]/tot]))
if print_steps:
print('{0:10.1f} {1:1.1s} {2:2d} {3:6.2f} {4:6.2f} {5:6.2f}'.format(
sol.root, 'T' if sol.converged else 'F', sol.iterations,
↪100*n[16]/tot, 100*s[1]/tot, 100*s[2]/tot
))
#
yPlot = np.array(yPlot)
species = np.array(species)
#
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,5))
plt.subplot(1,2,1)
plt.title(phase+' saturation for '+use_composition+' composition')
if deviate_plot_quantiles and deviates is not None:
plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(yPlot,0.50,axis=1), 'r-', label='mean')
plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(yPlot,0.05,axis=1), 'r--', label='5 %')
plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(yPlot,0.95,axis=1), 'r--', label='95 %')
plt.legend()
else:
plt.plot(T_array, yPlot, 'r-')
if ref_Zr_l is not None:
for x in ref_Zr_l:
plt.plot(np.array([tmin, tmax]), np.array([x,x]), 'g-')
plt.ylabel('PPM Zr')

```

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```

plt.xlabel('T °C')
#
plt.subplot(1,2,2)
plt.title('Zr speciation for '+use_composition+' composition')
if deviates is not None:
    if deviate_plot_quantiles:
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 0], 0.50, axis=0), 'r-', label=
↪ 'ZrSiO4 mean')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 0], 0.05, axis=0), 'r--', label=
↪ 'ZrSiO4 5%')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 0], 0.95, axis=0), 'r--', label=
↪ 'ZrSiO4 95%')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 1], 0.50, axis=0), 'g-', label=
↪ 'Na4ZrSi2O8 mean')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 1], 0.05, axis=0), 'g--', label=
↪ 'Na4ZrSi2O8 5%')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 1], 0.95, axis=0), 'g--', label=
↪ 'Na4ZrSi2O8 95%')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 2], 0.50, axis=0), 'b-', label=
↪ 'K4ZrSi2O8 mean')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 2], 0.05, axis=0), 'b--', label=
↪ 'K4ZrSi2O8 5%')
        plt.plot(T_array, np.quantile(species[:, :, 2], 0.95, axis=0), 'b--', label=
↪ 'K4ZrSi2O8 95%')
    else:
        for i in range(0, deviates.shape[0]):
            if i == 0:
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 0], 'r-', label='ZrSiO4')
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 1], 'g-', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 2], 'b-', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
            else:
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 0], 'r-')
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 1], 'g-')
                plt.plot(T_array, species[i, :, 2], 'b-')
    else:
        plt.plot(T_array, species[:, 0], 'r-', label='ZrSiO4')
        plt.plot(T_array, species[:, 1], 'g-', label='Na4ZrSi2O8')
        plt.plot(T_array, species[:, 2], 'b-', label='K4ZrSi2O8')
plt.ylabel('% Zr-species')
plt.xlabel('T °C')
plt.legend()
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
fig.savefig(phase + "_sat_" + use_composition + ".pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
return (T_array, yPlot, species)

```

Make some plots of zircon saturation for various compositions

```

T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='rhyolite', ref_Zr_
↪ l=[80, 100, 120], tmin=700, tmax=800, print_steps=False)

```

```

T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='rhyolite', ref_Zr_
↪ l=[80, 100, 120], tmin=700, tmax=800, print_steps=False,
                                                    deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_
↪ quantiles=True)

```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='California-  
↪rhyolite', ref_Zr_l=[110], tmax=800, print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='Iceland-rhyolite',  
↪ ref_Zr_l=[385], print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='dacite', tmin=700,  
↪ ref_Zr_l=[150], Zr_PPM_root_min=1.0,  
print_steps=False, debug=False,  
↪deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='pantellerite',  
↪ref_Zr_l=[1800],  
tmin=700, tmax=900, print_  
↪steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='comendite', ref_  
↪Zr_l=[1250], print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='trachyte', ref_Zr_  
↪l=None, print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='phonolite', ref_  
↪Zr_l=None, print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

This rock is saturated with a wadeite solid solution

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='madupite',  
↪tmin=700.0, tmax=1200.0, ref_Zr_l=[2073],  
Zr_PPM_root_min=1.0, Zr_PPM_root_  
↪max=250000.0, print_steps=False,  
deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_  
↪quantiles=True)
```

This rock is saturated with wadeite, $\text{Zr}_2\text{K}_4\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}$ in solid solution with its Ti-equivalent, $\text{Ti}_2\text{K}_4\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}$

```
T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(use_composition='wyomingite',  
↪tmin=700.0, tmax=1200.0, ref_Zr_l=[2073],  
Zr_PPM_root_min=10.0, Zr_PPM_root_  
↪max=500000.0, print_steps=False, debug=False,
```

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```

deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_
↪quantiles=True)

```

```

T_array, yPlot, species = generate_saturation_plot(phase='badelyite', use_composition=
↪'wyomingite', tmin=700.0, tmax=1200.0, ref_Zr_l=[2073],
                                                    Zr_PPM_root_min=10.0, Zr_PPM_root_
↪max=500000.0, print_steps=False, debug=False,
                                                    deviates=deviates, deviate_plot_
↪quantiles=True)

```

16.10 Zircon Geothermometer

```

def zircon_geothermometer(use_composition='rhyolite', # str references dictionary_
↪element in composition_d, else dictionary
                        ref_Zr_ppm=100, p=2000.0, tmin=500.0, tmax=1200.0,
                        print_steps=True, debug=False):
    global composition_d, core, plt, sci, np, rMELTS_ZR
    #
    if isinstance(use_composition, str):
        grm_oxides = composition_d[use_composition]
    else:
        grm_oxides = use_composition
    elm_sys = ['H', 'O', 'Na', 'Mg', 'Al', 'Si', 'P', 'K', 'Ca', 'Ti', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Fe', 'Co', 'Ni']
    tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
    for key in grm_oxides.keys():
        tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
    mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_
↪moles=True)
    mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
    elm_ref = np.zeros(107)
    for i, sym in enumerate(
        ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P',
↪'H', 'C', 'O']):
        index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
        elm_ref[index] = mol_elm[i]
    #
    elm = np.copy(elm_ref)
    Zr_ppm = ref_Zr_ppm
    wtZrO2 = 123.218*Zr_ppm/91.224/1000000.0
    wtZrO2 *= tot_grm_oxides + wtZrO2
    elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
    elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
    n = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_conv_elem_to_moles(elm)
    if not rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_test_moles(n):
        print ('Output of intrinsic composition calculation fails tests for_
↪permissible values.')
    return
    # Function used by minimizer
    def zero(t):
        global rMELTS_ZR
        mu = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_dgdn(t,p,n)
        y = zirconium_min_affinities(t, p, mu, print_results=False)[0]

```

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```

    if debug:
        print (t)
    return y

#
remember_param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
results = np.zeros(deviates.shape[0])
for irow, row in enumerate(deviates):
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(5, ref_param_values[ 5] + adj_
↪H_ZrSiO4 - 225000.0 + row[0]) # Na4ZrSi2O8
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(6, ref_param_values[ 6] + adj_
↪S_ZrSiO4
        + row[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(7, ref_param_values[ 7] + adj_
↪V_ZrSiO4
        + row[4])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(8, ref_param_values[ 8] + adj_
↪H_ZrSiO4 - 75000.0 + row[1]) # K4ZrSi2O8
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(9, ref_param_values[ 9] + adj_
↪S_ZrSiO4
        + row[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(10, ref_param_values[10] + adj_
↪V_ZrSiO4
        + row[4])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(11, ref_param_values[11] + adj_
↪H_ZrSiO4
        + row[2]) # ZrSiO4
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(12, ref_param_values[12] + adj_
↪S_ZrSiO4
        + row[3])
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(13, ref_param_values[13] + adj_
↪V_ZrSiO4
        + row[4])
    try:
        sol = sci.optimize.root_scalar(zero, bracket=[tmin, tmax])
    except ValueError:
        print ('No valid temperature solution in interval', tmin, 'to', tmax)
        return
    results[irow] = sol.root
rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_values(remember_param_values)
t_mean = np.quantile(results, 0.50) - 273.15
t_05   = np.quantile(results, 0.05) - 273.15
t_95   = np.quantile(results, 0.95) - 273.15
return (t_mean, t_05, t_95)

```

```
zircon_geothermometer(p=1750)
```

```
zircon_geothermometer(use_composition='dacite', ref_Zr_ppm=150)
```

```
zircon_geothermometer(use_composition = {
    'SiO2': 63.58,
    'TiO2': 0.64,
    'Al2O3': 16.67,
    'Fe2O3': 2.24,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 3.00,
    'MnO': 0.11,
    'MgO': 2.12,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 5.53,

```

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```
'Na2O': 3.98,
'K2O': 1.40,
'P2O5': 0.0,
'H2O': 3.00,
'CO2': 0.05
}, ref_Zr_ppm=200)
```



```
t = 1000.00
p = 1000.0
def exchange_prop(t=1000, p=1000, param_test=ref_param_values):
    mu0_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0( 0, t, p)
    mu0_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0( 2, t, p)
    mu0_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0( 11, t, p)
    mu0_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_mu0( 12, t, p)
    S0_SiO2 = -rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT( 0, t, p)
    S0_Al2O3 = -rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT( 2, t, p)
    S0_Na2SiO3 = -rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT( 11, t, p)
    S0_KAlSiO4 = -rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dT( 12, t, p)
    V0_SiO2 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP( 0, t, p)
    V0_Al2O3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP( 2, t, p)
    V0_Na2SiO3 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP( 11, t, p)
    V0_KAlSiO4 = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_calib_endmember_dmu0dP( 12, t, p)
    H0_SiO2 = mu0_SiO2 + t*S0_SiO2 - (p-1.0)*V0_SiO2
    H0_Al2O3 = mu0_Al2O3 + t*S0_Al2O3 - (p-1.0)*V0_Al2O3
    H0_Na2SiO3 = mu0_Na2SiO3 + t*S0_Na2SiO3 - (p-1.0)*V0_Na2SiO3
    H0_KAlSiO4 = mu0_KAlSiO4 + t*S0_KAlSiO4 - (p-1.0)*V0_KAlSiO4
    deltaH = param_test[ 8] + 2*H0_Na2SiO3 + 2*H0_Al2O3 + 2*H0_SiO2 - param_test[ 5] -
    ↪ 4*H0_KAlSiO4
    deltaS = param_test[ 9] + 2*S0_Na2SiO3 + 2*S0_Al2O3 + 2*S0_SiO2 - param_test[ 6] -
    ↪ 4*S0_KAlSiO4
    deltaV = param_test[10] + 2*V0_Na2SiO3 + 2*V0_Al2O3 + 2*V0_SiO2 - param_test[ 7] -
    ↪ 4*V0_KAlSiO4
    return (deltaH, deltaS, deltaV)
exchange_prop()
```

```
exchange_prop(param_test=rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values())
```

16.11 Save revised parameter values

```
new_param_values = rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_get_param_values()
new_param_values
```

```
import pickle

with open('calib_params.pickle', 'wb') as f:
    pickle.dump(new_param_values, f, pickle.HIGHEST_PROTOCOL)
```

```
import pickle

with open('calib_params.pickle', 'rb') as f:
    params_stored = pickle.load(f)
```

```
params_stored
```

16.12 Evaluate data from the experimental study of Gervasoni et al. (2016)

```
df4 = pd.read_excel('Gervasoni_2016.xlsx')
df4.fillna(0)
```

```
import matplotlib.colors as mcolors
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
df_iterator = df4.itertuples()
for row_indx,data in enumerate(df_iterator):
    compo = {
        'SiO2': data[6],
        'TiO2': data[7],
        'Al2O3': data[8],
        'Fe2O3': data[9]*0.1,
        'Cr2O3': 0.0,
        'FeO': data[9]*0.9,
        'MnO': 0.0,
        'MgO': data[10],
        'NiO': 0.0,
        'CoO': 0.0,
        'CaO': data[11],
        'Na2O': data[12],
        'K2O': data[13],
        'P2O5': 0.0,
        'H2O': 0.1,
        'CO2': 0.01
    }
    result = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_ppm=data[2],
    ↪tmax=2000.0, p=data[5])
    result_l = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_ppm=data[2]-
    ↪data[3], tmax=2000.0, p=data[5])
    result_h = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_
    ↪ppm=data[2]+data[3], tmax=2000.0, p=data[5])
    plt.errorbar(data[2], data[4], xerr=data[3], fmt='ro', label=data[1]+'
    ↪'+str(data[2])) # mean, low, high
    plt.errorbar(data[2], result[0],
    ↪yerr=np.array([[np.fabs(result[1]-result[0])], [np.fabs(result[2]-
    ↪result[0])]]), fmt='bo')
    plt.errorbar(data[2]-data[3], result_l[0],
    ↪yerr=np.array([[np.fabs(result_l[1]-result_l[0])], [np.fabs(result_
    ↪l[2]-result_l[0])]]), fmt='b,')
    plt.errorbar(data[2]+data[3], result_h[0],
    ↪yerr=np.array([[np.fabs(result_h[1]-result_h[0])], [np.fabs(result_
    ↪h[2]-result_h[0])]]), fmt='b,')
```

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```

plt.plot(np.array([data[2], data[2]]), np.array([data[4], result[0]]), 'k--')
plt.plot(np.array([data[2]-data[3], data[2]+data[3]]), np.array([result_l[1],
↪result_h[1]]), 'b-')
plt.plot(np.array([data[2]-data[3], data[2]+data[3]]), np.array([result_l[2],
↪result_h[2]]), 'b-')
plt.fill(np.array([data[2]-data[3], data[2]+data[3], data[2]+data[3], data[2]-
↪data[3], data[2]-data[3]]),
        np.array([result_l[2], result_h[2], result_h[1], result_l[1], result_
↪l[2]]),
        color=mcolors.CSS4_COLORS['lightyellow'])
plt.title('Gervasoni et al., 2016, temperature recovery')
plt.ylabel('T °C')
plt.xlabel('Zr (PPM)')
plt.legend()
fig.savefig("Gervasoni_et_al.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()

```

16.13 Calibrant temperature recovery

```

plot_watson = False
plot_boenke = True
fig, main_plt = plt.subplots(figsize=(15,10))
T_meas = []
T_estm = []
T_estm_l = []
T_estm_h = []
lst = []
if plot_watson:
    lst.append(df1)
if plot_boenke:
    lst.append(df2)
for df in lst:
    df_iterator = df.itertuples()
    #
    for row_indx, data in enumerate(df_iterator):
        #print (row_indx)
        auth_id = data[3]
        t = data[25 if auth_id == 1 else 17]
        p = data[26 if auth_id == 1 else 18]*10000.0
        if data[4] != 'Liquid':
            continue
        compo = {
            'SiO2': data[5 if auth_id == 1 else 5],
            'TiO2': data[7 if auth_id == 1 else 6],
            'Al2O3': data[9 if auth_id == 1 else 7],
            'Fe2O3': 0.0,
            'Cr2O3': 0.0,
            'FeO': data[11 if auth_id == 1 else 8],
            'MnO': 0.0,
            'MgO': data[13 if auth_id == 1 else 9],
            'NiO': 0.0,
            'CoO': 0.0,
            'CaO': data[15 if auth_id == 1 else 10],

```

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```

        'Na2O': data[17 if auth_id == 1 else 11],
        'K2O': data[19 if auth_id == 1 else 12],
        'P2O5': 0.0,
        'H2O': data[24 if auth_id == 1 else 15],
        'CO2': 0.01
    }
    zr_ppm = 91.224*1000000.0*data[22 if auth_id == 1 else 13]/100.0/123.218
    zr_ppm_err = 91.224*1000000.0*data[23 if auth_id == 1 else 14]/100.0/123.218
    result = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_ppm=zr_ppm,
    ↪tmax=2000.0, p=p)
    result_l = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_ppm=zr_ppm-zr_
    ↪ppm_err, tmax=2000.0, p=p)
    result_h = zircon_geothermometer(use_composition=compo, ref_Zr_ppm=zr_ppm+zr_
    ↪ppm_err, tmax=2000.0, p=p)
    T_meas.append(t)
    T_estm.append(result)
    T_estm_l.append(result_l)
    T_estm_h.append(result_h)
    main_plt.errorbar(zr_ppm, t, xerr=zr_ppm_err, fmt='ro')
    main_plt.errorbar(zr_ppm, result[0],
        yerr=np.array([[result[0]-result[1]], [result[2]-result[0]]]), fmt=
    ↪'co')
    main_plt.errorbar(zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err, result_l[0],
        yerr=np.array([[result_l[0]-result_l[1]], [result_l[2]-result_
    ↪l[0]]]), fmt='y,')
    main_plt.errorbar(zr_ppm+zr_ppm_err, result_h[0],
        yerr=np.array([[result_h[0]-result_h[1]], [result_h[2]-result_
    ↪h[0]]]), fmt='y,')
    main_plt.plot(np.array([zr_ppm, zr_ppm]), np.array([t, result[0]]), 'k--')
    main_plt.plot(np.array([zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err, zr_ppm, zr_ppm+zr_ppm_err]), np.
    ↪array([result_l[1], result[1], result_h[1]]), 'y-')
    main_plt.plot(np.array([zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err, zr_ppm, zr_ppm+zr_ppm_err]), np.
    ↪array([result_l[2], result[2], result_h[2]]), 'y-')
    main_plt.fill(np.array([zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err, zr_ppm, zr_ppm+zr_ppm_err, zr_
    ↪ppm+zr_ppm_err, zr_ppm, zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err, zr_ppm-zr_ppm_err]),
    ↪np.array([result_l[2], result[2], result_h[2], result_h[1], result[1],
    ↪result_l[1], result_l[2]]),
        color=mcolors.CSS4_COLORS['lightyellow'])
#
inset_plt = fig.add_axes([0.5, 0.2, 0.35, 0.35])
inset_plt.plot(np.array(T_meas), np.array(T_estm)[: ,0], 'ro')
inset_plt.errorbar(np.array(T_meas), np.array(T_estm)[: ,0],
    ↪yerr=[np.array(T_estm)[: ,0]-np.array(T_estm)[: ,1], np.array(T_
    ↪estm)[: ,2]-np.array(T_estm)[: ,0]], fmt='ro')

inset_plt.set_xlabel('T °C, reported')
inset_plt.set_ylabel('T °C, estimated')
#
main_plt.set_ylabel('T °C')
main_plt.set_xlabel('Zr (PPM)')
if plot_watson and not plot_boenke:
    main_plt.set_xlim([0., 4000.])
    main_plt.set_ylim([690., 1100.])
    inset_plt.set_xlim([690., 1100.])
    inset_plt.set_ylim([690., 1100.])
    inset_plt.plot(np.array([690, 1100]), np.array([690, 1100]), 'k-')

```

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```

main_plt.set_title('Watson and Harrison, 1983, temperature recovery')
fig.savefig("WandH_1983_temperature_recovery.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
elif not plot_watson and plot_boenke:
    main_plt.set_xlim([0., 4000.])
    main_plt.set_ylim([700., 1100.])
    inset_plt.set_xlim([700., 1100.])
    inset_plt.set_ylim([700., 1100.])
    inset_plt.plot(np.array([700, 1100]), np.array([700, 1100]), 'k-')
    main_plt.set_title('Boehnke et al., 2013, temperature recovery')
    fig.savefig("Boehnke_2013_temperature_recovery.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
else:
    inset_plt.plot(np.array([700, 1250]), np.array([700, 1250]), 'k-')
    main_plt.set_title('Temperature recovery')
    fig.savefig("Temperature_recovery.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()

```

16.14 Statistics of calibrant temperature recovery

```

low = np.array(T_estm[:,0] - np.array(T_estm[:,1])
hgh = np.array(T_estm[:,2] - np.array(T_estm[:,0])
low_l = np.array(T_estm_l[:,0] - np.array(T_estm_l[:,1])
hgh_l = np.array(T_estm_l[:,2] - np.array(T_estm_l[:,0])
low_h = np.array(T_estm_h[:,0] - np.array(T_estm_h[:,1])
hgh_h = np.array(T_estm_h[:,2] - np.array(T_estm_h[:,0])
if plot_watson and not plot_boenke:
    pass
elif not plot_watson and plot_boenke:
    low = low[:-4]
    hgh = hgh[:-4]
    low_l = low_l[:-4]
    hgh_l = hgh_l[:-4]
    low_h = low_h[:-4]
    hgh_h = hgh_h[:-4]
print ('5% quartile T (ave Zr):', -np.average(low), '95%', np.average(hgh))
print ('5% quartile T (low Zr):', -np.average(low_l), '95%', np.average(hgh_l))
print ('5% quartile T (hgh Zr):', -np.average(low_h), '95%', np.average(hgh_h))

```

```

err = np.array(T_estm[:,0] - np.array(T_meas)
err_l = np.array(T_estm_l[:,0] - np.array(T_meas)
err_h = np.array(T_estm_h[:,0] - np.array(T_meas)
if plot_watson and not plot_boenke:
    pass
elif not plot_watson and plot_boenke:
    err = err[:-4]
    err_l = err_l[:-4]
    err_h = err_h[:-4]
print ('T est ave (ave Zr) - T meas', np.average(err), '+', np.std(err))
print ('T est ave (low Zr) - T meas', np.average(err_l), '+', np.std(err_l))
print ('T est ave (hgh Zr) - T meas', np.average(err_h), '+', np.std(err_h))

```


7-PHASE EQUILIBRIA: MELTS LIQUID MODEL WITH ZRSIO₄

Associated solution model:

Zircon Geothermometry and Zr-mineral saturation in natural magmas using rhyolite-MELTS

Components:	Species:	Reaction:	Variable:	Component:	Species X:
SiO2	SiO2			n_1	X_1
TiO2	TiO2		r_1	n_2	X_2
Al2O3	Al2O3		r_2	n_3	X_3
Fe2O3	Fe2O3		r_3	n_4	X_4
MgCr2O4	MgCr2O4		r_4	n_5	X_5
Fe2SiO4	Fe2SiO4		r_5	n_6	X_6
MnSi1/2O2	MnSi1/2O2		r_6	n_7	X_7
Mg2SiO4	Mg2SiO4		r_7	n_8	X_8
NiSi1/2O2	NiSi1/2O2		r_8	n_9	X_9
CoSi1/2O2	CoSi1/2O2		r_9	n_{10}	X_{10}
CaSiO3	CaSiO3		r_{10}	n_{11}	X_{11}
Na2SiO3	Na2SiO3		r_{11}	n_{12}	X_{12}
KAlSiO4	KAlSiO4		r_{12}	n_{13}	X_{13}
Ca3(PO4)2	Ca3(PO4)2		r_{13}	n_{14}	X_{14}
H2O	H2O		r_{14}	n_{15}	X_{15}
CO2	CO2		r_{15}	n_{16}	X_{16}
ZrSiO4	ZrSiO4		r_{16}	n_{17}	X_{17}
	CaCO3	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{CaSiO}_3 = \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_1		X_{18}
	Na4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 2\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 = \text{Na}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{SiO}_2$	s_2		X_{19}
	K4ZrSi2O8	$\text{ZrSiO}_4 + 4\text{KAlSiO}_4 = \text{K}_4\text{ZrSi}_2\text{O}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{SiO}_2$	s_3		X_{20}

17.1 Gibbs energy minimization (fixed T, P, bulk composition)

Closed system; crystallization of a rhyolitic liquid using rhyolite-MELTS 1.1 + Zr-model

```
import numpy as np
import scipy.optimize as opt
import scipy.linalg as lin
import sys
from thermoengine import core, phases, model, equilibrate
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=FutureWarning)
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import scipy as sci
%matplotlib inline
```

```
model_working_dir = "working"
%cd {model_working_dir}
from pyximport import install
install()
import rMELTS_ZR
import zirconium_minerals
modelDB_ZR_min = model.Database(database="CoderModule", calib=True,
                                phase_tuple=('zirconium_minerals', {
                                    'Zrc':['zircon', 'pure'],
                                    'Bdd':['baddeleyite', 'pure']
                                }))
modelDB_ZR_liq = model.Database(database="CoderModule", calib=True,
                                phase_tuple=('rMELTS_ZR', {
                                    'liq':['Liquid', 'solution']
                                }))
%cd ..
```

```
modelDB_ZR_min.phase_info
```

```
modelDB_ZR_liq.phase_info
```

17.2 Read in parameter estimates from first calibration notebook

```
import pickle
with open('calib_params.pickle', 'rb') as f:
    params_stored = pickle.load(f)
for i,x in enumerate(params_stored):
    rMELTS_ZR.cy_Liquid_rMELTS_ZR_set_param_value(i, x)
```

17.3 Create phases for equilibrium assemblages

```
src_obj = core.get_src_object('EquilibrateUsingMELTSv102')
modelDB = model.Database()
Liquid = modelDB_ZR_liq.get_phase('liq')
Feldspar = modelDB.get_phase('Fsp')
Quartz = modelDB.get_phase('Qz')
Spinel = modelDB.get_phase('SplS')
Opx = modelDB.get_phase('Opx')
RhomOx = modelDB.get_phase('Rhom')
Zircon = modelDB_ZR_min.get_phase('Zrc')
Baddeleyite = modelDB_ZR_min.get_phase('Bdd')
```

The MELTS 1.0.2 water model.

```
Water = phases.PurePhase('WaterMelts', 'H2O', calib=False)
```

The MELTS 1.1.x fluid (H2O, CO2) model.

```
Fluid = phases.SolutionPhase('FluidDuan', 'Fld')
```

17.4 Define elements in system and phases in system

```
elm_sys = ['H', 'C', 'O', 'Na', 'Mg', 'Al', 'Si', 'P', 'K', 'Ca', 'Ti', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Fe', 'Co', 'Ni',
           ↪ 'Zr']
#phs_sys = [Liquid, Feldspar, Quartz, Spinel, Opx, RhomOx, Zircon, Baddeleyite, Water]
phs_sys = [Liquid, Feldspar, Quartz, Spinel, Opx, RhomOx, Zircon, Baddeleyite, Fluid]
```

17.5 Composition of the system

This is a high-silica rhyolite

```
grm_oxides = {
    'SiO2': 77.5,
    'TiO2': 0.08,
    'Al2O3': 12.5,
    'Fe2O3': 0.207,
    'Cr2O3': 0.0,
    'FeO': 0.473,
    'MnO': 0.0,
    'MgO': 0.03,
    'NiO': 0.0,
    'CoO': 0.0,
    'CaO': 0.43,
    'Na2O': 3.98,
    'K2O': 4.88,
    'P2O5': 0.0,
    'H2O': 5.5,
    'CO2': 0.0005
```

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```
}
Zr_ppm = 100
```

Cast this composition as moles of elements for input to the Equilibrate class

```
tot_grm_oxides = 0.0
for key in grm_oxides.keys():
    tot_grm_oxides += grm_oxides[key]
mol_oxides = core.chem.format_mol_oxide_comp(grm_oxides, convert_grams_to_moles=True)
mol_elm = core.chem.mol_oxide_to_elem(mol_oxides)
elm_ref = np.zeros(107)
for i, sym in enumerate(
    ['Si', 'Ti', 'Al', 'Fe', 'Cr', 'Mn', 'Mg', 'Ni', 'Co', 'Ca', 'Na', 'K', 'P', 'H',
    'C', 'O']):
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(sym)
    elm_ref[index] = mol_elm[i]
#
elm = np.copy(elm_ref)
wtZrO2 = 123.218*Zr_ppm/91.224/1000000.0
wtZrO2 *= tot_grm_oxides + wtZrO2
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('Zr')] += wtZrO2/123.218
elm[core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index('O')] += wtZrO2*2.0/123.218
blk_cmp = []
for x in elm_sys:
    index = core.chem.PERIODIC_ORDER.tolist().index(x)
    blk_cmp.append(elm[index])
blk_cmp = np.array(blk_cmp)
```

17.6 Instantiate class instance and run calculation

```
equil = equilibrate.Equilibrate(elm_sys, phs_sys)
```

```
t = 762.0 + 273.15
p = 1750.0
state = equil.execute(t, p, bulk_comp=blk_cmp, debug=0, stats=False)
state.print_state()
```

Set up a function to help with plotting results

```
phs_mass = []
phs_name = []
temperatures = []
def plot_data():
    global phs_mass, phs_name, temperatures
    phs_state = state.properties()
    temperatures.append(state.temperature - 273.15)
    masses = []
    names = []
    for key in phs_state.keys():
        if phs_state[key] == 'stable':
            names.append(key)
```

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```
        masses.append(state.properties(phase_name=key, props='Mass'))
    phs_name.append(names)
    phs_mass.append(masses)
plot_data()
```

Run a sequence ...

```
for i in range(1,61):
    state = equil.execute(t-i/5.0, p, state=state, debug=0, stats=False)
    state.print_state()
    plot_data()
```

Massage output into a suitable state for plotting

```
temperatures = np.array(temperatures)
phs_name_unique = []
for lst in phs_name:
    phs_name_unique += lst
phs_name_unique = list(sorted((set(phs_name_unique))))
phs_name_unique.remove('System')
phs_mass_unique = []
for i,lst in enumerate(phs_mass):
    masses = np.zeros(len(phs_name_unique))
    for j,name in enumerate(phs_name[i]):
        if name is not 'System':
            ind = phs_name_unique.index(name)
            masses[ind] = lst[j]
    phs_mass_unique.append(masses)
phs_mass_unique = np.array(phs_mass_unique)
zr_onset = 0.0
zr_ind = phs_name_unique.index('zircon')
for i,tval in enumerate(temperatures):
    if phs_mass_unique[i,zr_ind] > 0.0:
        zr_onset = tval
        break
```

17.7 Plot results of sequence

```
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
for i,name in enumerate(phs_name_unique):
    plt.plot(temperatures, phs_mass_unique[:,i], label=name)
plt.plot(np.array([zr_onset, zr_onset]), np.array([0,105]), 'k--', label='zircon_
↳liquidus')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

```
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(15,10))
plt.stackplot(temperatures, phs_mass_unique.T, labels=phs_name_unique)
plt.plot(np.array([zr_onset, zr_onset]), np.array([0,105]), 'k--', label='zircon_
↳liquidus')
plt.legend(loc='upper right')
```

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```
plt.title("High-silica rhyolite")
plt.xlabel("Temperature °C")
plt.ylabel("Mass (g)")
plt.xlim(750, 762)
plt.ylim(0,105)
fig.savefig("MELTS-zr-rhyolite.pdf", bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
```


Part IV

References Cited

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

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